

**Factors influencing the success of outsourcing in e-governance- an
empirical investigation of public services in United Kingdom**

Submitted by

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Dedication

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Abstract

The technological advancement is compelling the governments around the world to adopt e-governance models. Particularly after the pandemic, the pressure to offer e-services has significantly increased in public organizations. In UK, the government is showing great interest towards investing on e-services to implement their e-governance model. However, resource constraints inhibit them from managing e-services in-house, and therefore, they are considering outsourcing e-services to the private sector. Although, public firms are considering outsourcing a viable opportunity to deliver e-services without expanding organizational competencies and capacities, but high outsourcing failure rate due to ineffective relational governance has become a major cause of concern. This research study was conducted to explore how public firms in UK can enhance relational governance effectiveness to increase the e-service outsourcing success chances. To do this, the researcher conducted empirical investigation into three public firms and their vendors that are currently involved in outsourcing arrangements. Based on survey and interview findings, the researcher provided knowledge about the people (perceptions, commitment, co-operative behaviour) and management (trust and communication management mechanisms) related factors that influence the quality of relationships with the outsourcing partners. The study proposed a conceptual framework that explained how public firms can ensure effective relational governance by focusing on trust and commitment. Effective communication and co-operative behaviour emerged as strong trust predictors, and mutual trust between outsourcing partners encouraged parties to strengthen their commitment to fulfil contractual obligations and share valuable knowledge with each other. The knowledge sharing and strengthened commitment directly determined the relational governance effectiveness, which ultimately enhanced the e-service outsourcing success chances. The study proposes recommendations that public firms in UK can consider developing trust, strengthen commitment and enhance their relational governance to achieve desired outsourcing objectives. The study has some limitations as well that open venues for further research. These future research suggestions are presented at the end of this report.

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Chapter 1 – Introduction

1.1 Overview and Context

The increasing demand for service delivery in public and private organisations forced these organisations to improve the service provision to their customers (Afonasova *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, the outsourcing choice was an effective way to improve the quality of these services while leaving the public sector to concentrate on its core business. (Trushchenko *et al.* 2021).

In the public sector, e-services (electronically provided services) are defined as the services offered by various public service organisations through the Internet. Although the advancement in information and communication technologies has brought revolutionary changes in the public sector's service delivery mechanisms (Scupola, 2008), according to the scholars like Golubeva and Gilenko (2010) and Sirkemaa (2010), the e-services development has not been as rapid as in the e-business area. Moreover, in the public sector, the management has to cross various structural and administrative barriers to create value for the e-service users. In order to avoid such administrative complexities, public organisations tend to outsource e-services to the private sector (Nehemia *et al.*, 2019). There has been unprecedented growth in the outsourcing of e-services during the last two decades. The e-service outsourcing trend has profoundly influenced the quality of e-services (Mahalik, 2016). P 269

Dickinson and Yates (2021) argued that to enhance resilience, companies are seeking ways to decrease the negative impact of the pandemic through service outsourcing. Macro-environmental forces are essential in pushing companies towards outsourcing (Marco-Simó *et al.*, 2020). For instance, in the post-pandemic world, state policies have increased the cost of running businesses, which is further increasing the attractiveness of considering outsourcing options to manage business operations, as firms find it more cost-efficient to outsource the business operations instead of investing resources to expand organisational capacity needed to manage those operations (Dickinson and Yates, 2021).

Other than state policies, the intensifying competition and development of information and communication technologies further encourage service organisations to outsource

their services (Hoque *et al.*, 2019). Information technology outsourcing is gradually becoming an integral component of business strategies because it enables client organisations to access outside expertise, reduce IT functions costs and share the risks with their outsourcing partners (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2016). The outsourcing option is desirable to large-scale organisations engaging in information technology outsourcing to access worldwide capabilities (Varajão *et al.*, 2017). Large-scale business organisations free up their resources by outsourcing information technology operations and focusing on their core competencies, enhancing the firm's performance and helping management achieve the desired strategic objectives (Varajão *et al.*, 2017; Gonzalez *et al.*, 2016).

The fast-paced development of information and communication technology ICT increased the interest towards using these technologies to improve public service responsiveness, performance, and quality (Jansen and Ølnes, 2016; Hoque *et al.*, 2019). However, resource constraints, lack of expertise and drive to maximize service excellence motivate many public service firms to outsource their e-services to the private sector (Lindgren and van Veenstra, 2018).

Modern governance is shared governance that involves policy implementation apportioned between private and government sector actors. Public organisations tend to routinely offload information technology, park management, medical services, prison management, water treatment, and other e-services to the private sector (Potter, 2022). The pandemic-led digitalization has further increased the scope of outsourcing e-services to the private sector, and the outsourcing trend is being replicated at the federal level (Dickinson and Yates, 2021). There is an ongoing debate about whether private or public sectors offer e-services more efficiently and effectively (Michaels 2017 as cited in Leipo, 2018).

Even though outsourcing has significant benefits for e-services quality (Hoque *et al.*, 2019) but on the other hand some serious challenges arise during the outsourcing process (Hoque *et al.*, 2019), such as the generation of new relationships where not paying attention to this relationship may cause the failure of e-services outsourcing (Mahalik, 2010).

A recent literature review suggests that outsourcing e-services to the private sector involves inherent risks. A look over global statistics suggests that governments' IT outsourcing projects meet a high failure rate. For instance, in the USA, less than 50 per cent of IT outsourcing from the public to the private sector is rated successful. It has

delivered the expected benefits to the client organisations (Mehta and Mehta, 2017). One of the critical reasons for the low success rate of outsourcing projects is the need for more understanding of the factors that determine e-service outsourcing success (Bates, 2022). Studies like Mihalache and Mihalache (2020) and Rahman *et al.* (2021) consider inadequate relationship management capabilities among the most common reasons for outsourcing failure. Public organisations continuously invest in e-service outsourcing despite failing to accomplish the desired objectives (Mehta and Mehta, 2017; Oshri *et al.*, 2019).

Bates (2022) said that the commonly cited reason is that organisational leaders need to understand the factors required for outsourcing success. The management-related factors influencing the client-vendor relationship are considered more robust determinants of outsourcing success or failure than technical factors (Mehta and Mehta, 2017; Oshri *et al.*, 2019). This inability to focus on the relationship governance factors results in a high outsourcing failure rate (Oshri *et al.*, 2019). This empirical research aims to critically evaluate the factors that influence effective relationship management in outsourcing electronically provided services (e-services).

Effective relationship management fits with relational governance, as according to Zaheer and Venkatraman (1995), effective relational governance refers to the "*inter-firm exchanges which include significant relationship-specific assets, combined with a high level of inter-organisational trust*" and "*is embodied in both the structure and the process of an inter-organisational relationship*" (Zaheer and Venkatraman, 1995, p. 374). This relational governance definition suggests that effective, trust-based relationship management is critical for successful inter-firm exchanges, which may include the exchange of relationship-specific assets. In the outsourcing context, e-service outsourcing frequently requires the exchange of relationship-specific assets, and trust provides a solid basis for these relational exchanges, which can only be ensured through effective relationship management strategies and practices (Strieborny and Kukenova, 2016). An example of relationship-specific assets includes vendors' willingness to invest in the customization of products/services to meet the purchaser's specific needs. As noted by Rai *et al.* (2012), the value of these exchanges is usually low in alternative uses. However, it has high intangible value in existing relationships, as this 'additional' value supports ongoing business relationships (Zaheer and Venkatraman, 1995). These arguments indicate that effective relational governance in e-service outsourcing depends on trust and effective relationship management.

Therefore, it is essential to explore the factors that determine trust and positively influence the relationship management abilities of parties involved in business relationships. Next, the researcher discusses how previous scholars have defined the relational governance mechanisms to understand better how relational governance is linked with trust and relationship management in an outsourcing context.

Relational governance mechanisms denote the mechanisms that support business contracts through effective collaboration and practical relationship management tools and techniques (Goo and Huang, 2008). According to Gill (2009), all economic and business exchanges happen in a relational context, so studying the relational governance mechanisms is essential for e-service outsourcing success. Huber *et al.* (2013) explained relational governance as a governance kind in which the personal relations of parties are strongly intertwined with the economic and business exchanges. Personal relations indicate social norms like trust, solidarity and cooperation. As noted by Goo and Huang (2008), governance mechanisms can be categorized into two forms-formal governance mechanisms and relational governance mechanisms.

Formal governance mechanisms refer to authoritative and contractual governance (Caniels and Gelderman, 2010), whereas relational governance mechanisms refer to trust's role in successful business relations (Cai *et al.*, 2011). Liu *et al.* (2020) defined relational governance as establishing different management strategies and behavioral routines to develop self-enforcing, informal safeguards in collaborative relationships (Zaheer and Venkatraman, 1995). Liu *et al.* (2020) defined relational governance as the extent to which management strategies successfully achieve the desired collaborative behavior in business exchange relationships. Baker *et al.* (2002) proposed a similar relational governance definition by stating that relational governance is the governance of business/economic transactions through relational norms. The authors also defined relational norms by stating that relational norms denote the social regulations and processes that exist due to the counterpart party's relations in the transactions (Baker *et al.*, 2002).

All these definitions consider trust the most important factor, as all exchange relations are built over it. Based on these definitions, the current study defines relational governance mechanisms as the exchange mechanisms that increase outsourcing success chances by increasing trust and encouraging the flow of relation-specific assets to strengthen the collaboration among parties (vendor and client) involved in the exchange

process. With this definition, the main emphasis is trust and collaboration between vendor and client organisations in the e-service outsourcing context.

Out of formal and relational governance mechanisms, the current research study focuses on the relational governance mechanisms because, according to some previous studies (Meng *et al.*, 2007; Mahalik, 2010), ineffective handling of the relational governance mechanisms accounts for most outsourcing failure cases. Still, the current literature offers insufficient empirical evidence to understand how e-service outsourcing initiatives can succeed by focusing on the right tools and techniques that may make relational governance easier (Baker *et al.*, 2002).

E-services can be broadly categorized into four types- e-services directed to the citizens, businesses, employees, and government. The research context is narrowed down by focusing on the outsourced e-services offered by the public sector to the citizens (Mukamurenzi *et al.*, 2019). The specific focus on this specific type of outsourcing is that g2c e-governance is increasingly being used to strengthen the relationship between government and citizens through the efficient delivery of services through digital platforms (Mukamurenzi *et al.*, 2019). However, the high failure rate of g2c e-service initiatives indicates the need to increase the knowledge about factors that determine the success of such initiatives (Meng *et al.*, 2007; Mahalik, 2010). Therefore, the current study has narrowed its focus to this particular type of e-services. The research context is further narrowed down by applying the geographic filter, as the empirical investigation is conducted in a single country- the UK. The UK has been selected for two reasons. First, it is easier to collect data from the UK as a researcher has some personal connections that can be utilized to draw responses from the targeted participants. Second, the findings of some recent reports (The House of Commons, 2018; Wearden, 2018; BBC, 2018) indicate that the British government currently faces issues managing its e-service outsourcing relationships, resulting in high e-service g2c outsourcing failure rates.

1.2 Problem discussion

Governments outsource the e-services to external parties that could share the risks and offer similar quality or even better services to the people at a comparatively lesser cost (Kesan *et al.*, 2019). This outsourcing motivation validates the economic principles, which consider outsourcing to achieve economic objectives (cost reduction and productivity/efficiency). However, the analysis of the real-world outsourcing examples shows that achieving the economic objectives through e-service outsourcing is more complex and requires effective management of the new relationships that are borne after the outsourcing decision (de Carvalho *et al.*, 2018). The inability to handle the new business relationships can cause an array of thorny problems that could not only hamper the organizational performance, but the resultant complications in the core operations can also offset the cost savings achieved through outsourcing (Nehemia *et al.*, 2019).

Usually, organizations outsource activities to maintain a relational distance from the outsourced function and keep focus on the core competencies. However, these expectations mask the fact that even though outsourcing simplifies some managerial/administrative functions, it introduces some complex, novel relationships between vendors and outsourcing organizations (de Carvalho *et al.*, 2018). In some cases, the new relationships seek more attention from management than required when outsourced functions are handled in-house (Gewald and Helbig, 2006). Scholars like Gewald and Helbig (2006) and de Carvalho *et al.* (2018) argue that before outsourcing services, organizations must understand how new relationships can be effectively managed so that the challenges associated with outsourcing may not outweigh the promised/expected benefits.

Though extensive research is available to understand the motives behind organizations' outsourcing decisions, more knowledge is needed to understand how outsourcing can create value for all partners to ensure outsourcing success (Ahmed, 2018). Within the new relationships associated with e-service outsourcing, the relationship with the vendor holds critical importance in the outsourcing context, which needs to be carefully handled to increase the outsourcing success chances. Examples of other outsourcing relationships are- technicians, top management of vendor organizations, middle managers/representatives responsible for relationship dealing,

and customers. Therefore, it is essential to understand the relational governance mechanisms from different contexts so that organizations can develop healthy, long-term outsourcing relationships (Zheng *et al.*, 2008). Reviewing recent scholarly studies like Young *et al.* (2020) and de Carvalho *et al.* (2018) further reveals that the relational governance understanding in the outsourcing context needs to be more straightforward for academics and practitioners. The current research study attempted to fill the identified literature gap by exploring the relational governance and relationship management dynamics in the e-service outsourcing context.

In the UK, e-government outsourcing has become essential to delivering local and central e-services. The House of Commons (2018) report states that the UK government spends around £251.5 billion annually on contracting and outsourcing different services. Despite the UK government's strong commitment to innovation in its e-governance model, it has been unable to learn from its previous mistakes. The collapse of Carillion provides a recent example of poor government service outsourcing. Carillion was a British multinational construction and facility management services company which collapsed due to ineffective e-governance outsourcing management, resulting in a loss of £148m (BBC, 2018). Poor relational governance and relationship management during outsourcing government services was considered one of the most critical factors behind Carillion's outsourcing failure (Wearden, 2018). The need to revive the trust in the government's ability to deal with the private sector during outsourcing effectively has been highlighted by Rt Hon David Lidington MP- the Minister for Cabinet Office, as a series of outsourcing failure scandals triggered a widespread crisis of confidence in the British government's dependence on the private sector to deliver e-services. Lu, Zhong and Mei (2009) agreed by commenting that up until now, it is unclear why government decides whether a particular e-service needs to be outsourced.

Although Treasury has developed a process to assist the outsourcing decisions by stating how outsourcing should be managed, the government often needs to follow the offered guidelines, which can be a reason for poor relational governance, leading to outsourcing failure (House of Commons, 2018). This research work has attempted to understand which factors enhance relational governance, what is the impact of relational governance on e-service outsourcing success, why governments decide to outsource e-services (by identifying the environmental tendencies for outsourcing e-

services), and how much outsourcing decisions can be made successful by effectively handling the relational governance aspects.

Based on the overall analysis, relational governance in the e-services outsourcing context is an important subject area that could be explored from different dimensions. This research explored the relationship management practices that public service firms can adopt to develop positive and healthy relationships with the concerned authorities so that management could yield the best results from their outsourcing decision. The multidimensionality of the chosen research area required the researcher to adopt the mixed research methodology. The quantitative research methods were selected to evaluate the effect of each relationship management factor (identified through qualitative exploration) on outsourcing success. On the other hand, the qualitative research methods were selected to conduct an in-depth exploration of the people (perceptions towards trust, cooperation, commitment and knowledge sharing) and management (communication and trust-building strategies) factors that determine the quality and strength of firms' relationship with internal and external outsourcing participants.

1.3 Research questions

This research work has attempted to answer the following research questions:

- 1- Understand which factors enhance the relational governance
- 2- What is the impact of relational governance on e-service outsourcing success?
- 3- Why governments decide to outsource the e-services (by identifying the environmental tendencies for outsourcing e-services).
- 4- how can such an outsourcing decision be successful by effectively handling the relational governance aspects?

1.4 Research gaps

This research has been undertaken to fill the following knowledge gaps:

Gap 1

Lioliou *et al.* (2014) and Benítez-Ávila *et al.* (2018) noted that relational governance has become an essential concern for firms that outsource their e-services to third-party vendors. It is because poor relationship management is cited as one of the factors for outsourcing failure. However, despite the high importance of the issue for the practitioners, academic scholars have paid inadequate attention towards conceptualizing the relational governance term in the e-service outsourcing context (Lioliou *et al.*, 2014; Mathrani and Mathrani, 2016). This knowledge area is under-researched, so practitioners must rely on untested/ subjective recommendations about the best practices for effective relationship management that may lead to outsourcing success.

Gap 2

To understand how outsourcing success could be improved through effective relational governance, it is essential to explore the factors that determine trust and strengthen the commitment of outsourcing partners to fulfil each other's expectations (Huber *et al.*, 2013). Moreover, as noted by Schoenherr, Narayanan and Narasimhan (2015), in most cases, the previous studies explored trust from the client organization's perspective, and further research is needed to understand how trust is formed and how it influences the outsourcing success from both client and vendor organizations' perspectives. In response to this literature gap, the current research study explored the importance of trust in determining outsourcing success by taking the views of both vendor and client organizations involved in e-governance outsourcing relationships in the UK.

Gap 3

Recent empirical research by Fehrenbacher and Wiener (2019) explored the influence of knowledge-sharing willingness and commitment on IT outsourcing success and found both factors to be significant success predictors. However, this study was conducted on private IT firms. The small sample size (experiment conducted on only

198 IT professionals involved in outsourcing relationships) and lack of specificity (by collecting data from a specific region) affect the generalizability of these results. Some other empirical studies like Karimi-Alagheband and Rivard (2020), Sanchis-Pedregosa and Machuca (2018) and Zhu *et al.* (2017) also considered strong relational governance and effective relationship management critical for successfully achieving the desired outcomes from outsourcing projects. However, the literature review indicates the need for more context-specific research to understand how relationship management factors enhance the overall relational governance and ultimately increase the success of e-service outsourcing contracts in the UK.

Gap 4

There could be different external environmental and organizational factors that could motivate organizations to make outsourcing decisions. Although previous scholarly studies have attempted to identify various environmental tendencies that encourage business organizations to make outsourcing decisions, only limited literature is available in the specific context of public organizations that decide to outsource their e-services to a specialized vendor from the private sector. The high contextual difference between the private and public sectors decreases the generalizability of these arguments for public organizations. It increases the need for more research to understand the related aspects associated with public enterprises' decision to outsource e-services in the UK. On another world, the current study explored why organizations make outsourcing decisions and how the motives behind making outsourcing decisions influence the relationship between relational governance and outsourcing success.

1.5 Research rationale and significance

1.5.1 *Research rationale/motivation*

An increasing number of e-governance outsourcing failure cases in the UK provide the rationale for doing this research. High e-governance outsourcing failure rate is compelling the British government to address the causes of repeated outsourcing failures (Sasse, 2019). However, the review of e-governance outsourcing literature reports several reasons (like contractual, political, technical, environmental, legal and management-related factors) responsible for the outsourcing failure; considering all possible aspects into a single research work can be challenging and may widen the scope of this research (Hilesand Hon, 2016). Therefore, the researcher has focused on the relational governance mechanisms involved in e-governance outsourcing. The rationale for focusing on this dimension is that according to recent scholarly studies (like Enlow and Ertel 2006 and Lioliou *et al.* 2014), poor relationship management is among the most critical causes of e-services outsourcing failure.

Lioliou *et al.* (2014) noted that poor e-service outsourcing could be associated with ineffective relational governance due to inadequate knowledge of the technical and non-technical factors influencing outsourcing success. Lack of trust between outsourcing partners is cited as a common reason for ineffective relational governance (Lee *et al.*, 2008) because distrust between outsourcing partners hinders the knowledge sharing between outsourcing partners, weakens the partners' commitment, and ultimately affects the relational governance, which is an essential determinant of outsourcing success (Lee and Choi, 2011). These arguments suggest that trust holds central importance in ensuring effective relational governance. By taking the motivation from this argument, the researcher has placed trust as a central factor (as shown in the framework) that leads towards strong relational governance, which is connected with e-service outsourcing success.

To sum up, the growing strategic importance of e-service outsourcing and relationship management complications associated with the outsourcing decision increases the need to understand critical factors for effective relationship management. High e-service

outsourcing failure rates in the UK public sector, along with the dearth of empirical literature to understand how relational governance dimensions of e-service outsourcing can be handled, set the overall motivation basis for this research. The successful execution of this research work has theoretical and practical importance.

1.5.2 Theoretical and practical significance

By developing a framework for e-service outsourcing success through effective relationship management, the current research work makes a valuable contribution to the existing body of knowledge. By exploring the key personal and management-related factors, the study sets the direction for further research, as future researchers can use the proposed knowledge to analyse e-service outsourcing success in different contextual environments. The framework is developed by identifying the key concept from the literature, as well as from the survey and interviews with experts from the e-services outsourcing field. The study also adds a new perspective to the existing literature by exploring UK public service managers' perceptions, experiences and opinions about relational governance mechanisms that lead towards e-service outsourcing success. A valuable addition to existing knowledge will be conceptualising relational governance in the e-service outsourcing context, which is reported to be an under-explored research area that seeks further attention (Lioliou *et al.*, 2014; Mathrani and Mathrani, 2016).

Concerning practical importance, the study is attempting to propose recommendations to improve practices for effective relationship management that may lead towards outsourcing success. The practitioners can learn from the findings how factors like communication, cooperative behaviour, trust, knowledge sharing, and commitment influence relational governance effectiveness, which leads towards e-service outsourcing success. Findings to also aim to understand the extent to which effective relational governance influences e-service outsourcing success chances.

Practitioners may review the results to understand how trust could be developed by adopting effective communication and cooperation strategies. Effective communication and cooperation strategies are discussed in detail. Their impact on the trust between

vendor and client organisation has also been measured to achieve more reliable and practically applicable results. Although literature (e.g. Lee *et al.*, 2008; Marchewka and Oruganti, 2013) highlights the importance of creating mutual dependency in a positive way to promote knowledge sharing, not enough empirical evidence is available to confirm the moderating impact of knowledge sharing on trust-knowledge sharing relationship. Practitioners can review the proposed results to understand 'how' and 'to what extent' they can promote knowledge sharing by creating a mutually dependent relationship. Some challenges of mutual dependency are also discussed, and possible solutions for overcoming those challenges to maximise the positive impact of mutual dependency have also been explored, further increasing the practical value of this research.

The importance of trust commitment has been frequently discussed in the outsourcing literature, but more context-specific guidance is needed for public service organisations in the UK. The current study guides in this regard in two ways- 1) by qualitatively exploring 'how' trust strengthens the commitment between outsourcing partners, 'what' challenges firms face in fostering trust and commitment, and 'how' trust and commitment could be enhanced to improve the overall relational governance, and 2) by quantitatively measuring the impact of trust on the commitment to understand the extent to which firms' efforts to develop trust between outsourcing partners could be translated into a commitment to accomplishing the shared goals.

The study also discusses critical knowledge-sharing mechanisms management can focus on to enhance overall relational governance. Due to the mixed method design, the researcher explored the importance of knowledge sharing from multiple dimensions. First, the researcher explored different knowledge-sharing mechanisms to improve relational governance effectiveness. Second, the effect of knowledge-sharing on relational governance was measured to understand whether investment in knowledge-sharing activities brings any significant improvement in relational governance effectiveness. Proposed findings can help practitioners understand how to encourage knowledge sharing by focusing on the proper mechanisms, how associated challenges could be handled, and what relational governance outcomes they can expect through improved knowledge sharing.

Practitioners can also use the results to understand how 'trust' is perceived in vendor organisations. The study has interviewed vendor organisations to understand the importance of trust for effective relational governance from multiple perspectives. Knowledge gained from a comparative analysis of different perspectives (client versus vendor organisations) can be used to resolve possible misunderstandings and strengthen inter-organisational trust for better relational governance outcomes. Another way the proposed findings can benefit the practitioners is that study explains how environmental tendencies influence relational governance and outsourcing success. Through in-depth qualitative exploration, the study evaluated how firms' motivations to outsource e-services (like cost reduction, lack of expertise or service quality improvement) may influence inter-organisational trust and overall relational governance effectiveness.

More knowledge is needed to understand that trust between vendor and client organisations derives influence from e-service outsourcing motivations. However, studies like Rannard *et al.* (2016) and Ali *et al.* (2018) contend that contextual motivational factors behind outsourcing are essential in determining relational governance effectiveness. So, the knowledge in this regard will also be helpful for practitioners to understand how they can manage relational governance dynamics in a specific context.

Another essential theoretical and practical contribution made by current research is that based on empirical (quantitative and qualitative) evidence, it proposes an e-service outsourcing framework that explains how e-service outsourcing can be successful through effective vendor-client relationship management. The multi-case study design is adopted to achieve this research objective. The chosen case organisations are- United Kingdom Accreditation Services UKAS, Birmingham and Southend city councils. By proposing a context-specific framework, these three organisations can specifically benefit from the proposed framework to gain an in-depth understanding of how they can increase outsourcing success chances by improving relational governance mechanisms. Detailed comparative research is also conducted to highlight the key similarities and differences in how relational governance is handled in chosen city councils. This comparison further enhances the results' specificity and practical applicability in targeted contexts.

The study has developed the following research aim and objectives based on the above rationale.

1.6 Research aim

This research aims to investigate the factors and environmental tendencies that influence the decision to outsource electronic services (e-services) in public organisations to provide guidance and a framework for these organisations to facilitate the outsourcing process before and during the outsourcing decision.

Accomplishing the above research aim requires research to achieve the following objectives by conducting an empirical investigation.

1.7 Research objectives

This research is trying to achieve the following objectives:

- 1) Explore how practitioners conceptualize e-service outsourcing relational governance.
- 2) Identify the environmental tendencies that motivate public service organizations to outsource e-services.
- 3) Determine the moderating effect of environmental tendencies on relational governance and outsourcing success.
- 4) Determine the predictive power of the antecedents and outcomes (factors) of trust on relational governance effectiveness.
- 5) Explore the outsourcing success factors in light of social exchange theory and trust and commitment theory.
- 6) Propose an integrated e-service outsourcing framework that explains how effective relationship management can improve the success of e-service outsourcing collaborations.

The key research objective is to explore the nature of relational governance in the e-service outsourcing context.

The secondary interest areas of this research work are- to analyse the factors that determine relationship strength with partners involved in e-service outsourcing, evaluate the relationship between relational governance and e-service outsourcing success, and explore the environmental tendencies (e.g. specific economic, socio-economic or political motives that motivated the firm to make outsourcing decision) that motivate public service firms to outsource e-services. In this section, the researcher provides a detailed justification for each sub-research objective achieved by conducting mixed-method empirical research.

1.8 Context (Public organizations in the UK)

The specific focus on this specific type of outsourcing is that g2c e-governance is increasingly being used to strengthen the relationship between government and citizens through the efficient delivery of services through digital platforms (Mukamurenzi *et al.*, 2019). However, the high failure rate of g2c e-service initiatives indicates the need to increase the knowledge about factors that determine the success of such initiatives (Meng *et al.*, 2007; Mahalik, 2010). Therefore, the current study has narrowed its focus to this particular type of e-services. The research context is further narrowed down by applying the geographic filter, as the empirical investigation is conducted in a single country- the UK. The UK has been selected for two reasons. First, it is easier to collect data from the UK as a researcher has some personal connections that can be utilised to draw responses from the targeted participants. Second, the findings of some recent reports (like Lu *et al.*, 2009; The House of Commons, 2018; Wearden, 2018; BBC, 2018) indicate that the British government is currently facing issues in managing its e-service outsourcing relationships, resulting in high e-service g2c outsourcing failure rates.

The Three public organisations selected for the interviews are United Kingdom Accreditation Services UKAS, Birmingham city council, and Southend City Council.

The United Kingdom Accreditation Service (UKAS) is the only National Accreditation Body in the UK. UK Government recognised UKAS in assessing against nationally and internationally set standards and gives accreditation to the certifying bodies of these standards worldwide.

Birmingham City Council is a governmental body responsible for managing municipal issues of the city. Birmingham is considered the largest city in the west midlands and the second biggest city in the UK after London.

Southend or (Southend-on-Sea) City Council is a governmental body managing municipal issues. Southend City is a district in Essex, England.

Besides conducting interviews with the client organisations, the researcher conducted six interviews with the vendor organisations. These interviews were with IT contract professionals from Accenture, RTECH and Cloud Central. The interview findings are presented below by applying the thematic analysis technique. (to be edited)

1.9 Research methodology

This research study's primary focus was exploring the power of trust to predict relational governance effectiveness and e-service outsourcing success. Trust and commitment theory guided the researcher in identifying trust predictors and consequent outcomes that enhance relational governance.

As mentioned before, the study adopted a mixed methodology. Use of quantitative data guided the researcher to test the causal relationships between identified variables (that are- effective communication, cooperation, trust, knowledge sharing, commitment, relational governance and e-service outsourcing success) (Byrne and Humble, 2007), while the use of qualitative data enabled the researcher to explore the motivations for outsourcing, challenges they face in managing outsourcing relations and recommendations for increasing outsourcing success through effective relational governance. The qualitative data complemented the quantitative information by enhancing the data richness (Creswell, 1999), validating the findings obtained through quantitative research (Byrne and Humble, 2007), answering the specific part of the research objective (that is- an exploration of environmental tendencies for making outsourcing decision) that could not be effectively done through quantitative research,

and refining the tested framework through identification/discovery of new management related factors that influence trust in outsourcing relations (Byrne and Humble, 2007). The researcher collected quantitative and qualitative data by targeting a population that included three public service organisations in the UK that outsourced their e-services to the private sector with different motives (like cost, quality and non-availability of required competencies). Within targeted organisations, the study targeted middle-level managers working in the targeted public service organisations and actively engaged in managing the outsourcing relationships were the target population for conducting the quantitative survey. The interviews were also conducted with the same population segment. However, while conducting interviews, the researcher also targeted the managers from vendor organisations to take their perspectives. In both cases (client and vendor organisations), the middle-level management staff responsible for managing different relationship management dynamics was contacted. Interviews were conducted by considering the following criteria for interviewee recruitment- middle or senior management position in the targeted organisation, spent at least five years at the current organisation, and actively handled the relational governance dynamics of the e-service outsourcing contract.

Quantitative data were collected using a close-ended survey questionnaire, and qualitative data were collected using semi-structured interviewing guidelines. During interviews, the researcher asked questions like 'Why do public service firms outsource e-services' 'What were the key motivations' 'How' do such motivations influence the relational governance dynamics, 'why' is trust important in outsourcing relations? And 'what' management strategies influence the trust in outsourcing relationships. Collected quantitative data was analyzed by using SPSS. The analysis started with interpreting descriptive statistics to understand basic data patterns. Then inferential tests were run to evaluate the effect of identified factors on relational governance effectiveness and outsourcing success. The qualitative data was analyzed by applying the thematic analysis technique.

After analyzing the quantitative and qualitative data, the researcher proposed a conceptual framework by mapping key variables. A proposed conceptual framework has theoretical and practical value and is discussed in detail in light of the survey, interview and literature findings in the fifth chapter of this report.

After presenting an overview of the research methodology, the following section presents the definitions of key terms used throughout the research.

1.10 Research limitations and delimitations

This research study has limitations and delimitations that set the scope of this research and determine the extent to which the proposed findings could be applied in practical settings. A key research limitation is that outsourcing success depends on various technical, non-technical and contextual factors. However, this research focused only on the non-technical factors that influence relational governance. Another key limitation is that the researcher specifically focused on the outsourced e-services offered by the public sector to the citizens. E-services have four broad categories- e-services directed to the citizens, businesses, employees and government.

Due to the high outsourcing failure rate involving e-services directed to citizens, the current study focused on this particular category. The research scope is further narrowed down by only collecting the data from three public firms in the UK. The small sample size (client and vendor organizations) can influence the generalizability of the proposed results. Although the study adopted the mixed methodology, data was only collected from the management of client and vendor organizations, while other key stakeholders involved in outsourcing arrangements (like IT professionals and personnel involved in creating and delivering e-services) were ignored. The researcher could not collect any outsourcing data due to a lack of access to the required documents, and the accuracy of findings depends on the participant's willingness to share true and honest opinions.

The cross-sectional survey design is another limitation of this research, as the researcher captured the insights only in a single period, which presents a static view of reality, which is highly fluid and dynamic. Lastly, the researcher selected a limited set of variables influencing trust and commitment and enhancing relational governance effectiveness. More variables and contextual factors could have provided a more accurate understanding of how client and vendor organizations can foster trust and commitment to strengthen mutual relationships and increase e-service outsourcing success chances.

1.11 Definition of key terms

While writing this thesis, the researcher has used some key terms frequently repeated in all chapters. In this section, the researcher presents the definitions of key terms to help the reader understand what most repeated terms in this project mean and how they could be defined.

Key terms	Definitions	Reference
E-services	E-services are the services delivered through electronic channels. Delivery of such services require use of information and communication technologies, and e-services have three main components- service receiver, service provider and the service delivery channel.	Tambouris <i>et al.</i> , 2001, Sprecher, 2000.
E-service outsourcing	Government's decision to outsource the e-services to private firm that possesses the knowledge and capabilities to provide high quality e-services to the citizens	Tambouris <i>et al.</i> , 2001, Sprecher, 2000.
Trust	Confidence that is required to commit the valuable capabilities, competencies and resources with the outsourcing partner, and accepting the risk of exploitation and being taken advantage by the outsourcing partner	Mazzola, and Perrone, 2013; Sambasivan <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Palvia <i>et al.</i> , 2010
Contractual flexibility	Contractual flexibility refers integrating flexibility into contractual terms and conditions in a way that enables the outsourcing partners to accommodate the changes occurring in their relationships in terms of rewards and needs.	Dyer and Chu (2000)
Commitment	While outsourcing e-services, commitment refers the obligation to fulfil the contractual obligations, fulfil each other's expectations and exert full efforts to make e-service outsourcing successful.	Morgan and Hunt (1994)

Knowledge sharing	Knowledge sharing denotes the parties' willingness to share the important information with each other for accomplishment of mutual goals	Rutten <i>et al.</i> 2016
Mutual dependence	Mutual dependency reflects the dependency between organizations that arises when perceived mutual benefits are aligned with each other.	Marchewka and Oruganti, 2013
Relational governance	Management of trust-based relationships between client (government) and vendor (public sector IT firms) organizations, governance of business/economic transactions through relational norms and values, which refer social regulations and complex processes that exist due to counterpart party's relations in the transaction	Zaheer and Venkatraman (1995)
Outsourcing success	Outsourcing success is assessed by evaluating the outsourcing parties' satisfaction with the overall benefits availed through outsourcing, ability to achieve the desired benefits, considering outsourcing benefits to outweigh associated challenges, improving service quality through e-service outsourcing, client organization becoming in a better position to focus on other more important matters of strategic concern, enhancing client organization's IT competencies, and considering e-service outsourcing experience to be overall successful.	Choudhury and Sabherwal, 2003

Table 1- Defining key terms.

After presenting the definitions of key terms, next section now presents the thesis outline by explaining how overall thesis has been organized into different chapters.

1.12 Chapter summary

This research study attempts to analyse the relationship management dynamics involved in public service outsourcing. Outsourcing can be classified into different categories, such as manufacturing outsourcing, professional outsourcing, project outsourcing, process outsourcing and IT outsourcing. This research focuses on IT-enabled e-services outsourcing by public service companies to the private sector in the United Kingdom. The knowledge gained through mixed-method empirical research is used to develop a comprehensive framework for successful e-service outsourcing relationship management. The research aims to understand how public firms in the UK can successfully outsource their e-services to the private sector by improving relational governance. This research purpose is achieved by devising four key research objectives.

The first research objective is to explore how scholars and practitioners conceptualise e-service outsourcing relational governance and how conceptualisations of both sides [may/ or not] differ and support each other. The second research objective is to explore the environmental tendencies that motivate public service organisations to outsource e-services. The third research objective is to explore the factors (such as communication, cooperative behaviour, trust, knowledge sharing and commitment) that influence relational governance effectiveness, which leads towards e-service outsourcing success. The fourth research objective is to propose an e-service outsourcing framework that explains how e-service outsourcing can be made successful through effective vendor-client relationship management. These research objectives are achieved by collecting data from three public service organisations in the UK that outsourced their e-services to the private sector with different motives (like cost, quality and non-availability of required competencies). The researcher has conducted surveys and interviews with outsourcing managers in client and vendor organisations.

The proposed findings aim to help public firms in the UK understand how they can develop trust, strengthen commitment and enhance overall relational governance effectiveness to increase the e-service outsourcing success chances.

Chapter Two – Literature Review

2 Outsourcing

2.1 Outsourcing and e-services outsourcing

Despite being considered an unhealthy business practice when different businesses started using it, outsourcing gained more popularity due to its significant importance in the increasingly complicated business environment (Hira, 2020). Outsourcing is also becoming an inevitable choice for public organizations to cope with the lack of resources and expertise and the increasing cost of delivering services (Khan and Khan, 2017).

Cordella and Willcocks (2012) contend that public organizations were motivated to outsource their services for many reasons. Mainly to cut the cost and reduce the bureaucracy. Freeman and Minow (2009) adds the need for more specialized expertise, technology, human resources, and the desire to concentrate on the core business to the main outsourcing motivations in public organizations.

The political influence soon became visible, as trade unions opposed the outsourcing decision during the 1980s and 90s (Guardian, 2022). The resistance started intensifying when competition increased, resulting in salary reductions. Such resistance made outsourcing management a real challenge for public organizations, and consequently, many outsourcing contracts failed (Whitfield, 2014).

In a speech given by Tony Blair in 1977 he supported public organizations to consider outsourcing options if it is more efficient and effective than in-house service delivery (Guardian, 2022). Also, He said that what matters is to deliver high-quality services, offer the best value for money, and be held publicly accountable (Guardian, 2022). Today, the world is witnessing a renewed interest in government outsourcing, and public firms are spending time and effort choosing the right partners for their service delivery projects (Whitfield, 2014). While discussing the outsourcing history, Cordella and Willcocks (2012) contend that since the 1990s, the world has witnessed a consistent rise in government outsourcing at the local and state levels. The reports published by

state governments showed a visible increase in the variety and number of outsourcing activities (Cordella and Willcocks, 2012).

The literature also suggests that outsourcing has become an exciting research area for academic researchers during the last decade. From 2020 onwards, the push to invest in e-governance has changed outsourcing from a choice to an inevitable decision that public service organizations are making to maintain relevance in a changed business environment (Mahalik and Guru, 2020). The IT outsourcing market is proliferating and enables public firms to learn from the private sector while delivering high-quality e-services to the citizens (Mahalik and Guru, 2020).

While explaining IT outsourcing activities, Schoenherr *et al.* (2015) described outsourcing as shifting the transactions that were previously governed internally to external suppliers by developing long-term contracts and transferring operations to the vendor from the private sector.

Today, outsourcing has become a complex business activity involving various functions. Public sector organizations outsource complex operations to drive efficiency and effectiveness (Whitfield, 2014). However, outsourcing objectives can only be achieved once both vendor and client organizations recognize and manage the risks associated with IT outsourcing (Ali *et al.*, 2017). As the outsourcing trend is rising, it is grabbing the attention of multiple stakeholders whose interests are aligned with the success or failure of outsourcing decisions (Ali *et al.*, 2017). Outsourcing decisions have become more complex than ever before, as public firms today are not merely making outsourcing decisions to cut costs but have much more complex, interconnected, and broader objectives that must be clearly understood and communicated to increase outsourcing success chances (Happonen and Siljander, 2020).

As contract agreements are becoming more sophisticated, managing outsourcing relations, have become more challenging, as client and vendor organizations now have to extend their focus from technical matters to non-technical relation-building matters to avoid conflict and execute outsourcing contract in a highly complex and ever-changing environment (Dickinson and Yates, 2021).

When outsourcing relations are effectively managed, government outsourcing becomes a source of new ideas, learning new competencies, and using the knowledge to enhance

efficiency and effectiveness (Ali *et al.*, 2017; Happonen and Siljander, 2020). Outsourcing becomes more feasible when government organizations lack the human and financial capacity to invest in emerging innovative technologies. The pandemic has spurred technological innovation, and the continuously changing technological environment makes it challenging for firms to manage e-services without taking help from the private sector (Dickinson and Yates, 2021).

Siliander (2020) said that successful outsourcing enabled government organizations to free up their resources and emphasize strategic planning, core competencies, and capabilities to deliver functions in the best possible manner. Outsourcing is also being viewed to reduce government organizations' long-term structural challenges due to cultural and structural rigidity (Felisoni *et al.*, 2019). However, extensive literature confirms that these objectives can only be fully achieved by effectively managing inter-organizational (client and vendor) relationships (He and Lu, 2017).

2.2 Benefits and risks of outsourcing and e-services outsourcing

Using the latest information technology applications and other tools for providing services to citizens, businesses, and other government agencies by the government is referred to as electronic government (Nam, 2014). E-government is not merely connected with the online or IT-based interaction with the citizens but also covers the span of all government sectors (Larsson and Grönlund, 2016). Public administrations and other government sectors are transformed to an extensive capacity by using information technology through e-government (OECD, 2003). E-Government has utilized IS to improve the flow of information within and around public organizations and, in the process, improve the interaction between government and citizens (Estevez and Janowski 2013).

It is worth mentioning here that the usage of information technology in public administration has improved internal and external operating methods within and outside government institutions (Chadwick and May 2003; OECD, 2008). The OECD countries had started the usage of New Public Management (NPM) theories before the initiation of e-government (Hood, 1995). NPM management contained a set of principles for

describing public administration to improve and enhance the public sector's productivity by adopting the private sector's management procedures (Brown *et al.*, 2003). A prominent example in this regard is the process of outsourcing in the private sector for service implementation.

There are numerous advantages of outsourcing when it is implemented in a public organization. The employees in the public sector will have a much lower burden through outsourcing, starting from the initiation stage to the end stage. The employees are left with more time to find the most suitable supplier to form a service agreement for reaping the maximum benefits of control (Bellamy and Taylor, 1994). Governments can use extensively efficient operating procedures by creating a well-competitive service delivery market. Most importantly, the government can reduce costs and time by investing in the service delivery procedures of the private sector (Barton, 2006).

Even though outsourcing has many benefits, its risk potential should not be overlooked in any way (Harland *et al.*, 2005). It has been estimated that outsourcing costs exceed the anticipated management cost. Outsourcing is a long and complicated process of identifying IT vendors, evaluating them, and negotiating with them for the best possible cost (Barthelemy, 2003; Earl, 1996). Also, these extra costs include the transition process in work through set-up, running costs under other heads, and redeployment of anything needed for the project (Earl, 1996; Barthelemy, 2001). Management costs may be increased or decreased regarding the obligations of contracts, negotiation with the vendors, and changes in defined contract terms. (Barthelemy, 2003; Harland *et al.*, 2005)

Project business requirements can be changed while the lifecycle development is in progress (Clark *et al.*, 1995; Gonzalez *et al.*, 2005). The overall cost and time of the contract may increase by adding any additional requirements or if the client asks for a project amendment (Fowler and Jeff, 1998).

Outsourcing can also cause a client to experience a loss in IT skills and efficiency (Clark *et al.*, 1995; Gonzalez *et al.*, 2005). This loss may occur due to a lack of IT training (Harland, 2005) or the discontinuation of fixed internal IT positions. A client can lose any potential knowledge and expertise which it had gained through unique IT solutions to the vendor (Clark *et al.*, 1995), which means the extent of innovation can also be reduced and cause certain losses to the business (Clark *et al.*, 1995; Earl, 1996). For

running an outsourced project successfully, potential yet innovative knowledge is needed (Feeny *et al.*, 1998; Willcocks and Lacity, 1999). After losing the human resource and the technical infrastructure, the cost of deployment of these resources can get higher and higher enough to be stopped by the management (Jurison, 1995; Fowler and Jeff, 1998; Gonzalez *et al.*, 2005). The dependency on a vendor can be increased to a certain extent due to the irreversibility of outsourcing (Glass, 1996). The flexibility and efficiency in a corporate business environment can be badly affected by reducing or increasing dependence on the vendor by the project runners (Clark *et al.*, 1995).

Outsourcing organizations can provide staff to the vendor (Earl, 1996; Gonzalez *et al.*, 2005), thus giving the choice of selection to the client for its staff (Glass, 1996). Moreover, a vendor can transfer resources from one project to another under tender (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2005; Willcocks *et al.*, 1995). The outsourcer may not fully meet the requirements (Clark *et al.*, 1995) or completely understand and comprehend the actual need of a business (Glass, 1996; Gonzalez *et al.*, 2005). A vendor may find adapting to the new technologies challenging because of the practices already in use (Earl, 1996; Glass, 1996; Gonzalez *et al.*, 2005). The productivity of employees can be affected badly due to job insecurity and desperation at work (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2005; Palvia, 1995). Recruitment of misfit staff to certain positions can also cause a reasonable decline in the working capacity of the employees (Palvia, 2003).

Without a suitable disaster recovery plan and a commitment to trustable third-party storage firms, the security risk associated with the business is increased extensively (Alner, 2001). If the clients use the same storage devices, the risks associated with security can also occur (Alner, 2001). More than just comprehending the potential risks is required; it is always essential for the vendor to develop a security system to provide safety to the information and tools at the business.

2.3 Determinants of outsourcing success or failure

Today, e-governance is at the forefront of the government's efforts to deliver excellent services and up-to-date information to their citizens, third-sector organizations, employees, and other government units. Many governments have made delivery of e-services a policy priority (Khan and Khan, 2017). However, the delivery of e-services is made challenging due to certain factors, like shortage of IT skills, administrative burden, and lack of financial resources to manage the e-services. These challenges drive

public service organizations to outsource their e-services to third-party vendors (Khan and Khan, 2017). The literature provides various examples of e-government initiatives that failed due to lack of funding and required human capital. Moon *et al.* (2016) mentions that staffing and financial pressures are motivational forces for growing government and private sector partnerships. These challenges (staffing pressure and financial constraints) become severer when governments deploy real-time, interactive, and high-quality e-services (Khan and Khan, 2017). The trend of e-service outsourcing is rising due to its ability to resolve the governments' e-service challenges, offer economies of scale benefits, and extend access to skilled IT staff.

However, outsourcing e-services also involves some challenges that must be carefully addressed to avoid outsourcing failure. A recent research study by He and Lu (2017) analyzed the nature of risks and challenges that affect relations with outsourcing partners and ultimately reduce outsourcing success chances. Based on the e-government outsourcing and risk management theory, He and Lu (2017) found that the government's e-service outsourcing decisions involve various complex, multifaceted technical and management-related factors that can reduce the outsourcing benefits when poorly handled. Ahmed (2018) agreed with He and Lu's (2017) argument by asserting that e-service outsourcing decisions can only be made successful by deepening the knowledge of personal, management, and technical factors that influence relational governance, which ultimately leads to outsourcing success.

Lioliou *et al.* (2014) and Benítez-Ávila *et al.* (2018) noted that relational governance has become one of the most critical concerns of firms that outsource their e-services to third-party vendors. It is because poor relationship management is cited as one of the factors for outsourcing failure. However, despite the high importance of the issue for the practitioners, academic scholars have paid inadequate attention to conceptualizing the relational governance term in the e-service outsourcing context (Lioliou *et al.*, 2014; Mathrani and Mathrani, 2016). This knowledge area is under-researched, so practitioners must rely on untested/ subjective recommendations about the best practices for effective relationship management that may lead to outsourcing success. To fill this gap, the researcher has attempted to explore and compare how scholars and practitioners conceptualize e-service outsourcing relational governance.

2.4 E-services outsourcing and relational governance-definition and conceptualization.

The link between relational governance and outsourcing success has been extensively discussed in the literature. Zaheer and Venkatraman (1995) define relational governance as inter-firm exchanges, including relationship-specific assets in combination with a high-level inter-organisational trust, which is deeply embodied in the processes and structure of inter-organisational relationships. In the e-service outsourcing context, relational governance denotes the management of trust-based relationships between client (government) and vendor (public sector IT firms) organisations. Relational governance characterizes the governance of business/economic transactions through relational norms and values, which refer to social regulations and complex processes due to the counterpart party's relations in the trade (Baker *et al.*, 2002). Contending on the same note, Zaheer and Venkatraman (1995) assert that the relational governance of contractual relationships comprises a process and a structure. The structural dimension denotes vertical semi-integration, whereas the process dimension emphasizes the joint actions taken by all primary contractual parties. According to Heidi *et al.* (2010), relational contracting denotes the mechanisms that use non-legal sanctions, resulting in reduced opportunism and enhanced relational effectiveness (Carson *et al.*, 2006; Dyer *et al.*, 1998).

Dyer and Singh (1998) noted that relational governance acts as a value-adding function, and trust holds critical importance among relational governance mechanisms. Poppo *et al.* (2008) agreed and asserted that trust plays its role in different forms to achieve relational governance mechanisms. Trust affects the exchange relationship among contractual parties (Poppo *et al.*, 2008). McNeil (1978) explained contracts as exchange relations that must be carefully handled by emphasizing trust and collaboration. Poppo and Zenger (2002) made a similar assertion by contending that effective relational governance develops its foundation on trust and cooperation, collaboration, dependence and active information sharing. Heidi *et al.* (2010) suggested that contractual parties promote information exchange, flexibility and collaboration to effectively enforce expectations and promises. The inability to handle these relational governance aspects inhibits the exchange parties' ability to handle the exchange relations during an uncertain environment. Scholars (Heidi *et al.*, 2010; Heide and John, 1992; Uhlaner *et al.*, 2007) noted that contractual/formal governance targets the exchange hazards,

which can be minimized through relational governance that functions through social processes and resultant norms.

After explaining relational governance, the researcher presents some definitions of e-service outsourcing. Laabs (1997) defined *outsourcing* as having an outside vendor who performs the service normally in-house (Laabs, 1997). Gibson (1996) defined *outsourcing* as the transference of repetitive and routine tasks to a vendor. *Outsourcing* is the decision to get goods/services from an external party. According to Embleton and Wright (1998), outsourcing denotes the management's inclination to look for expertise for handling certain business areas by availing services of an outside firm. In the e-service context, outsourcing refers to the government's decision to outsource the e-services to a private firm with the knowledge and capabilities to provide high-quality e-services to the citizens (Chen and Perry, 2003)

3 Trust

3.1 Academic conceptualization of trust

Literature on outsourcing relationships emphasizes the appropriate relational governance for the success of outsourcing relationships. In this context, trust is viewed as the outsourcing success' social dimension, which contributes to maximizing the outsourcing benefits (Mazzola and Perrone, 2013; Sambasivan *et al.*, 2013; Palvia *et al.*, 2010). When outsourcing partners trust each other, it reflects their perceptions of their partners' benevolence and credibility. The motivation for including trust in this review is taken from the arguments proposed by previous studies about the importance of trust for developing effective relational governance that guarantees outsourcing success. As mentioned earlier, effective relational governance requires inter-firm exchanges that involve significant relationship-specific assets, and their exchange is based on a high level of inter-organisational trust (Zaheer and Venkatraman, 1995). This relational governance definition suggests that outsourcing relationships can only be successful when they are developed on trust, which could promote the critical asset exchange for outsourcing success (Strieborny and Kukenova, 2016). The success of outsourcing contracts depends on the technical, contractual terms and relies on the relational governance mechanisms that support the business contracts through active collaboration between contractual parties. As Gill (2009) mentioned, the importance of studying trust and relational governance is highlighted by the fact that all business and economic exchanges happen in a relational context, and failure to develop trust-based relationships can lead any contractual relationship towards loss.

Therefore, to understand how outsourcing success could be improved through effective relational governance, it is essential to explore the factors that determine trust and strengthen the commitment of outsourcing partners to fulfil each other's expectations (Huber *et al.*, 2013). Moreover, as noted by Schoenherr, Narayanan and Narasimhan (2015), in most cases, the previous studies explored trust from the client organisation's perspective, and further research is needed to understand how trust is formed and how it influences the outsourcing success from both- client and vendor organisations' perspective. In response to this literature gap, the current research study explored the importance of trust in determining outsourcing success by taking the perspectives of both- vendor and client organisations involved in e-governance outsourcing relationships in the UK.

Previous research conducted by Child (2002) defined trust as confidence required to commit the valuable capabilities, competencies and resources with the outsourcing partner and accept the risk of exploitation and being taken advantage of by the outsourcing partner. This confidence provides a firm foundation for trust between parties involved in outsourcing contracts. Much literature is available to confirm that trust plays a central role in determining outsourcing relationship success (Lee *et al.*, 2008). At the same time, scholars also acknowledge that trust in outsourcing relationships is very fragile (Oza *et al.*, 2006), which means it needs to be handled carefully to increase relationship success chances. Babin *et al.* (2017) considered trusting an institutionalized mechanism that could be built and repaired through particular enforcement mechanisms and socialized norms. These mechanisms and norms support the restraint expectations that may inhibit outsourcing partners from adopting opportunistic behavior (Babin *et al.*, 2017; Kramer and Lewicki, 2010). Based on these definitions, the current study defines *trust* as a state that involves confident, positive expectations about each other's motives and avoidance of opportunistic behavior that may put the other party's interests at risk.

Building and nurturing trust becomes particularly challenging when there is a **physical distance** between the locations of vendor and client organisations, as this physical distance makes the provision of a shared environment for developing trust increasingly challenging (Child, 2002). The existing literature offers inconsistent findings about how inter and intra-organizational distance influences the success of outsourcing relationships. Exploring whether the physical distance between outsourcing partners influences management's ability to formulate and sustain trust is interesting.

Goo *et al.*, (2008) consider the geographic distance important while exploring trust antecedents and consequences in outsourcing relationships. In contrast, Chen and Lin, (2019) do not consider physical distance important and argue that physical distance by itself cannot influence the outsourcing relationship management success and it can only emerge as a significant success predictor when combined with the psychic distance between organisations, which is determined by mutual trust and understanding. The current research study attempted to test the validity of Chen and Lin's (2019) argument by evaluating how possible 'psychic distance' (measured through assessing perceived trust, cooperation, mutual understanding and commitment) influences outsourcing success through effective relationship management.

Besides the physical distance, the importance of a robust institutional environment in which outsourcing contracts are conceived has also been discussed in the literature. While contending on the same note, Child (2002) mentioned that the development of trust becomes easier in regions with solid institutional basis. In contrast, regions with weak law enforcement have a higher risk of distrust and consequent outsourcing failure (Goo *et al.*, 2008). By taking the examples of high and low trust societies, Goo *et al.* (2008) considered countries like USA and UK as high trust societies due to vigorous law enforcement, and countries like China and India were considered low trust societies due to weak law enforcement. However, the high outsourcing failure rate in the UK refutes Goo *et al.*'s (2008) argument, which means only a solid institutional environment for effective legal enforcement is needed to develop trust in outsourcing relationships. Managers involved in outsourcing relationships must stretch their focus from formal/legal/contractual obligations to soft management aspects that may facilitate the exchange of relation-specific assets (Strieborny and Kukenova, 2016). These arguments motivated the current research study to understand whether the emphasis on the soft management aspects (trust and commitment) can increase outsourcing success chances (as proposed by Strieborny and Kukenova, (2016) in the business outsourcing context).

A previous study by Kern and Willcocks (2000) mentioned that extensive investment is required to pursue outsourcing relationships successfully. This relation-specific investment requires actively sharing knowledge, resources and competencies among outsourcing partners. Trust encourages this knowledge sharing and paves the way for successful outsourcing relationship management. While contending on the same note, Babin *et al.* (2017) asserted that repairing and building trust is highly important in outsourcing relationships to meet societal expectations.

Outsourcing partners can generate and **sustain trust** by actively interacting and observing each other's behaviour (Child, 2001). The literature suggests that it is more challenging for the management to sustain the trust than formulate the trust through initial interactions (Greenberg *et al.*, 2008). Therefore, it is crucial to analyse how the ability to formulate and sustain the initial trust through continuous investment in building relation-specific assets can benefit the outsourcing parties by increasing outsourcing success chances (Child, 2001). While contending on a similar note, Babin *et al.* (2017) mentioned that organisations successfully formulate trust in many cases. However, they cannot sustain the developed trust at later stages of the contract due to

weak commitment to the continuous development of relational assets (trust and commitment) through effective communication and cooperation strategies.

The current study makes a valuable addition to this knowledge dimension by exploring the management's willingness to invest in trust formulation and sustaining by investing in developing relationship-specific assets (through regular communication and cooperation, as discussed in the next paragraph). The study also explores how successful trust influences outsourcing success through effective relational governance and how initially formulated trust could be sustained through effective management strategies. This literature review has highlighted some management strategies (including communication, cooperation and knowledge sharing). The study collects quantitative empirical data to assess the effect of each identified strategy on relational governance effectiveness. Qualitative data is also collected to explore other possible management-related factors that are essential in developing and sustaining trust (as discussed in Chapter 4).

Child (2001) further mentioned that an inadequate understanding of each other's expectations could hamper the trust-building process, which may ultimately halt the successful completion of an outsourcing agreement (Babin *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, regular communication and cooperative behaviour is essential to build rapport and construct the basis for initial trust, which may protect the outsourcing contact from failure. The trust gets strengthened through regular communication, and once strengthened; it facilitates knowledge exchange, which is critical for outsourcing success (Lumineau, 2017). As Kern and Willcocks (2000) noted, outsourcing relationship managers may employ both formal and informal communication strategies to develop trust and facilitate knowledge exchange.

Erdogan and Tokgoz (2020) agreed by mentioning that the formation of trust in outsourcing relationships requires both- intentions and capabilities to cooperate to achieve the mutual goal- of outsourcing success. Child (2001) and Kern and Willcocks (2000) used the term 'outsourcing relational governance' to denote these intentions and effective relationship management capabilities that are critical in ensuring outsourcing success. While discussing the importance of trust in outsourcing relations, Lumineau (2017) posited that outsourcing partners can strengthen trust by strengthening relational and social ties (Lumineau, 2017; Kramer and Lewicki, 2010). Trust in outsourcing relations is also formed and built when outsourcing partners are highly experienced, as their relationship management experience enables them to develop an environment of

cooperation and mutual understanding (Lumineau, 2017). This experience also helps outsourcing partners correctly interpret each other's actions, intentions and behaviour. When outsourcing contracts are formed, it **carries the risk of various** breaches that could impair trust and hamper the service delivery process. A relevant example of a possible breach of trust is outsourcing partners' tendency to be involved in opportunistic behaviour that may harm the other parties' interests (Rebernik and Bradač, 2006). An in-depth knowledge of the outsourcing relational governance and factors involved in effective relationship management decreases the risk of breach and enables the outsourcing partners to repair the trust quickly in case of any breach (Babin *et al.*, 2017). Firms with deep knowledge of effective relational governance and relationship management are more likely to achieve their desired objectives from outsourcing and signal that they have successfully developed the skills required for managing the outsourcing relationships (Erdogan and Tokgoz, 2020). A continual relationship management capability allows these firms to acquire the institutionalised outsourcing relationship management norms and signal the legitimacy of business/economic exchanges (Scott, 2014). The current research study has attempted to evaluate the validity of these arguments by assessing whether firms with in-depth knowledge of effective relational governance are more likely to achieve outsourcing objectives, and if so, then which relationship management factors play a more critical role in determining outsourcing success chances. In the literature review section, the researcher has highlighted some best practices or 'factors' that significantly impact relational governance effectiveness.

In case of any breach, the literature review highlights various best practices that may enable outsourcing partners to repair the relationships successfully. Instead of using the punishment strategies for preventing the breach of trust in future, studies (Gergin, 2018; Babin *et al.*, 2017) consider apologetic communication and open and transparent interaction more effective, as punishment tends to develop a hostile environment and hampers the solidarity among outsourcing parties (Kramer and Lewicki, 2010; Kern and Willocks, 2000). However, it is also important to note that apologetic communication may not prove to be effective upon repeated breaches (Kramer *et al.*, 2010), which means it is essential to adopt a proactive attitude and prevent the breach by adopting effective relational governance strategies that may lead towards successful outsourcing relationship management.

Here, relational governance refers to the factors governing the outsourcing relationships, and relationship management refers to the extent to which outsourcing relations are effectively managed by focusing on the right factors that comprise overall relational governance. In the relational governance framework, communication, cooperation, supportive behaviour, commitment and knowledge exchange are considered as the relations-specific assets that are exchanged among the outsourcing partners for effective outsourcing relationship management, which is the vehicle to outsourcing success (Babin *et al.*, 2017; Erdogan and Tokgoz, 2020).

Overall, a **plethora of literature** is available to confirm the central role played by trust in determining the success of outsourcing relationships. However, the literature review also suggests that trust is a complicated factor that requires an in-depth understanding of each other's needs and expectations. The review of previous studies has identified that in the development of trust, cooperative behaviour and effective communication play a critical role (Gittell, 2002).

The overall conclusion drawn from the above discussion is that the successful accomplishment of the desired outsourcing objectives require management to invest in building relational assets, and trust is considered among the essential relational asset in outsourcing contracts. This investment is vital because outsourcing contracts involve extensive interactions among the parties that can only be successful when they are based on trust. Management can develop and sustain trust by focusing on the proper management strategies. The literature considers effective communication and cooperative behaviour as essential management strategies for developing and sustaining trust. Once trust is developed and successfully sustained, it strengthens the parties' commitment to the outsourcing contract and encourages knowledge sharing due to prevailing mutual dependency. The strengthened commitment and increased willingness to share knowledge ultimately enhance the relational governance effectiveness, which shares a direct connection with outsourcing success. The significance of this research is established by quantitatively testing the proposed relationship between trust antecedents (communication, cooperative behaviour) and consequences (knowledge sharing strengthened commitment, which ultimately predict effective relational governance and outsourcing success) and qualitatively exploring the possible management strategies (not covered in literature and quantitative survey) that

may influence the trust. The study also adds to the existing literature by exploring environmental tendencies (environmental factors/reasons that motivated organisations to make the outsourcing decision) that may moderate the influence of relational governance on outsourcing success.

3.2 Theories underpinning understanding of trust.

Schoenherr *et al.* (2015) adopted the relational and social exchange theories to understand the inter-organisational relationships in outsourcing. Social exchange theory (abbreviated as SET) was introduced by Homans (1958) to explain social interactions between humans and their behaviours during the exchange process with a central emphasis on rewards and costs. The exchange theories place paramount importance on equity, exchange and trust. They consider it essential to reduce the opportunism risk, increase confidence in outsourcing partners' willingness to fulfil contractual obligations, and lay the foundation for long-term business relationships (Alwahdani, 2019). Equity denotes sharing benefits and burdens; exchange means the social processes of give-and-take relationships. Exchange theories consider the relations long-term rather than a single-shot transaction and consider trust a critical variable for effective relational governance (Gottschalk and Solli-Sæther, 2005). The cooperation between exchange parties occurs reciprocally, and this cooperative behaviour, along with effective communication, lays a strong foundation for trust-based long-term business relations (Schoenherr *et al.*, 2015).

By design, trust is socially embedded between outsourcing partners, and by nature, it is shaped by the context in which exchanges between outsourcing partners occur. Strong social ties reduce the outsourcing partners' inclination to behave opportunistically (Chiles and McMackin, 1996; Lusch and Brown, 1996), which is essential for building healthy outsourcing relations. The current research study deems SET an appropriate theoretical lens for hypothesising the relationship between trust and effective relational governance in the e-service outsourcing context. This theory is precious for better understanding outsourcing relational governance dynamics.

As per Sia *et al.* (2008), outsourcing relationships are influenced by contractual elements and derive a strong impact from the social dimensions, among which trust holds critical importance. A previous study by Blau (1964) contended that give-and-

take relations based on cooperative behaviour are more successful as their foundation is built over trust. Social exchange theory supports these arguments by considering proactive relationship management critical for outsourcing performance (Sia *et al.*, 2008). Although social exchange theory has been frequently employed to explore the relational governance dynamics in various organisational settings, scholars like Blau (1964) and Cropanzano and Mitchell (2005) called for more empirical research to understand how trust and social exchange theory could be integrated to understand the relational aspects in an outsourcing context.

It is important to note that propositions and assumptions govern the social exchange theory. SET assumes that social actors behave rationally to maximise the return (Huo *et al.*, 2016). The theory further assumes that the gratification depends on others, partners prefer social credit over indebtedness, partners have goal orientation, and the interactions between partners occur in a specific context (John *et al.*, 2017). Now, when these assumptions are applied to the e-service outsourcing context, SET assumes that the interactions between outsourcing partners are based on rational grounds, which means each outsourcing partner considers effective relational governance critical for the outsourcing success, which is mutually beneficial for all partners involved in outsourcing (Schoenherr *et al.*, 2015). All outsourcing partners tend to effectively communicate and cooperate in exchanging knowledge in a trust-based environment to fulfil business goals (Huo *et al.*, 2016). The last assumption encouraged the researcher to explore the context in which outsourcing decisions are made. It is done by exploring the environmental tendencies that motivated targeted public service organisations to outsource their e-services to private IT companies (John *et al.*, 2017).

SET is also developed on some propositions. The first SET proposition stipulates that partners' inclination to act again increases by rewarding the specific actions. The second proposition emphasises that over the probability and value of return, the chances of performing the same action will increase when the perceptions towards the probability and value of return are positive (Schoenherr *et al.*, 2015). The third SET proposition is closely related to the second proposition and stipulates that the negative perceptions towards the probability and value of expected return decrease the chances of repeating the action (Lee *et al.*, 2010). Application of these propositions in the e-service outsourcing context suggests that when outsourcing partners consider cooperative behaviour and trust-based relations essential for ensuring outsourcing success, then the

partners will be more likely to cooperate and effectively communicate with each other for developing trust-based relations so that it could improve the outsourcing success chances (Homans, 1961).

Other than social exchange theory, relational governance mechanisms in the e-service outsourcing context can also be analysed in light of trust and commitment theory. As the name depicts, this theory emphasises the trust and commitment among outsourcing partners to make outsourcing relationships successful. The relationship centrality has motivated the researchers to explore critical factors that ensure successful relational exchange (Goles and Chin, 2002; Kern and Willcocks, 2002; Zaheer and Venkatraman, 1995; Lambe *et al.*, 2000; McEvily *et al.*, 2003). Exploring factors influencing relational governance and its role in outsourcing success has been an exciting research topic in literature. Among the scholars who studied relational governance aspects in the outsourcing context, Morgan and Hunt (1994) theorised that relationship commitment and trust mediate in outsourcing relationship development and performance. Trust and commitment can achieve the relational governance outcomes' effectiveness, productivity, and efficiency (Morgan and Hunt, 1994).

While contending on the same note, Kern and Willcocks (2002) mentioned that trust in outsourcing relationships derives influence from shared values, opportunistic behaviour, trust and cooperation. Trust and commitment are desired relationship management outcomes, leading to successful relationship management. However, trust is also considered a part of the relationship development process due to its abstract and qualitative nature. Mohr and Nevin (1990) shared a similar assertion by mentioning that the perceived relationship benefits and perceived relationship termination costs influence the commitment between outsourcing partners, trust and commitment also derive the influence from shared values, and opportunistic behaviour and effective communication influence trust, which then influences the commitment (Morgan and Hunt, 1994; Mohr and Nevin, 1990; Kern and Willcocks, 2002).

Besides taking theoretical support from the relational exchange theory, the current research study also takes theoretical guidance from the trust and commitment theory, as the present study has also taken effective communication and cooperative values as the predictor of trust, which may predict commitment. In addition, to trust and commitment, Morgan and Hunt (1994) theorised that relationship success largely

depends on the leaving propensity and acquiescence that are commitment outcomes. The authors also mentioned that uncertainty and functional conflict could be considered trust outcomes and trust and commitment positively correlate to cooperation. Some previous studies conducted in the context of IT outsourcing (like Choudhury and Sabherwal, 2003 and Sabherwal, 1999) proposed that both- relationship commitment and trust play a central role in determining the success of outsourcing relationships.

Outsourcing engagements involve organisations to achieve collective goals. In some cases, these goals need more clarity. They are attained in a highly uncertain environment in which invisible assets (in the form of trust, commitment and cooperation) are frequently exchanged with each other (Langfield-Smith and Smith, 2003). The value of these intangible asset exchanges is sometimes higher than that of exchanging tangible assets that occur in purely transactional relationships (Itami and Roehl, 1991). In some cases, the outsourcing relationship is formed among organisations already engaged with each other for other business transactions. Even in those cases, building trust and commitment remains important (Langfield-Smith and Smith, 2003). However, in many cases, the outsourcing relationship is formed among parties that were previously unknown to each other. In those cases, there is a need to first focus on the initial trust-building mechanisms, which may provide the basis for outsourcing success (McKnight *et al.*, 1998). McKnight *et al.* (1998) further contended that in the absence of the interaction history, focusing on initial trust-building mechanisms can reduce the relationship uncertainty and encourage trust, commitment and cooperation. Kern and Willcocks (2002) added that the focus on developing initial trust is gaining more importance due to the rise of temporary teams for managing tasks and projects.

Although companies can develop initial trust among each other through contractual agreements (Baber *et al.*, 2007), the importance of effective and regular communication cannot be undermined, and the absence of effective communication can increase the risk of misunderstandings, which can hamper the trust, and ultimately reduce the outsourcing success chances. Authors like (Gefen *et al.*, 2005) further assert that besides relying on the institutional trust that is formed through formal contractual obligations, inter-organisational trust and commitment require the management of both organisations to take care of the soft aspects of relationship management (Gefen *et al.*, 2005). These arguments encourage the researchers to explore the soft relationship

management aspects that may foster trust and commitment and drive the outsourcing relationship towards success.

In consistency with the relational exchange and Morgan and Hunt's trust commitment theory, the current research study theorised that trust is necessary and essential for outsourcing relationship success (Morgan and Hunt, 1994). Although the literature review has indicated that trust in outsourcing relationships is influenced by both- formal (contractual) and informal (soft relationship management aspects) factors, the current study maintains its focus on the soft relationship management aspects because, as noted by some recent studies (Ali *et al.*, 2018; Khan and Khan, 2017), inability to focus on soft aspects (like regular communication, adoption of shared/cooperative values) account for the outsourcing failure more than technical reasons, as these factors can be considered as the root causes of relationship failure. Therefore, the study theorised that trust is the critical relational attribute that is formed by focusing on communication and cooperative behaviour. Once formed, trust strengthens the commitment and facilitates the knowledge flow; both factors are essential for outsourcing relationship success.

Based on the above discussion, it is clear that the management of trust-based relationships between client and vendor organisations requires outsourcing managers to take care of various personal and management-related factors that determine the relationship's health and influence the chances of outsourcing success.

3.3 Antecedents and outcomes factors of trust

Although many factors affect the success of e-services outsourcing, this research study considered those which appeared in most of the related literature and their importance was agreed upon by most of the authors. Moreover, this was the motive behind choosing these specific factors for this research study.

In the next section, the researcher analyses the critical factors that must be carefully considered to foster trust in outsourcing relationships.

3.3.1 *Effective communication and trust in outsourcing relationships*

As discussed, effective communication is critical for developing trust and ensuring successful outsourcing relationship management. Vendor and client organisations that maintain regular communication with each other throughout the contract period are more likely to achieve the desired objectives from their outsourcing relationships (Ali and Green, 2012). Effective communication is critical, as poor communication is cited as one of the most common causes of misunderstandings in outsourcing relationships (Schneider-Borowicz, 2003).

Studies like Leeman and Reynolds (2012) considered a well-balanced formal and informal communication as an influential trust antecedent, which enhances the trust, and improved trust becomes a vehicle of outsourcing success. While discussing the importance of communication in outsourcing relations, González-Lloret (2003) commented that all communication aspects (formal, informal, verbal, writing, and face-to-face or tech mediated) are essential to successful business relationships.

Active communication enables the outsourcing partners to understand each other's expectations and resolve possible misunderstandings. Some research studies (like Miller and Luse, 2004) considered effective communication more critical than the technical factors for successfully managing business relations. However, it is essential to ensure a strong alignment between management strategies and effective communication practices (Babin *et al.*, 2017). The evolution of computer-mediated communication requires management to carefully handle the communication and avoid possible communication gaps, which may hinder outsourcing relationship management (Erdogan and Tokgoz, 2020)

Brownell and Reynolds (2002) considered **active** communication essential for developing healthy vendor and client relationships. For client organisations, opening formal and informal communication channels for vendors is essential to provide timely feedback and share ideas, which may act as catalysts for improving the outsourcing relationship quality. A systematic literature review conducted by Ali *et al.* (2017) explored the success factors for software outsourcing relationship management and found that active and effective communication and cooperative behaviour towards each other encourage collaboration and increase trust in outsourcing relationships. Ali *et al.* (2017) analysed active communication based on the three C's- coordination, cooperation and collaboration. Happonen and Siljander (2020) agreed with Ali *et al.*

(2017) by commenting that timely communication is critical for decreasing the chances of misunderstandings and possible delays in important decisions and increasing trust in outsourcing relationships. When parties actively communicate with each other.

Oza *et al.* (2006) commented that effective communication between client and vendor organisations strengthens the vendors' commitment to the outsourcing relationship, reduces misunderstanding chances, and encourages cooperative behaviour. As noted by Schmitt and Van Biesebroeck (2013), effective communication between vendor and client organisations can be enhanced by developing effective feedback mechanisms with an opportunity for two-way communication between parties involved in outsourcing contracts. Zineldin and Jonsson (2000) agreed with Langfield-Smith and Smith (2003) by contending that two-way communication and constructive feedback facilitates the attainment of compatible goals and strengthens mutual trust. Langfield-Smith and Smith (2003) also noted that vendor and client organisations are likely to cooperate more when they regularly communicate through formal and, where necessary, informal channels.

Based on the above arguments, the researcher proposes that: effective communication strategies play an essential role in fostering trust in outsourcing relationships. The validity of this argument is assessed by conducting an empirical investigation into the selected research context. Qualitative and quantitative data are collected to get a broader and deeper understanding of how and to what extent effective communication influences trust in outsourcing relationships. In the next section, the researcher discusses the importance of cooperative behaviour that emerges from contract flexibility and lays a strong foundation for enhancing trust in outsourcing relationships.

3.3.2 Co-operative behaviour due to contract flexibility and trust in outsourcing relationships

The importance of adopting cooperative instead of competitive and opportunistic behaviour for making outsourcing relationships successful has been frequently emphasised in the literature. Contractual flexibility makes adopting this cooperative behaviour easier for the outsourcing partners. Usually, outsourcing occurs in an environment of uncertainty. The turbulent external environment makes it difficult for outsourcing partners to rigidly follow contractual terms (Susarla *et al.*, 2020). According to Schoenherr *et al.* (2015), uncertainty in outsourcing relationships tends to

influence the partner's behaviours towards each other. Scholars like Tan and Sia (2006) consider contractual flexibility desirable when the goal is to develop strong outsourcing relationships based on cooperation and trust. When an outsourcing contract is flexible, it enables the outsourcing partners to accommodate the changes occurring in their relationships regarding rewards and needs. Dyer and Chu (2000) state that flexible outsourcing contracts generate goodwill and promote partner trust. Social exchange theory supports these arguments as SET emphasises the social exchange processes that depend on relationship monitoring based on trust and cooperation instead of contract stipulations (Das and Teng, 2002).

The application of social exchange theory suggests that contract flexibility can indicate the cooperation and partners' positive expectations from their outsourcing relationship (Mayer and Argyres (2004). Schoenherr *et al.* (2015) also contended that a flexible outsourcing contract increases the outsourcing partners' willingness to deviate or modify the contract to accommodate uncertain events to continue adopting cooperative and non-opportunistic behaviour. By elaborating further, Griffith *et al.* (2006) contended that a flexible outsourcing contract does not strictly force the outsourcing partners to enforce contractual penalties for events (like delivery delay). Such events rarely occur and may damage partners' cooperation and relationship quality. This flexibility develops positive attitudinal dispositions (Griffith *et al.*, 2006), which enhances relational governance and ultimately increases outsourcing success chances. Dyer and Chu (2000) asserted that the flexible and cooperative behaviour emerging from contract flexibility creates social credit, which is expected to foster trust.

While contending on the same note, Butler (1995) considered contract flexibility as a form of reward to outsourcing partners that conveys a sense of commitment in the outsourcing relationships. An indication of the enhanced commitment between outsourcing partners due to trust and cooperative behaviour is an adaptation of the contract due to uncertain events, rewarding the vendor performance for exceeding expectations and respecting and appreciating each other's business needs.

On a similar note, Dyer and Chu (2000) asserted that trust in outsourcing relationships emerges when the parties involved in outsourcing are known for making adjustments in their contracts (in response to the changing market conditions) in a manner that is perceived fair by all partners and do not involve the inclination to take excessive advantage of another partner when the opportunity is available.

In summary, cooperative behaviour supported by contract flexibility creates an environment where outsourcing partners are less likely to exhibit opportunism, laying a solid foundation for trust (Dyer and Chu, 2000; Goo *et al.*, 2009). The review has included contractual flexibility because it is deemed essential for integrating flexibility into the behaviour towards each other in outsourcing relationships. Outsourcing partners cannot adopt cooperative behaviour if inflexible contractual terms strictly dictate their behaviour.

Based on these arguments, the researcher hypothesises adopting cooperative and flexible behaviour encourages trust between outsourcing partners. The study tests the validity of this argument by quantifying the effect of 'cooperative and flexible' behaviour on the perceived trust in targeted organisations involved in outsourcing contractual relationships.

3.3.3 *Trust and knowledge sharing in outsourcing relationships.*

Although trust plays a central role in determining the success of outsourcing relationships, the literature review suggests that the relationship between trust and outsourcing is indirect due to the involvement of various moderating and mediating variables (Lee and Huynh, 2005). Knowledge sharing is considered an essential trust outcome that significantly affects relationship health, which is strongly connected to outsourcing success (Fehrenbacher and Wiener, 2019). *Knowledge sharing* can be defined as the proactive, voluntary behavioural awareness that motivates individuals and organisations to transmit and diffuse knowledge from one individual/organisation to another so that knowledge can be effectively utilised by all parties to accomplish mutual goals (Zheng, 2017). A plethora of literature is available to confirm the effect of trust on the outsourcing partners' willingness to share knowledge. For instance, empirical research conducted by Cheng *et al.* (2008) found a statistically significant relationship between trust and knowledge sharing among value chain partners to accomplish green supply chain management goals.

Monica *et al.* (2012) employed the social exchange theory. They proved the statistically significant relationship between trust, social exchange and knowledge sharing among business partners collaborating to pursue service innovation objectives. The empirical research conducted by Liao *et al.* (2009) also proved the effect of trust on knowledge sharing among IS outsourcing partners. Based on a survey of IS managers managing

outsourcing relationships, Liao *et al.* (2009) considered knowledge sharing a significant predictor of overall outsourcing success. Another research by Lee *et al.* (2009) explored the importance of knowledge sharing and outsourcing success from the client organisation's perspective. Based on the interviews with IT professionals, Lee *et al.* (2009) found that initial trust, initial distrust and ongoing trust- all three trust dimensions played their role in determining the knowledge-sharing willingness at later stages of outsourcing contract implementation. When parties trust each other, they are confident that the other party will not exploit the shared knowledge for their benefit and will utilise it to accomplish mutual objectives (Monica *et al.*, 2012; Lee *et al.*, 2009; Liao *et al.*, 2009).

Based on the above arguments, the current research study proposes that- perceived trust between outsourcing partners positively impacts the outsourcing partners' willingness to share knowledge. This argument is tested by collecting the survey data from targeted respondents and analysing the collected data by using various statistical techniques. To sum up, the study has included knowledge sharing as an essential trust consequence that enhances the relational governance effectiveness by facilitating the flow of ideas, solutions and critical information that could enable outsourcing partners to make the right decisions at the right time. The social exchange theory is discussed in this section because it provides theoretical justification for the argument that when outsourcing parties trust each other, this trust is exchanged with the knowledge each party possesses and can share with others to achieve mutually beneficial goals. However, the review also highlights that although trust promotes knowledge sharing, the effect gets enhanced when the interests of both parties are intertwined in a way that their existing high mutual inter-dependency.

3.3.4 Trust and commitment in outsourcing relationships

The relationship between trust and commitment in outsourcing relationships derives theoretical and empirical support from the existing literature. The academic support is derived from the trust and commitment theory proposed by Morgan and Hunt (1994), who suggested that outsourcing parties' commitment to the outsourcing contract largely depends on the trust between both parties, and commitment acts as a mediator in the relationship between trust and effective outsourcing relationship management. Kern and Willcocks (2002) made a similar assertion by contending that trust in outsourcing

relationships is developed based on shared values and cooperation, and once created, it strengthens the outsourcing parties' commitment to the outsourcing contract. In the IT outsourcing context, some previous scholars have established the relationship between trust, commitment and outsourcing success (like Choudhury and Sabherwal, 2003 and Sabherwal, 1999).

The above discussion shows how trust and commitment theory establishes the connection between both variables, which can be interesting to study while exploring the relational governance dimensions in the e-service outsourcing context. Other than theoretical support, the existing literature also provides empirical solid support to establish the effect of trust on commitment in business relationships. For instance, comparative research by Ndubisi (2011) on Indian and Chinese organizations involved in IT outsourcing considered conflict handling and trust as the antecedents of commitment in outsourcing relationships. Ndubisi (2011) also called for more empirical research to understand how trust shapes the commitment in outsourcing relationships in different world regions.

Another research by Leeman and Reynolds (2012) explored the value of trust in outsourcing relationships—the study aimed to explore how perceptions towards trust influence the retention of outsourcing partners. By surveying 4,000 purchasing executives, the researchers found that perceived operational competence, effective communication, and perceived operational benevolence collectively predict trust, which shares a significant relationship with commitment, and commitment then drives towards outsourcing success through vendor retention. Later studies by Schoenherr *et al.* (2015) and Happonen and Siljander (2020) validated the Leeman and Reynolds (2012) results by considering trust a significant predictor of commitment in outsourcing relationships.

Based on the above discussion, the researcher proposes that trust between outsourcing partners enhances their commitment to fulfilling the contract. Commitment is the direct outcome of trust, which is vital in determining relational governance effectiveness.

3.3.5 Knowledge sharing and effective relational governance in outsourcing.

Knowledge sharing denotes the parties' willingness to share important information to accomplish mutual goals. Business organisations often face severe losses due to ineffective knowledge-sharing mechanisms. Knowledge sharing has been considered

critical for outsourcing and overall organisational success (Rutten *et al.*, 2016). Yam and Chan (2015) reported that by placing effective knowledge-sharing mechanisms, management could effectively discourage opportunistic behaviour and strengthen the outsourcing partners' commitment to pursue collective goals. Lee *et al.* (2015) attempted to explain the knowledge-sharing mechanisms by employing the social capital theory and reported that shared knowledge positively influences the outsourcing team's performance due to collaborative and closer relationships between vendor and client organisation. Rutten *et al.* (2016) agreed with Lee *et al.* (2015) by reporting that knowledge sharing enhances the relationship quality and increases the chances of project success. Wickramasinghe (2015) commented that knowledge sharing leads towards disseminating innovative ideas across organisations. This idea-sharing can improve work processes and strengthen the ties among business partners.

Although knowledge sharing is, to some extent, a natural function, however, management can exercise effective control over its dissemination by developing a trust-based environment that supports open communication and interactions among outsourcing partners (Attar *et al.*, 2019). Wickramasinghe (2015) proposed similar insights by contending that in order to develop an environment conducive to knowledge sharing, it is essential for organisations to identify and resolve the hurdles that may constrain the knowledge-sharing process and discourage employees from openly sharing their ideas. In outsourcing relations, the outsourcing partners generally see the economic value in intangible rather than tangible assets, and knowledge is one of the most essential and desired assets that determine the relationship quality and paves the way for the successful accomplishment of outsourcing objectives (Attar *et al.*, 2019).

Based on the above arguments, the current research study proposes that effective relational governance in the outsourcing context is strongly influenced by the outsourcing parties' willingness to share knowledge. The validity of this argument is tested by collecting qualitative and primarily quantitative data from targeted participants.

3.3.6 Commitment and effective relational governance in outsourcing

Commitment denotes the partners' willingness to fulfil the outsourcing contract despite challenging circumstances. In organizational management literature, commitment is an important variable that shapes a positive work environment and increases workplace

productivity (Díaz-Reza *et al.*, 2018). In the outsourcing context, the commitment of the vendor to fulfil the contract and the commitment of the client organization to provide the necessary support when required is a vital success determinant. By strengthening the commitment, the management enhances the relational governance quality, which is strongly connected with outsourcing success (Choudhury and Sabherwal, 2003). While explaining the value of commitment in outsourcing relationships, Moorman *et al.* (1992) defined *commitment* as an enduring desire to maintain the value of relationships. It implies that a higher level of obligation for making the relationship flourishing, mutually beneficial, and satisfying strengthens the commitment to fulfil the contract. Ali *et al.* (2018) also argued that increasing the interdependence between service providers and outsourcers increases the need to handle conflicts effectively and raises the importance of commitment to getting desired outsourcing results.

The findings of these studies suggest that commitment between outsourcing parties is deemed critical in outsourcing business relationships to ensure effective relational governance. Based on these arguments, the researcher proposes that- commitment between outsourcing partners enhances the overall relational governance, which increases the success chances of e-service outsourcing in the UK.

3.3.7 *Relational governance and outsourcing success*

As mentioned before, in current research, relational governance refers to the overall mechanism of exchanging relationship assets. In the current case, these relationship-specific assets refer the trust, commitment, cooperation and knowledge exchange. These exchanges benefit client and vendor organisations and are essential for developing effective business relationships (Qi and Chau, 2013). In this section, the researcher discusses how effective relationship management based on a robust relational governance framework increases outsourcing success chances. For this purpose, the researcher reviews arguments of some previous scholarly studies that explored the relationship between relational governance, relationship management and outsourcing success.

Previous research by Ring and Van de Ven (1994) argued that organisations decide to continue their relationships when considering inter-organisational relationships fair and

economically efficient. This assessment is made based on past transactions. Therefore, it is important to carefully handle inter-organisational relations by focusing on technical, formal, and non-technical, informal factors. The contractual terms and conditions make handling formal aspects easier and less uncertain (Chen and Bharadwaj, 2009). However, management of non-technical and informal relationship aspects largely depends on the managers' experience and soft skills (Das and Teng, 2001). While contending on the same note, Kirsch (2004) asserted that relational governance denotes the human elements involved in inter-organisational relationships that can drive a business relation towards success or failure. Lioliou *et al.* (2014) mentioned a similar point by contending that effective relational governance provides informal, social control over business relations, reducing risks and facilitating coordination among parties involved in outsourcing contracts.

The literature review highlights various studies highlighting different relational governance aspects to determine outsourcing success. Previous quantitative research by Carson *et al.* (2006) identified trust, reputation and history of the interaction quality as the relational governance aspects that determine the success of outsourcing relationships. Chen and Bharadwaj (2009) also conducted a quantitative survey and found trust, learning and knowledge exchange as the most critical relational governance aspects determining outsourcing success. Das and Teng (2001) conducted qualitative conceptual research and proposed a model comprising trust and social control as critical dimensions. The qualitative research conducted by Faems *et al.* (2008) also emphasised trust while exploring the relational governance aspects in the outsourcing context.

Quantitative research by Goo *et al.* (2009) proposed that the success of outsourcing relationships largely depends on effective relational governance, which comprises relational norms, commitment, trust, mutual dependence and harmonious conflict resolution. Quantitative research by Gulati and Nikerson (2008) considered effective communication, cooperation and trust essential to relational governance. A qualitative study by Huber *et al.* (2013) emphasised trust and social control in outsourcing relationships. A conceptual study by Inkpen and Curral (2004) also considered trust a central factor in outsourcing relational governance. Kirsch (2004) considered trust and informal control over business relations important for developing a solid foundation for relational governance in an outsourcing context. Klein-Woolthuis *et al.* (2005)

conducted qualitative interviews with outsourcing managers and found trust and dependence as the two most crucial relational governance aspects.

Quantitative survey-based research by Li *et al.* (2010) highlighted trust and shared goals as the two most crucial relational governance aspects determining outsourcing success. Quantitative studies by Malhotra and Lumineau (2011), Rustagi *et al.* (2008) and Mellewigt *et al.* (2007) also placed central importance to trust for increasing outsourcing success chances through effective relational governance. A quantitative study by Poppo and Zenger (2002) found trust, open communication and sharing of information, dependence and cooperation as the essential relational governance aspects that play an important role in determining outsourcing success chances.

Although the above discussion shows that various studies have explored the value of relational governance in the outsourcing context, Lioliou *et al.* (2014) noted a need for coherence in viewpoints about how managers can ensure effective relational governance to increase outsourcing success chances. Different scholarly studies have highlighted different relational governance aspects and factors to make outsourcing relations successful. However, trust has been most commonly highlighted as determining relational governance success. Other relational governance factors commonly highlighted by previous studies include- communication (Swar *et al.*, 2012; Nguyen *et al.*, 2006; Lahiri and Kedia, 2011), commitment (Díaz-Reza *et al.*, 2018; Ali *et al.*, 2018), knowledge exchange (Lee, 2001; Park *et al.*, 2011), co-operative behaviour (Park *et al.*, 2011), and mutual dependency (Lee *et al.*, 2008; Lee and Kim, 2005).

The above arguments also derive empirical support from previous studies that established the significant relationship between relational governance and outsourcing success by providing empirical evidence. For example, Qi and Chau (2012) adopted a multi-case study approach to analyse two case studies descriptively. Both organisations were selected from China, and results revealed that outsourcing success derives a strong influence from different relationship management dimensions. Outsourcing relationship management requires managers to take care of various relational dimensions that must be carefully considered to increase the outsourcing success chances. Another research by Qi and Chau (2013) established the significant effect of trust and inter-organisational and interpersonal trust on the success of IT outsourcing

in the Chinese public sector. Schwarz (2014) considered effective relationship management as a significant factor that is the cause of many failed outsourcing initiatives. Lee and Choi (2011) empirically established the significant relationship between trust, effective relationship management and outsourcing success. They considered initial and ongoing trust a factor in overall outsourcing relational governance.

Recent empirical research by Fehrenbacher and Wiener (2019) explored the influence of knowledge-sharing willingness and commitment on IT outsourcing success and found both factors to be significant success predictors. However, this study was conducted on private IT firms. The small sample size (experiment conducted on only 198 IT professionals involved in outsourcing relationships) and lack of specificity (by collecting data from a specific region) affect the generalizability of these results. Some other empirical studies (like Karimi-Alagheband and Rivard, 2020; Sanchis-Pedregosa and Machuca, 2018; Zhu *et al.*, 2017) also considered strong relational governance and effective relationship management critical for successfully achieving the desired outcomes from outsourcing projects. However, the literature review indicates the need for more context-specific research to understand how relationship management factors enhance the overall relational governance and ultimately increase the success of e-service outsourcing contracts in the UK.

Based on the above arguments, the current research study proposes that: effective relational governance provides a solid basis for strengthening the relationship between vendor and client organisations, which increases the success chances of outsourcing relationships between client and vendor organisations. The researcher has tested the validity of this argument by conducting empirical research into public organisations in the UK that entered into an outsourcing contract to outsource e-services for various reasons.

3.4 Mutual dependency as moderator between trust and knowledge sharing in outsourcing relationships.

Previous scholarly studies report that the willingness to share knowledge in trust-based outsourcing relationships strongly influences mutual dependency. The absence of mutual dependency reduces the impact of trust on the parties' knowledge-sharing willingness. These arguments suggest that besides the relational costs, the parties' desire

to share important information also strongly influences the possible economic loss they may face because of not sharing critical information due to their dependency on their partner (Marchewka and Oruganti, 2013). When perceived economic loss is low due to low dependency, the chances of sharing critical information will get reduced despite sharing trust-based relationships. A previous study by Lee and Kim (2005) validates these arguments by proving that mutual dependency is a significant moderator in the relationship between trust and knowledge sharing. Qualitative research by Lee *et al.* (2008) agreed with the findings proposed by Lee and Kim (2005) by contending that when parties' interests are aligned in outsourcing contracts, it compels them to adopt cooperative behaviour and share essential knowledge for increasing outsourcing success chances. Mutual dependency reflects the dependency between organizations that arises when perceived mutual benefits are aligned with each other, and this mutual dependency varies with the outsourcing partnership quality, size and exchange importance (Lee and Kim, 1999). When an outsourcing partner considers others the best alternative, and when products/services to be outsourced hold high importance for the client organization, it increases the moderating impact of the mutual dependency on the trust-relational governance relationship (Marchewka and Oruganti, 2013).

Based on the above arguments, this research study proposes that: Perceived mutual dependency moderates the relationship between perceived trust between outsourcing parties and their willingness to exchange knowledge. The researcher has collected quantitative survey data to test the moderating power of mutual dependency in the proposed relationship. Besides knowledge exchange, commitment between outsourcing parties is the most commonly highlighted trust outcome in outsourcing relationships.

3.5 Environmental tendencies to make outsourcing decision- contextual variable.

Environmental tendencies refer to the 'motivations' or 'tendencies' within a particular environmental context within which public service organisations decided to outsource their e-services to private sector IT firms. In the current case, environmental tendencies refer to the motives that motivate firms to make outsourcing decisions (Lahiri and Kedia, 2011). The literature review highlights various economic, socio-economic, political and other reasons that encourage entering into outsourcing relations. The knowledge gained from the literature review is then compared with the qualitative interview insights, as interviewees are asked to share the reasons and mention

internal/external environmental factors that motivated/compelled them to outsource the e-governance services.

The literature review reveals that political and regulatory factors substantially impact the government's decision to outsource e-services. Political mandates dictate the e-service outsourcing contractual terms and conditions and shape priorities. For instance, a previous study by Chen and Perry (2003) mentioned how the Bush administration placed heavy emphasis on 'security' when making IT outsourcing decisions because of its focus on homeland security. Mahalik (2010) also agreed by contending that governments' political mandates significantly influence their outsourcing priorities.

Besides the political factors, the marketplace situation also influences the outsourcing decision. The easy availability of vendors with the right skills and competencies makes outsourcing a favourable decision for the government. A highly mature IT outsourcing marketplace increases the attractiveness of outsourcing options, and the prevailing regulatory environment also influences outsourcing priorities (Lahiri and Kedia, 2011). Vendor quality and reliability influence the intensity of risks involved in outsourcing relationships. High outsourcing risk discourages the government from entering into outsourcing contracts. In the case of government organisations, finding reliable and quality vendors is relatively easy, as in the case of small organisations seeking to outsource their services (Johaand Janssen, 2010).

Another factor influencing the outsourcing decision is the **complexity and** compatibility of the IT services that need to be outsourced to a vendor. High compatibility and low complexity require less communication and coordination between public agencies and vendors (Lahiri and Kedia, 2011). Project size and customisation increase the outsourcing complexity and require public agencies to handle the outsourcing relationship management to avoid undesired circumstances more carefully (Žitkienė and Dudė, 2018). A previous research study by Iqbal and Dad (2013) considered skills shortage in the labour market as one of the most potent environmental factors that encourage public agencies to outsource their services. The skills shortage has influenced not only Eastern (developing) but also Western (developed) world regions. Lahiri and Kedia (2011) also considered skills shortage an essential institutional factor that increases the urge to outsource services to vendors with the required skills and competencies.

Cost reduction is one of the most potent outsourcing motives, as a gradual and consistent rise in costs has made it difficult for organisations to remain competitive in

the highly dynamic business environment (Moon *et al.*, 2016). In today's highly dynamic business environment, survival increases the need to procure and utilise the best resources for achieving desired outcomes. Besides achieving the differentiation, quality and cost reduction objectives, complying with the complex regulatory environment makes the business environment more challenging (Cordella and Willcocks, 2012). Application of the transaction cost theory (TCE) on these arguments suggests that organisations that represent the governance structure prefer market-based transactions (which means purchasing) upon hierarchies (which means making in-house) in cases when perceived transaction costs as a result of contracting are lesser than controlling (Lacity *et al.*, 2011). Another environmental factor that motivates the outsourcing decision is the advancement in the information and communication technologies that made the management of outsourcing relationships easier than before. Communication with the relevant stakeholders with the help of advanced digitalisation tools has become more effective, and these factors have made it possible for organisations to consider overseas vendors for outsourcing (Jun and Weare, 2011).

Growing competition for market share and resources has become a severe cause of concern for managers in public organisations. The intensifying competition and rapid competitive moves compel organisations to make quick decisions and achieve multifaceted objectives to ensure long-term survival (Jun and Weare, 2011). In order to tackle the intensifying competition, many businesses tend to outsource some value chain activities to specialised vendors so that they may reduce the burden and focus on the core functions (Chen and Perry, 2003). The premise for this move is that by diverting the organisational resources and capabilities to the core areas that need the most significant attention, firms can better handle the competition and prevent possible decline due to an increasingly saturated and mature market (Lahiri *et al.*, 2008). Operating cost reduction is another major factor encouraging organisations to make outsourcing decisions. Escalating costs have become a major institutional factor that induces firms to explore all possibilities for reducing costs to tackle the competition and offer superior value on a limited budget (Jun and Weare, 2011).

As per Pfannenstien and Tsai (2004), outsourcing may result in up to 40 to 50 per cent cost reductions. However, this argument holds particular relevance in the case of offshore outsourcing. This cost reduction may emerge from economies of scale, wage differentials or/and business specialisation. Another common factor that acts as a motivational trigger for making outsourcing decisions is experience utilisation. Many

firms outsource their activities to specialised vendors for a cooperative exchange specialising in a particular business area/competence (Jun and Weare, 2011). The successful strategic alliances and private-public sector partnerships signify the importance of outsourcing for successfully managing business operations in the increasingly complex and competitive business environment (Jun and Weare, 2011).

The above discussion suggests external environmental and organisational factors could motivate organisations to make outsourcing decisions. Although previous scholarly studies have attempted to identify various environmental tendencies that encourage business organisations to make outsourcing decisions, only limited literature is available in the specific context of public organisations that decide to outsource their e-services to a specialised vendor from the private sector. The high contextual difference between the private and public sectors decreases the generalizability of these arguments for public organisations. It increases the need for more research to understand 'why' related aspects associated with public enterprises' decision to outsource e-services in the UK.

Based on the above arguments, the current research study proposes that considering environmental tendencies or motives for making outsourcing decisions is essential to understand how effective management of the outsourcing relationships leads towards successful outsourcing in targeted organisations

4 Conceptual framework

The relationship between trust and outsourcing success is complicated due to the presence of various moderators and mediators. First, it is essential to understand the factors that increase the trust between vendor and client organizations to develop trust.

4.1 Explanation of conceptual framework

Trust plays a central role in effective relational governance, which is strongly connected with the success of e-service outsourcing (Lee and Choi, 2011). A plethora of literature is available to confirm the importance of trust in outsourcing success (Alwahdani, 2019). However, only limited empirical research is available in the context of e-service outsourcing in public service organisations in the UK. Lee and Choi (2011) and Alwahdani (2019) have studied the influence of vendor and client relationship management on outsourcing success and found that outsourcing success largely depends on two pillars- contractual factors that represent the hard side of the outsourcing management, and mutual trust that represents the soft side of the outsourcing management (Barthelemy, 2001). Lee and Choi (2011) and Paravastu (2007) consider trust as the central factor mediating the effect of relationship management factors on effective relational governance in outsourcing. Studies like (Langfield-Smith and Smith, 2003 and Leeman and Reynolds, 2012) also found that the trust-based relationship between vendor and client significantly increases outsourcing success. The researchers further claim that besides formal relations, informal relation-building tactics build trust and ultimately increase outsourcing success chances.

Therefore, it is essential first to understand how management can foster trust in outsourcing relationships to enhance relational governance, which is strongly associated with outsourcing success. A previous scholarly study conducted by Swar *et al.* (2012) in the IT outsourcing context revealed that management could cultivate trust in outsourcing relationships through effective communication, cooperation and mutual understanding. Nguyen *et al.* (2006) also contended that management can develop a trust-based environment by adopting effective communication strategies, as open, transparent and well-balanced formal and informal communication between

outsourcing partners increases mutual trust, leading towards improved relational governance.

Similarly, Lahiri and Kedia (2011) guide outsourcing managers to adopt cooperative behaviour towards their outsourcing partners to develop trust-based relations. This cooperative behaviour denotes the willingness to help and support each other in achieving mutually beneficial objectives. Based on these arguments, the study argues that trust in outsourcing relationships depends on effective communication and cooperative behaviour towards outsourcing partners.

After understanding the factors influencing the trust among outsourcing partners, the researcher now evaluates how trust between vendor and client organisations enhances relational governance. The impact of trust on effective relational governance in the outsourcing context is mediated by knowledge-sharing propensity and commitment (Alwahdani, 2019). Studies like Alwahdani (2019) and Lee and Choi (2011) found that the trust between outsourcing partners encourages them to share essential knowledge, and a plethora of literature is available to confirm the effect of knowledge sharing and transfer on effective outsourcing relational governance. Besides knowledge sharing, trust also strongly impacts the partners' commitment to their outsourcing relationship. Various theoretical and empirical research studies like Goo, Huang and Hart (2008) and Ndubisi (2011) have established the significant impact of trust and commitment on effective relationship management, leading towards outsourcing success.

While contending on the same note, Ndubisi (2011) and Qi and Chau (2012) considered commitment and knowledge sharing as the most critical outcomes of trust, which enhance relational governance in outsourcing projects. Later studies (like Alwahdani, 2019) validate Qi and Chau's (2012) and Ndubisi's (2011) argument by proving the effect of trust on the commitment and knowledge sharing in outsourcing relationships and both trust consequences exert a direct impact on the outsourcing relational governance. Based on these arguments, the study asserts that when vendors and clients trust each other, this trust-based environment facilitates knowledge sharing and strengthens their commitment to the contractual relationship, leading towards enhanced relational governance.

The literature review further suggests that although trust facilitates knowledge sharing, mutual dependency between vendor and client positively moderates the effect of trust

on knowledge sharing. Lee and Huynh (2005) noted that mutual dependency does not directly impact knowledge sharing in outsourcing relationships, but it also influences the effect of trust on knowledge sharing. Lee and Kim (2005) agreed by mentioning that in the outsourcing context, mutual dependency denotes the relationship in which outsourcing partners share the risks and perceive mutual benefits from mutual interactions. The organisations' perceptions towards mutual dependency are formed by their overall perceptions of their dependency on their partner. Mutual dependency increases with an increase in the size and importance of the exchange (Heide and John, 1990). A later study by Lee and Kim (1999) also confirmed that mutual dependency positively influences partners' willingness to share knowledge. Based on these arguments, the researcher (in the outsourcing context) posits that when mutual dependency between vendor and client relationship is high, the effect of trust on the knowledge exchange between outsourcing partners will get strengthened.

To sum up, the discussion held up till now, the review of existing literature provides a solid theoretical foundation to argue that trust plays a central role in enhancing relational governance. Management can foster trust in outsourcing by employing effective communication strategies and adopting cooperative behaviour. This cooperation and communication foster trust, which enhances relational governance by facilitating knowledge sharing and strengthening the partners' commitment to the outsourcing relationship. The relationship between trust and knowledge sharing is influenced by mutual dependency, as higher mutual dependency enhances the impact of trust on knowledge sharing. Knowledge sharing and commitment ultimately improve the outsourcing relational governance, which increases the chances of outsourcing success.

According to Lee and Choi (2011), outsourcing success depends on the initial trust between client and vendor and the management's ability to consider trust as an ongoing factor for effective relational governance and, consequently, successful outsourcing (Lee and Choi, 2011). Organisations must continuously evaluate their relationship quality with outsourcing partners to ensure continued trust. This ongoing relationship management evaluation is made easier by continually investing in developing relation-building assets and adopting outsourcing relationship management tools and techniques. Outsourcing relationship management tools are primarily used for monitoring and measuring the relationship's effectiveness.

Although outsourcing relationship management tools are considered to be useful for effective relational governance, some scholars like (Hirschheim *et al.*, 2009) collected data from outsourcing partners and found that many participants are either unaware of the appropriate relationship management tools or they do not consider such tools to be worthy of investment. The effectiveness of outsourcing relationship management tools is still under debate, as the existing literature review provides inconsistent findings about the usefulness of outsourcing relationship management tools for fostering trust in outsourcing relationships (Alvarez, 2017; Agarwal *et al.* 2017). This contradiction in the previously proposed arguments motivated the researcher to explore the outsourcing managers' perceptions of these tools' usefulness through qualitative research. The qualitative data is also used to study the environmental tendencies (motives behind outsourcing decisions) to understand whether such motives impact the relationship between relational governance and outsourcing success.

The overall insights gained from the literature review are mapped into the following diagram:

Figure 1- Conceptual framework

Overall, the proposed conceptual framework includes various factors considered trust predictors and consequences, which increase outsourcing success chances through effective relational governance. The conceptual framework is tested by collecting both-qualitative and quantitative data. Quantitative data tests the proposed relationship between trust predictors and consequences, and qualitative data is used to consider the context in which the data collection process occurred. It is done by asking practitioners why they made outsourcing decisions, what other management-related factors influence relational governance, and what outsourcing relationship management tools are currently used to develop strong relations among outsourcing partners.

4.2 Variable operationalization and framework sub-parts

4.2.1 Communication, co-operative behaviour and trust

The conceptual framework can be divided into various sub-parts. The framework shows different ways management can increase outsourcing success chances through effective relational governance. The first sub-part of the framework includes two independent variables- effective communication and cooperative behaviour, and one dependent variable- trust. The relationship between effective communication, cooperative behaviour and trust has been discussed and validated by various previous studies, including Swar *et al.* (2012), and Lahiri and Kedia (2011).

Figure 2- Framework sub part-1

Following table concisely presents how each variable in this sub part are operationalized by taking theoretical support from previous studies:

4.2.2 *Trust, knowledge sharing and commitment.*

The second sub-part of the framework includes one independent variable- trust, two dependent variables- knowledge sharing and commitment, and one moderating variable- mutual dependency. The relationship between trust and knowledge sharing (Alwahdani, 2019) and trust and commitment (Ndubisi, 2011; Qi and Chau, 2012) has been established and needs further testing. Scholars like Lee and Kim (1999) and Lee and Huynh (2005) have stressed the need to check the moderating impact of mutual dependency while evaluating the impact of trust on knowledge sharing.

Figure 3- Framework sub part-2

4.2.3 Knowledge sharing, commitment and effective relational governance

The third sub-part of the framework includes two independent variables- knowledge sharing and commitment, and one dependent variable- effective relational governance. The relationship between knowledge sharing and effective relational governance (Qi and Chau, 2013; Teo and Bhattacharjee, 2014) and commitment between outsourcing partners and effective relational governance (Qi and Chau, 2013) have been discussed by previous scholars and require further research to understand better how both variables play a role in improving the relational governance.

The following table presents important information about the chosen variables:

Figure 4- Framework sub part-3

4.2.4 Effective relational governance and e-service outsourcing success

The last sub-part of the framework includes one independent variable- effective relational governance, one contextual variable- environmental tendencies and one dependent variable- outsourcing success. A plethora of literature is available to confirm the impact of effective relational governance on outsourcing success (Qi and Chau, 2013; Lioliou *et al.*, 2014) and some scholars (like Lahiri and Kedia (2011), Chen and Perry (2003), Mahalik (2010) and John and Janssen, 2010) have stressed over the importance of considering environmental tendencies while evaluating the factors influencing outsourcing success.

Figure 5- Framework sub part-4

4.3 Chapter summary

The literature review confirms that outsourcing failure has become a serious cause of concern for public organizations. Findings of previous studies consider relational governance as a key determinant of e-service outsourcing success, as poor relationship management is considered one of the key factors responsible for outsourcing failure. When effectively managed, relational governance becomes a value-adding function that drives the e-service outsourcing success chances. Literature places importance on trust and commitment and considers these two factors as critical success factors determining relational governance effectiveness. In light of social exchange theory, trust is considered socially embedded between outsourcing partners. Trust in outsourcing relationships is shaped by the underlying context in which relational exchange between outsourcing partners occurs. When outsourcing parties trust each other, they reciprocate the trust by demonstrating the commitment to fulfil contractual obligations and each other's expectations. Besides social exchange theory, the study also takes theoretical support from trust and commitment theory. It considers effective communication and a cooperative attitude as key trust determinants establishing trust. Once trust is established, the outsourcing parties strengthen their commitment and share valuable knowledge.

Although the literature review considers both- contractual and informal (relational) mechanisms as outsourcing success determinants, the focus of this research study remains on the informal, relational governance mechanisms, which means the study focuses on the soft relationship management factors that influence outsourcing success. The main reason for focusing on relational factors is that, according to the literature, most outsourcing failures occur due to management's poor understanding of the relational governance factors that could strengthen the ties between outsourcing parties. The knowledge gained from the literature review provides the theoretical foundation for this research. It provides a basis for the conceptual framework, refined and tested by collecting quantitative and qualitative data from targeted organizations.

Chapter Three- Research Methodology

3.1 Chapter introduction

The third chapter outlines the philosophical approach, strategy and methods that underpin current research. Choosing an appropriate research design is an essential concern for academic researchers. The central focus of this research study remains on exploring the relational governance-related factors essential for ensuring the successful completion of e-service outsourcing contracts in the UK. In the previous chapter, the researcher developed the theoretical understanding by exploring the relational governance factors influencing e-service outsourcing success in different world regions. Relevant theories and concepts were reviewed to construct the theoretical foundation. In this chapter, the researcher communicates how the research questions identified from a literature review are answered by conducting an empirical investigation into the selected research context.

The philosophical foundation of the research methodology is constructed by considering the nature of the research questions and the type of data needed to generate the desired knowledge. The literature review provided essential insights into predictors of effective relational governance and outsourcing success, emphasising trust. Analysing extracted insights by collecting and interpreting primary data can generate knowledge that could be applied to improve the success of e-service outsourcing in the UK. The chapter first describes the theoretical aspects of the research methodology, including research philosophy, approach and strategy. Afterwards, practical research methodology aspects are discussed to communicate how primary data has been collected and analysed to achieve the key research objectives.

3.2 Research philosophy

In the research philosophy section, the researcher first analyses the advantages and disadvantages of positivism and interpretivism, and the rest of the discussion critically analyses and justifies philosophical choice by reviewing how similar e-service outsourcing relational governance studies applied different philosophies, which were strengths and weaknesses of choosing each philosophy, and why particular philosophical choice is made for this research.

Research philosophy denotes an overall framework that sets the assumptions and guides the researcher about how the chosen research questions could be answered by collecting and analysing the data. Two central philosophical positions lie at the opposite ends of the research philosophy spectrum- positivism and interpretivism. All other philosophical stances can be between these ends (Alharahshehand Pius, 2020). The positivist philosophical stance is built on the belief that the credibility of knowledge is established by its logic and objectivity. Positivist research studies test existing theories to enhance the predictive understanding of the chosen research phenomenon (Alharahshehand Pius, 2020).

As mentioned by Lincoln and Guba (1985), positivism's origin dates back to the 19th century. The positivist inquiry model considers truth logical, objective, prevailing and strictly detached from the researcher. The positivist philosophical stance becomes evident when quantifiable variables are evaluated through hypothesis testing (Ryan, 2018). Although positivist studies offer more reliable and generalizable knowledge with enhanced practical applicability, this philosophical stance is criticized for its highly structured and rigid design that imposes strict data collection and analysis constraints. This methodological inflexibility can discourage divergent thinking and ignore the underlying context, which is essential for more accurate understanding (Spicer, 2004).

Contrary to positivist studies, interpretive studies aim to understand the research phenomenon by exploring the meanings that people assign to them based on their understanding, perceptions, opinions and experiences. Interpretive research methods conduct the subjective evaluation to gain in-depth knowledge of the research phenomenon (Goldkuhl, 2012). Interpretivists believe that social reality is subjective and socially constructed, increasing the need to employ qualitative research methods to understand reality in its underlying social context (Antwiand Hamza, 2015). Interpretive studies explore the individuals' perceptions to understand the research problem. This philosophical stance is mainly adopted when the researcher intends to explore an under-explored research phenomenon without adequate prior knowledge of relevant literature streams (Goldkuhl, 2012).

Interpretive studies provide a more accurate understanding of reality by realizing that reality is multi-dimensional, complex and can have multiple interpretations. In contrast, positivist studies tend to over-simplify reality, which may lead towards incomplete or inaccurate understanding. However, subjective assessment weakens the reliability and increases the chances of bias as the researcher actively gets involved in the data collection and analysis process (Antwi and Hamza, 2015).

Relational governance researchers have discussed the advantages and disadvantages of applying positivism and interpretivism in outsourcing. Although scholars like Di Guardo *et al.* (2012) relate the e-service outsourcing research problem to the information system literature stream, instead of exploring the technical factors that may play their role in determining outsourcing success, the focus of the current study remains on the soft aspects of contractual management (like effective communication and co-operation) that determine the trust, and increase chances of outsourcing success through effective relational governance. Therefore, the advantages and disadvantages of each philosophical position are analysed by taking references from outsourcing trust and relational governance literature, which lies more towards organizational management than the information system side.

Positivist e-service outsourcing and relational governance studies hold objective and realist ontology, where ontology denotes the assumptions about the reality nature of reality. For positivist e-governance studies, the key assumed variables (like trust, commitment, relationship management, communication and coordination skills, leadership style, etc.) exist. It could be related to causal relations that are understandable by generalizable laws. For example, Chamas (2017) adopted the positivism philosophy to study the influence of contextual factors on e-governance success. The positivist philosophy guided the Chamas (2017) to adopt a highly structured approach to construct mathematically quantifiable relationships between identified contextual factors and success determinants. Although it enabled Chamas (2017) to model the statistical relationship and propose generalizable, reliable and practically applicable results, Chamas (2017) remained unable to dig deeper, as philosophical rigidity inhibited the divergent thinking abilities of the researcher, due to which Chamas (2017) called for more qualitative, interpretive research to explore/detect new aspects of the proposed model possibly.

The literature review identifies various studies that attempted to explore different relational governance and e-service outsourcing mechanisms by adopting an interpretive philosophy. These studies have their strengths and weaknesses. For example, Alwahdani (2017), Gregory *et al.* (2009) and Søderberg *et al.* (2013)- all these studies adopted interpretive philosophy to explore the role played by trust in managing the IT outsourcing relationships. The interpretive philosophy guided all these researchers to assume that trust as a phenomenon is socially constructed and could be understood by exploring the meanings assigned to it by the individuals based on their subjective perceptions, opinions and experiences (Antwiand Hamza, 2015). The epistemological position rests on the assumption that researchers must focus on exploring the meanings and perceptions towards the chosen phenomenon (trust in outsourcing relations).

By conducting qualitative research, these outsourcing relational governance researchers accepted another assumption that their interests, views and perceptions could not be separated from the research process (Becker and Niehaves, 2007). The detachment avoidance and methodological flexibility to interpret the findings through divergent thinking enabled these studies to provide in-depth knowledge with high validity. The complexity of relational governance mechanisms, how trust is formed and how it could be sustained by managing the contextual factors was effectively explained in greater depth than Chamas (2017), whose focus remained on testing the hypothesized relationships. However, unlike Chamas (2017), the findings of Alwahdani (2017), Gregory *et al.* (2009), and Søderberg *et al.* (2013) lacked breadth due to a specific focus on the targeted variables. They were comparatively less reliable due to a lack of objectivity.

Based on an analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of each philosophy and their relevance to the chosen research topic, the philosophical position of current research can be placed between positivism and interpretivism. Combining both interpretive and positivist philosophical components into a single research study enables the researcher to offset the weaknesses of one philosophical position with the strengths of another.

3.3 Justification for the philosophical position taken by current research.

The study applies the positivist philosophical position by conducting a quantitative survey to test the effect of trust predictors on outsourcing trust, relational governance and outsourcing success. The positivist philosophy guided the researcher to quantify the impact of each variable on the dependent variable and determine the extent to which identified variables predict relational governance effectiveness and outsourcing success (Antwiand Hamza, 2015). An advantage of applying positivist philosophy to current research is that the researcher collected data from many participants and offered reliable knowledge with high practical applicability (Goldkuhl, 2012).

Previous studies like Chamas (2017) also considered positivist philosophy a suitable approach for testing the validity of trust and commitment theory for predicting outsourcing success in e-governance. However, more than sole reliance on the positivist philosophy was needed to understand the underlying context. As mentioned in the literature, the effectiveness of relational governance and its impact on e-service outsourcing success derives a strong influence from the prevailing contextual factors that motivated the firm to make e-service outsourcing decisions (Rannard *et al.*, 2016). Understanding the tendencies or motives to enter into contractual relationships, the relationship between trust, relational governance and outsourcing success can be well understood (Ali *et al.*, 2018).

For this purpose, the researcher applied interpretive philosophy and conducted some in-depth qualitative interviews with the target participants, intending to understand the importance of trust for effective relational governance and outsourcing success based on the perceptions and experiences of the target participants. As mentioned, many previous relational governance studies adopted the interpretive stance to propose new and exciting insights that reflected the complexity of managing trust in outsourcing relationships. However, the findings proposed by these studies (Alwahdani, 2017; Gregory *et al.*, 2009; Søderberg *et al.*, 2013) lacked reliability and generalizability, due to which the offered results could not be applied by other organizations involved in e-service outsourcing.

Although previous discussions on the positivist and interpretive philosophies revolved around the contradictions of both philosophies, recently, discussions have shifted to the possible complementary nature of different philosophical positions and

the possibilities of integrating them into a single study (Spicer, 2004). It gave rise to the popularity of mixed-method research, a standard method in outsourcing relational governance literature. Cao and Lumineau (2015) and Venkatesh *et al.* (2013) advocate the combination of positivist and interpretive philosophies by contending to provide a more comprehensive and accurate view of reality. For example, by applying the pragmatic philosophy, Moatshe (2014) was able to not only explore the factors that influence the e-service implementation success (through in-depth interviews with the e-service professionals and citizens) but also quantify the effect of each variable on the e-service success (through a survey with citizens) for proposing reliable and generalizable results.

In the above example, methodological freedom enabled the researcher to employ different research methods for answering the research questions from multiple dimensions. In the current case, the use of both philosophical stances enabled the researcher to not only study the cause-and-effect relationship between trust, relational governance and outsourcing success but also understand the context in which the initial trust is formulated, how it is sustained, and how motives/tendencies to outsource the e-services possibly influence the relational governance effectiveness. Therefore, the current study combined the logic and objectivity of positivism (through the use of quantitative method) with the in-depth, subjective exploration characteristic of interpretivism (through the use of qualitative method) to provide deeper and broader knowledge about research problems with high reliability and validity.

The following table briefly describes each philosophical position's essential features, advantages, disadvantages, and relevance to current research. The table also describes the ontological and epistemological perspectives of three philosophical positions along with common data collection and analysis strategies advocated by each philosophy:

Philosophical position	Positivism	Interpretivism	Pragmatism
Approach	Deductive	Inductive	Both- inductive and deductive
Methods	Quantitative	Qualitative	Both- quantitative and qualitative
Epistemology	Trust in outsourcing relationships is an objective reality, and as research phenomenon, it's relationship with relational governance effectiveness and outsourcing success can be understood through scientific testing. The scientific testing could be done by statistically quantifying the effect of trust on relational governance and e-service outsourcing success	Trust in outsourcing relationships is a complex phenomenon that is socially constructed. This social construction takes place when individuals (outsourcing partners) assign meaning to the trust based on their perceptions, opinions, and experiences. The relation between trust, relational governance and outsourcing success is subjective in nature with no objective existence.	Trust, and its relationship with the relational governance effectiveness and outsourcing success is both- objective as well as subjective in nature, and this research phenomenon can be effectively understood by taking a position in between objectivity and subjectivity.
Ontology	Trust and its impact on relational governance and e-service outsourcing success is a single reality that is provable, testable and observable by taking in independent position	The influence of trust on the relational governance and e-service outsourcing success does not exist as a single reality, and instead depends on interpretive contexts	Focus of a researcher must on 'what' could work to understand the reality rather than focusing what could be considered

			objective, real or true
Appropriate data collection strategies for current study	Close-ended survey questionnaire	Semi-structured interviews (although interpretivism advocates many other qualitative methods also)	Use both data collection strategies according to what works best to achieve the research objectives
Data analysis	Statistical relationship testing	Thematic analysis	Both
Findings	Reliable and generalisable with high practical applicability	Low generalisability but multiple perspectives could be offered	Findings are corroborated and can be generalized
Relevance	Relevant because conceptual model that is based on the trust and commitment theory needs to be statistically tested to quantify the impact of 1) trust predictors on trust, 2) trust on relational governance effectiveness, and 3) relational governance effectiveness on e-service outsourcing success.	Relevant because the effectiveness of relational governance for ensuring success of outsourcing relationships needs an in-depth understanding of underlying context in which outsourcing decision was made. The interpretivism makes understanding the context in which research problem resides easier	High relevance, as it allows the research to statistically test the framework, and also understand the context in which trust based relational governance enhances success chances of e-service outsourcing in UK.
Advantages	Improved reliability, enhanced generalisability, greater practical	Incorporation of interpretive contexts enhance depth of understanding,	Offer both- breadth and depth of understanding. Model can be

	<p>applicability, ability to cover various dimensions of the research problem (effect of communication and co-operation on trust, effect of trust on knowledge sharing and commitment, effect of commitment and knowledge sharing on relational governance effectiveness and e-service outsourcing success) to get broader understanding of problem</p>	<p>divergent thinking increases chances of proposing unique/new insights</p>	<p>statistically tested, and underlying context could be qualitatively explored, leading towards a more reliable, valid and accurate understanding</p>
Disadvantages	<p>Reduced depth of understanding, no divergent thinking, rigid methodological principles that may inhibit discovery of new insights about trust and relational governance in e-service outsourcing,</p>	<p>Reduced reliability and weak generalisability, results may lack specificity, with inability to incorporate different dimensions of research problem (like understanding relationship between communication, co-operation and trust; trust, knowledge sharing and commitment; and knowledge sharing,</p>	<p>Combination of both- qualitative and quantitative data can be complex and more time consuming</p>

		commitment and effective relational governance for e-service outsourcing success can be difficult and more time-consuming if only qualitative research methods are used	
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Table 7- Ontological and epistemological perspectives of three philosophical positions

The above table provides justification for why the current research study takes philosophical position in between positivism and interpretivism.

3.4 Research approach

A research approach denotes the overall research procedure from broader assumptions to specific data collection and analysis techniques. Academic studies usually use inductive or deductive approaches to generate the desired knowledge. The inductive approach is usually qualitative and takes philosophical support from the interpretive philosophy, whereas the deductive approach is usually quantitative and takes philosophical support from the positivist philosophy (Soiferman, 2010). Inductive researchers focus on generating new theories and adding theoretical contributions to the existing literature. In contrast, the main focus of deductive researchers remains on testing existing theories to provide practically applicable knowledge. Choosing an appropriate research approach requires the researcher to review how previous scholars from the chosen study field have discussed the strengths and weaknesses of each approach and which approach seems to be best for achieving the current research objectives (Antwiand Hamza, 2015).

For the current study, the incorporation of both inductive and deductive approaches seems the most appropriate choice because the study derives its philosophical support

from pragmatism, considers inductive and deductive approaches to knowledge development complementary, and advocates the use of both in a single research setting for a better understanding of research problem. The support for combining the inductive and deductive approaches is taken from the modified grounded theory approach, which argues that main categories/dimensions for data analysis could be derived from an existing theory and could be complemented and further inductively developed based on the empirical data (Perry and Jensen, 2001). Combining inductive and deductive reasoning is also becoming common in the relational governance literature to achieve plurality through combining data richness and rigour (Ashworth *et al.*, 2019).

Taking the theoretical guidance from Perry and Jensen's (2001) work, the deductive approach is applied by identifying the predictors and consequences of trust in the context of e-service outsourcing relational governance. Trust and commitment theory provided theoretical support here. The deductive logic required the researcher to quantify the relationship between identified variables to understand the factors that influence trust and quantify the impact of trust consequences on the relational governance effectiveness of e-service outsourcing contracts (Soiferman, 2010). A follow-up inductive logic guided the researcher to explore how effective management can develop and sustain trust and how contextual factors that motivated the firm to make outsourcing decisions play their role in determining relational governance effectiveness. In this way, the strengths and weaknesses of both approaches were offset (Spicer, 2004).

3.5 Research strategy

After discussing and justifying this research's philosophical position and approach, this section explains the overall research strategy employed to conduct the empirical investigation. The choice of the most appropriate research strategy required the researcher to glimpse related research studies conducted in similar contexts with similar objectives. The literature review highlighted that most previous studies (like Lander *et al.*, 2004; Ashaye, 2014) preferred case studies over survey and experimental research because the case study strategy enabled them to generate more context-specific knowledge. The selection of an appropriate strategy required the researcher to apply the conditions proposed by Yin (2003), who argued that the appropriateness of a research

strategy is determined by the nature of research objectives and the underlying research context. The nature of current research objectives is quantitative as well as qualitative in nature. Research objectives are quantitative because they require statistical testing of the proposed relationships mapped in the conceptual framework. A part of the research objectives is qualitative as it requires consideration of environmental tendencies/motives/factors that motivated the public service firms in the UK to outsource e-services to the private sector.

The chosen research area- relational governance in the e-service outsourcing relationships is an inter-disciplinary field, which makes choosing an appropriate research strategy even more difficult. The research objectives nature and type of data required to accomplish objectives required the development of a conceptual framework for evaluating how e-service outsourcing success can be enhanced through trust-based relational governance. First, the initial conceptual framework was developed based on a literature review. Trust and commitment theory provided a theoretical foundation for placing trust as the central factor determining relational governance effectiveness.

The framework required testing in a selected research context. Complementing the deductive approach with inductive reasoning further enhanced the tested framework by collecting qualitative data and exploring management-related factors that may play their role in enhancing trust-based relational governance effectiveness (Spicer, 2004). Applying the inductive approach also required the researcher to consider the contextual factors responsible for the outsourcing decision. As each organization operates in a specific context, the type of knowledge requires the researcher to choose a research strategy that focuses on choosing a specific rather than general research context, and therefore, the case study strategy appeared as a suitable choice for current research (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006).

A case study strategy is also common in the relational governance and e-services outsourcing literature. Previous scholars like (Lander *et al.*, 2004; Ashaye, 2014) consider it a valid research strategy and a distinctive evaluation tool that could be adapted according to different contexts and different evidence and could also be used for assessing and testing the existing theories. Lander *et al.* (2004) further mentioned that relational governance dynamics of e-service outsourcing can only be effectively studied in the context in which the contract occurred. Although case study was primarily considered as a purely qualitative research strategy, later studies (like Sharp *et al.* 2012) discussed that case study strategy is more appropriate for mixed method

studies that aim at exploring a broader and deeper knowledge, as this strategy narrows down the context, making it possible for researchers to generate the knowledge with desired breadth and depth in limited time. Sharp *et al.* (2012) further asserted that a case study is an appropriate strategy for answering both- which and how related questions-

- Which management-related factors predict the trust in e-service outsourcing relationships, leading towards enhanced relational governance effectiveness?
- To what extent does effective relational governance influence e-service outsourcing success?
- How do environmental tendencies that motivate public service firms to make outsourcing decisions influence relational governance effectiveness?

The experimental strategy did not suit current research as the selected research phenomenon cannot be experimentally tested, and the time constraints make it possible for the researcher to experiment over an extended period. The survey strategy lost relevance due to its general context. Other strategies (like action research and grounded theory) are also needed to match the nature of research objectives and the data type required to do this research. It justified the decision to prefer the case study over other research strategies (Saunders and Lewis, 2012).

Case studies can be single or multiple. Single case studies focus on a single entity to generate highly context-specific knowledge. At the same time, multiple case studies focus on two or more entities to compare findings and propose results rooted in multiple pieces of evidence. In the current case, the multiple case study emerged as a more appropriate choice because the researcher not only wanted to understand the trust predictors and consequences in outsourcing relations but also aimed to explore the possible role of contextual factors. To elaborate further, if a single case study strategy were chosen, then it would not have been easy to understand if motives to make outsourcing decisions could influence the relational governance effectiveness (Aberdeen, 2013).

By conducting research in two or more organizations that made outsourcing decisions with different motives (like cost, quality or non-availability of required competencies), the comparison will make it easier for the researcher to understand the possible variation in the relational governance effectiveness due to changed context. Another reason for preferring multiple over single case study research is that the researcher wanted to test the proposed conceptual framework. The framework testing required a comparatively broad research context so that quantitative data could be collected from

a large sample size. Data collection from multiple organizations enhanced the rigour, and focus on comparatively few entities than a typical survey strategy enhanced the data richness (Gustafsson, 2017).

By applying multiple case study research, the researcher collected data from three public service organizations in the UK that outsourced their e-services to third parties in the private sector with different motives. The following table summarizes the key strengths, weaknesses and overall relevance of the multiple case study strategy for current research by taking examples from the relevant literature streams:

Justification for Choosing Multiple Case Studies over Single Case Study:

Lander *et al.* (2004) collected data from a single organization to explore trust-building mechanisms in IT projects. The specific focus on a single organization enabled the researcher to offer more detailed, in-depth and better theory (Dyer and Wilkins, 1991). However, the small sample size affected the generalizability and limited the applicability of the proposed results for other organizations. Lander *et al.* (2004) suggested that future researchers adopt the multiple case study strategy to collect data from a comparatively broader context for generating knowledge about trust-based mechanisms with comparatively better generalizability.

On the other hand, adopting a multiple case study strategy enabled Ashaye (2014) to explore the relational governance dynamics of e-governance implementation in Nigerian public firms. Multiple case study strategies enhanced the strength and reliability of the proposed evidence. A broader discovery of theoretical evolution was also ensured as evidence was rooted in three organizations. Proposed recommendations were more deeply grounded in multiple pieces of evidence, paving the way for proposing a more convincing theory (as mentioned by Eisenhardt and Graebner, 2007). However, as per Baxter and Jack (2008), multiple case studies are more time-consuming and complex than single case studies and do not suit when a specific research focus remains on conducting an in-depth exploration of a particular phenomenon.

In the current case, the researcher is interested in both- gaining detailed knowledge about trust and relational governance with adequate breadth and depth, and comparing the relational governance dynamics of different public service organizations that made outsourcing decisions with different motives, indicating the need to adopt multiple case study strategy according to Yin's (2003) suggestion.

3.6 Mixed research method

The justification for the mixed method approach by combining both- positivist and interpretive philosophies has already been detailed in section 3.2. In this section, the discussion aims to describe in detail how each research method has been applied to accomplish the research objectives and generate the required knowledge.

The current research study primarily focused on exploring the power of trust to predict relational governance effectiveness and e-service outsourcing success. Trust and commitment theory guided the researcher in identifying trust predictors and consequent outcomes that lead towards enhanced relational governance. Quantitative data based on positivist philosophical rules guided the researcher to test the causal relationships between identified variables (effective communication, cooperation, trust, knowledge sharing, commitment, relational governance and e-service outsourcing success) (Byrne and Humble, 2007). Although the main focus of this research study was on exploring how management-related factors that form the trust between outsourcing parties determine outsourcing success through effective relational governance, the study benefitted from the flexibility granted by the qualitative research method by exploring contextual factors that play an essential role in determining the effect of relational governance on the outsourcing success but cannot be gauged through quantitative research methods (Malina *et al.*, 2011).

One of the advantages of collecting qualitative data for the current research study was that it promoted divergent thinking and allowed the researcher to freely interpret the results without following any rigid philosophical and methodological rules (as imposed by positivist quantitative methods) (Byrne and Humble, 2007). The current study also explored some new findings during the collection and analysis of quantitative data, which needed to be highlighted by quantitative data. It was done by 1) exploring the environmental tendencies or factors that encouraged the organizations to make outsourcing decisions and 2) analysing other possible factors that influence the quality of relational governance and cannot be explored by asking close-ended questions.

For example, the researcher identified trust, its predictors and consequences in the relational governance context from literature and tested the predictive capability of each construct by collecting quantitative data. However, preliminary interview findings highlighted that management's willingness to use supportive relation management tools to facilitate communication with the outsourcing partners makes trust formulation and

sustaining easier. The practitioners shared mixed insights towards the usefulness of outsourcing relationship management tools. The researcher also explored the reasons for the negative perceptions of some practitioners towards outsourcing relationship management tools' usefulness. The purpose was to understand how these tools could be improved to maximize their effectiveness.

All these insights were unexpected and new, further enhancing the understanding of how relational governance can be improved to increase outsourcing success chances. The qualitative data also introduced some new variables (to be added later) into the conceptual framework developed based on literature review and tested by collecting quantitative data. The newly identified management-related factors that influence trust could not be discovered in the literature review, and their discovery made a unique contribution to the existing pool of knowledge.

Overall, the qualitative data complemented the quantitative information in various ways, like:

- By enhancing the data richness, rigour was established through quantitative data (Creswell, 1999)
- By validating the findings obtained through quantitative research (Byrne and Humble, 2007)
- By answering the specific part of the research objective (exploration of environmental tendencies for outsourcing decisions) that could not be effectively done through quantitative research.
- Refining the tested framework through the identification/discovery of new management-related factors that influence trust in outsourcing relations (Byrne and Humble, 2007).

Triangulation of literature review, quantitative survey and qualitative interview findings enhanced the overall research quality and allowed the researcher to understand the research problem from different perspectives (Casey and Murphy, 2009). After justifying why mixed method research suited current research work, the following section explains how data was collected under the mixed method approach, what the target population was, which sampling techniques were applied and what overall procedure was followed to complete the data collection process.

3.7 Data collection strategies for mixed method research

3.7.1 Target population

The target population of the current research study can be defined at organizational and individual levels. At the organization level, the study targeted three public service organizations in the UK that outsourced their e-services to the private sector with different motives (like cost, quality and non-availability of required competencies). At the individual level, the study mainly targeted client organizations. The target population for quantitative surveys was the middle-level managers working in the targeted public service organizations and actively managing the outsourcing relationships. The exact population group was targeted for collecting the interview data. However, the study also targeted another population segment for interviews- outsourcing managers in respective vendor organizations. The purpose of incorporating vendors' perspectives was to explore the importance of trust for effective relational governance from multiple perspectives. In both cases, the middle-level management staff responsible for managing different relationship management dynamics was contacted to get the required knowledge.

3.7.2 Sampling strategy

In academic research, sampling strategies can be broadly classified into two categories: random and non-random. Random sampling is more reliable as each population unit has equal selection chances. At the same time, non-random sampling is practical when the researcher cannot secure access to each population unit or when data collection mode makes applying random sampling difficult (Delice, 2010). A non-random sampling strategy is also suitable when data needs to be collected from a specific population segment (Delice, 2010). By considering the current research context, non-random sampling seems more suitable than random sampling for qualitative and quantitative data collection for the following reasons:

- Online data collection made the application of the random sampling strategy difficult.

- The researcher needed equal access to all managerial staff members employed in three targeted public service organisations in the UK.
- Convenience sampling (non-random sampling) was easier to apply, and its combination with another non-random sampling- snowball sampling further made the research process more accessible by creating a chain effect. The respondents were requested to forward the questionnaire to their colleagues working in managerial positions and know the relational governance dynamics of e-service outsourcing (Taherdoost, 2016).

However, it is essential to note that using a non-random sampling strategy affected the sample's representativeness for the target population and the reliability due to the chances of biased selection. In order to collect the qualitative data, the purposive sampling strategy was used because the researcher wanted to interview managers with specific characteristics (Tongco, 2007). The interviewees were selected based on the following criteria:

- The interviewee must hold a middle or senior professional position in the targeted organisation.
- The interviewee must have spent at least five years at the current organisation to share informed insights based on experience.
- The interviewee must actively handle the relational governance dynamics of the e-service outsourcing contract.

The application of convenience and snowball sampling enabled the researcher to survey 100 respondents. However, due to time constraints, the researcher conducted nine interviews with the client organisations and only three with the vendor organisations. Sharing further details about the survey sample, the researcher was able to draw responses from only 87 respondents initially. Then, after sending two reminder emails and creating a chain of referrals by applying the snowball sampling technique, the researcher was able to draw responses from 41 more respondents. In total, 128 responses were received. However, only 100 out of 128 survey questionnaires were filled and were error-free. So, the final selected survey sample size was 100 respondents. The interview administration was more time-consuming than surveys, as the researcher had to interact with each interviewee to collect data personally. Initially, 11 respondents from the client organisation accepted the interview invitation, but only nine participated in the interviews, and the other two apologised for their participation

for personal reasons. Four interview invitations were accepted in vendor organisations, of which three participated, and one withdrew from the process after accepting the invitation. In this way, in the available time, the researcher could get quantitative data from 100 respondents and qualitative data from 12 respondents (9 from clients and three from vendor organisations).

3.7.3 Data collection techniques, instrument and protocol

In order to collect the quantitative data, a close-ended survey questionnaire was used. The questionnaire was developed by identifying the variables and their constructs from the previous literature. The tables in section 2.5 of the literature review section provide detailed information about the variables, their sample constructs and sources from where they are identified. The close-ended questionnaire contained eight variables (communication, cooperation, trust, knowledge sharing, mutual dependency, commitment, relational governance, and e-service outsourcing success). The responses were recorded using the five-point Likert agreement scale, and the reason for using this scale is that its validity and reliability for measuring the perceptions and opinions towards relational governance dynamics has been previously tested and confirmed.

In the Likert scale, the researcher can use different numbers of responses, starting from 3 responses up to 10 according to the nature and need of the research nature and methodology design (Brown, 2015). In this research, the researcher used the five-point scale for several reasons. The main reason is its simplicity and ease of use for the participants. Also, the five points consume little time for the participants to decide without getting overwhelmed. The five-point scale also gives many options but only a few to the researcher and the participants by which the scale of different opinions can be adequately measured (Raymond and Haladyna, 2016).

The Likert scale makes the response rate much better than higher response points and, conversely, makes it easier for the researcher to analyse the extensive data (Raymond and Haladyna, 2016).

The internal consistency of the questionnaire was further established by conducting a small-scale pilot research. Data from 30 survey participants was collected to check the

Cronbach alpha value scored by each variable. The reliability test confirmed that the survey questionnaire is internally consistent and reliable for collecting data from the targeted population set (Santos, 1999).

To collect the qualitative data, the researcher used a highly popular- interviewing qualitative research method. Interviews are considered one of the oldest and most extensively used methods for exploring the research problem (Harper, 2011). The use of interviewing techniques for data collection is also common among relational governance and e-service outsourcing scholars (like Chen and Perry, 2003; Pluggeand Nikou, 2021). Interviewing data collection strategy can be divided into three strategies: structured, semi-structured, and unstructured (Harper, 2011). Among these three strategies, semi-structured interviewing appeared as the most appropriate technique because it guided the researcher to use the probing technique while maintaining a loose structure. Unstructured interviews could be challenging to handle as the discussion detracts from the primary research problem, and structured interviews allow limited scope for digging deep to discover unexpected results (Wethington and McDarby, 2015). Interviews were conducted over the telephone to avoid the time and travel costs and make participation in the interviewing process more convenient for the interviewees. However, telephonic interviews inhibited the researcher from observing the non-verbal communication cues (like facial expressions, body language, etc.), considered an essential source of information during interviewing (Sturges and Hanrahan, 2004).

The interview guideline mainly contained questions related to 'Why do public service firms outsource e-services?', 'What were the key motivations?', 'How' do such motivations influence the relational governance dynamics, 'Why' is trust important in outsourcing relations, and 'What' management strategies influence the trust in outsourcing relationships. The discussion focused on trust in outsourcing relations, the effectiveness of relational governance, and motivations for outsourcing decisions.

The following table summarises the strengths and limitations of the close-ended survey and interviewing technique. The comparison of both data collection strategies highlights their complementary nature and the opportunity for current research to combine both techniques to offset their strengths and weaknesses:

Justification of the development of the survey instrument:

Data collected through close-ended surveys had high response consistency across survey respondents. Survey administration from a large sample size was time-efficient and more straightforward.

It helped the researcher quantify variables' impact on the relational governance effectiveness. Collected data was analysed using interesting visual tools (like pie and bar charts). Statistical data made comparison of case study firms easier (Reja *et al.*, 2003).

However, sole reliance on the close-ended survey results increased the reliance on the assumption that all participants shared their honest opinions and that there was no hidden agenda. This assumption could be untrue. The lack of personalisation and freedom to record any response reduced the depth of understanding. Survey results also needed to be more comprehensive to explore the 'underlying context' in which the outsourcing decision was made (Fricker and Schonlau, 2002).

In semi-structured interviews, Participants had more freedom to respond and share their experiences related to managing trust in outsourcing relations; they freely shared information about the motivations behind outsourcing decisions, highlighted some weaknesses in existing management practices, and proposed suggestions for fixing them. Interview data provided valuable insights to achieve the second research objective and refine the proposed conceptual framework that was quantitatively tested (Cachia and Millward, 2011).

However, if the researcher had only depended on the semi-structured interview findings, the results would have been harder to tabulate for a clear comparison. Chances of subjective misinterpretation also remain there. Moreover, the researcher could only conduct interviews with a small sample size. Only interview findings are insufficient to test the model, as model testing requires the researcher to quantify the proposed relationships (Alshenqeti, 2014).

The researcher used the combination of both data collection strategies to collect the data required to accomplish both research objectives (Harris and Brown, 2010).

One disadvantage of this combination was that the data collection process took more time, and analysis also became more complex and challenging as the researcher

compared both data and critically analysed the comparison in light of the literature (Harris and Brown, 2010).

3.7.4 Overall data collection process

The overall data collection process followed a step-wise procedure, as depicted in following diagram:

The research process started with problem definition. Afterwards, review of relevant theories (particularly trust and commitment theory) and concepts constructed theoretical foundation. A conceptual framework developed and research questions refined based on the theoretical knowledge gained from literature review. Based on that, appropriate research methodology selected (mixed methodology, both-quantitative and qualitative). Data collection and analysis process followed these steps:

Figure 6- Flow-chart- data collection process

After completing the data collection process, the collected survey and interview data were analysed by applying appropriate analysis techniques (discussed in detail in section 3.8). The survey and interview findings from each of the three public service organizations, along with interviews with their respective vendors, were analysed and compared according to the multiple case study research strategy guidelines. The triangulation technique was applied by comparing and triangulating surveys, interviews (with client organizations), interviews (with vendor organizations) and literature findings. Overall, quantitative and qualitative data was analysed in light of literature to validate and refine the conceptual framework, and a refined conceptual model for effective trust-based relational governance and e-service outsourcing success was drawn in the context of public service firms in the UK. Finally, the conclusion was drawn, and the overall research process was completed. The diagram shows that the researcher applied a sequential explanatory data collection design, which means, firstly, quantitative data was collected. Then, qualitative data was collected to explain further and refine the findings obtained through quantitative research.

The following methodology matrix for exploring the relational governance dynamics of e-service outsourcing contracts explains the consistency and alignment between chosen research objectives, methods, data collection and data analysis strategies:

Research questions(what the researcher needs to know?)	What can be done to know this (research goals?)	Sampling decisions (from where the required data could be found?)	Data collection methods (what kind of data researcher needs to find to know this?)	Whom should researcher access to get the required data from the targeted population?	How collected data could be analysed to answer the research questions?

Which management related factors positively influence the trust-based relational governance effectiveness and e-service outsourcing success?	Explore the factors (such as- communication, cooperative behaviour, trust, knowledge sharing and commitment) that influence the relational governance effectiveness, which leads towards e-service outsourcing success.	Managerial staff employed in targeted three public service organizations in UK who outsourced their e-services to the private vendors (middle level), managers working in respective vendor organizations of each targeted public service firm, who are responsible for managing relationships with clients	Close-ended survey, semi-structured interviews	Responsible authorities in targeted organizations that can grant official permission to conduct surveys and interviews with the targeted population, and can also give access to their contact information	Multiple case, statistical analysis through SPSS, descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation and multiple linear regression to measure the cause and effect relationship between variables mapped in the framework, along with audio taping, transcription and manual thematic analysis
How do environment	Explore the environmenta	Senior/middle level	Close-ended	Responsible	audio taping,

al tendencies that motivate the public service firms to outsource e-services influence the trust based relational governance effectiveness and e-service outsourcing success?	l tendencies that motivate public service organizations to outsource the e-services, and analyse how such tendencies may influence the relational governance effectiveness and e-service outsourcing success	managers of targeted three public service organizations, s, outsourcing managers from respective vendor firms	survey, semi-structured interviews	authorities in targeted organizations who can grant official permission and access to the targeted population units	transcripti on and manual thematic analysis
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Table 10- Alignment between chosen research objectives, methods, data collection and data analysis strategies

The above table is developed by adapting Maxwell's (2013) research methodology matrix. The components briefly discussed in the table have been discussed in detail in the preceding and succeeding sections.

3.7.5 Reliability, validity and trustworthiness

The reliability of the survey questionnaire was ensured by conducting a small pilot research. A reliability test was run, and each variable's Cronbach alpha score was interpreted to ensure that each computed variable earned above 0.7 Cronbach alpha value. According to Santos (1999), above 0.7 Cronbach alpha shows that the survey questionnaire has high internal consistency. The internal validity was ensured using simple language to make the questionnaire understandable. The construct validity was

ensured by identifying the variables and their constructs from the literature review (Bolarinwa, 2015). In order to ensure external validity, the sample size was kept large to enhance its representativeness for the population (Fink and Litwin, 1995).

In order to enhance the trustworthiness, specific steps were taken. For example, the researcher requested independent research experts to check the identified themes against the initially generated code list to ensure that the thematic analysis remains credible. It was done to highlight and fix possible biases in the theme-generation process (Fink and Litwin, 1995). Confirmability is another important trustworthiness dimension ensured by verifying the transcripts. The collected interview data was sent back to the interviewees so that they could review and approve or highlight the possible mistakes in recording, transcription and interpretation (Roberts and Priest, 2006). Dependability- The third dimension of trustworthiness was ensured by getting all interviews recorded and transcribed with the help of speech-to-text software. It enabled the researcher to avoid possible information loss. The researcher collected high-quality information from experienced professionals by setting purposive sampling criteria (Shenton, 2004).

After explaining how the researcher enhanced the reliability, validity and trustworthiness of proposed results, the following section discusses the data analysis techniques applied to collected quantitative and qualitative data to answer the research question and achieve the proposed research objectives.

3.8 Data analysis

Choosing appropriate data analysis techniques is essential for extracting the maximum information from the collected data set. The current study employed different analysis techniques for quantitative and qualitative data analysis. First, quantitative data was interpreted, then qualitative data was analysed for a more refined understanding. Starting with quantitative data, the researcher used SPSS for data analysis purposes. After completing the survey, the data was entered in SPSS, and first of all, a simple descriptive analysis was run to extract the essential information from the data set. The mean values were analysed to understand the participants' general perceptions and opinions towards the asked variables (Mishra *et al.*, 2019). A participant profile was developed by conducting a percentage analysis of survey respondents' gender, age, experience and role in the outsourcing relationship. Mean values reflected overall data

trends indicating whether the overall perceptions towards communication effectiveness, cooperation, trust, knowledge sharing, commitment, relational governance effectiveness and e-service outsourcing success are mainly positive or negative (Mishra *et al.*, 2019).

After getting the basic information, the next step was to test the proposed relationships. Firstly, the Pearson Correlation technique checked the possible causal association between identified variables. However, as mentioned by Kumari and Yadav (2018), correlation only reflects the possibility of an association between two variables. It does not confirm the cause-and-effect relationship by classifying variables into independent and dependent positions. It indicated the need to apply the multiple linear regression technique. So, multiple linear regression was run four times. The following table describes the purpose of running each model for testing the overall framework:

Multiple linear regression model 1

The first regression test was run to model the relationship between effective communication, cooperation and trust. Trust was a dependent variable in this model, and the other two were independent variables.

Multiple linear regression model 2 and 3

Second and third regression tests were run to model the relationship between trust, knowledge sharing and commitment with mutual dependency as a moderating variable in the relationship between trust and knowledge sharing. In regression model 2, the effect of trust on knowledge sharing was established, and the moderating power of mutual dependency was assessed through PROCESS by the Hayes moderation test. A third regression test was run to establish the effect of trust on the commitment.

Multiple linear regression model 4

A fourth regression test was run to measure the effect of knowledge sharing and commitment on relational governance effectiveness. Here, knowledge sharing and commitment were independent variables, and relational governance effectiveness was a dependent variable.

Linear regression model 5

The last regression test was run by quantifying the effect of relational governance effectiveness (independent variable) on the e-service outsourcing success (dependent variable)

The qualitative data was analysed by using a manual thematic analysis strategy. For this purpose, guidance was taken from Braune and Clarke's (2014) work. The following steps were followed to complete the thematic analysis process:

- First step- the interviews were recorded with the interviewees' consent
- Second step- recorded interviews were transcribed
- Third step- developed transcriptions were read multiple times to gain familiarity with the data set
- The fourth step- a list of codes was generated after gaining familiarity.
- The fifth step- identified code list was re-organised and re-arranged to visualise the patterns
- Sixth step- similar codes were grouped into categories and themes
- Seventh step- identified themes were produced in the data analysis section after putting appropriate labels.

Justification of using thematic analysis

Thematic analysis is a widely used coding procedure to analyse qualitative data in social research (Braun and Clarke, 2006). This research will also adopt this coding technique for several reasons, mainly due to the flexibility in dealing with subjective data, which needs categorising and grouping according to the same ideas. The thematic analysis is easy to use and helps the researcher to extract outcomes quicker.

The thematic analysis is helpful in this study as it helps to examine the different opinions and perspectives of the participants as this study is conducted on three public and three private organisations with participants from different levels (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

This study will have nine interviews with public organisations and six interviews with private organisations. Each interview consists of at least 17 questions, which means that the amount of data is vast and needs a flexible, clear, easy, and structured method to deal with such qualitative data.

After analysing the quantitative and qualitative data, the researcher identified and mapped the key variables into the e-service outsourcing framework to explain how e-service outsourcing can succeed through effective vendor-client relationship management in the selected organisational context. In order to do this, the researcher first conducted an in-depth analysis of the literature, survey and interview findings. The knowledge gained from the critical analysis was then used to refine the conceptual framework (initially developed based on a literature review and tested through

quantitative empirical research) that explained how public service firms in the UK can effectively manage the relationships with crucial outsourcing partners, which leads towards the outsourcing success.

3.9 Ethical considerations

The overall research design must address specific ethical issues to improve the research quality. Non-compliance with ethical research principles raises concerns over the proposed results' theoretical and practical value. Therefore, in compliance with critical ethical principles, the researcher ensured that no research participants were subjected to psychological or physical harm (Hair *et al.*, 2019). The consent remains fully informed, as the research purpose, aim and objectives were communicated to all survey and interview participants (Saunders and Lewis, 2012). Each survey/interview participant participated in the research with free will. Their identity was kept anonymized, and survey/interview data was kept confidential by storing it in a safe place. All identifiable information from the dataset that could reveal the participants' identity was removed. Quantitative results were summarised, and qualitative data was presented so participants' identities may not be revealed from their response patterns (Byrne and Humble, 2007).

According to the guidance of the University of the West of Scotland, the researcher submitted the ethical approval form to the ethical approval committee before starting data collection in order to make sure that the data collection process does not breach any ethical issue.

The ethical approval included a complete summary of the planned study's purpose, justification, design and methodology. The ethical approval also addressed other issues, such as:

- The questionnaires and interview questions are not sensitive, embarrassing or upsetting for participants in any way.
- The participants are all in good physical and mental situations and not of any vulnerable categories.

- The duration and timing of questionnaires and interviews are suitable for the participants who have previously been informed about it.
- the study will not cause any discomfort or distress, either physical or psychological, and the research does not involve any physically invasive procedures.
- The research does not involve deception regarding aims, objectives or the investigator's identity.
- The confidentiality of data and participants' privacy are not invaded or shared with any parties.
- That the researcher took all measures to ensure the security and safety of the collected data and participants' information.

3.10 Chapter summary

To summarize, this study's philosophical position can be placed between positivism and interpretivism. Both inductive and deductive research approaches are applied to generate the desired knowledge. The researcher used the mixed research method to collect quantitative data through an online survey and qualitative data through semi-structured interviews. The data was collected from three public service organizations in the UK. SPSS was used for quantitative data analysis, and qualitative data was analysed using a manual thematic analysis strategy. In the next chapter, the researcher presents and interprets both- survey and interview findings by applying appropriate analysis strategies.

Chapter Four- Data Presentation and Interpretation

4.1 Quantitative data analysis

4.1.1 Overview

A total of 100 participants completely and accurately filled the questionnaire. Out of 100, 60% respondents were males and 40 percent were females. The percentage of males to females represents the overall percentage of the males to females in these organisations so the taken samples were representative. Average age was around 35 years, and average experience length was around 6 years. Most of the participants are working in the contracts outsourcing departments or have experienced outsourcing relationship at some point as a part of their job. So, most of the respondents were middle aged male outsourcing managers with around six years' experience at their current organization. The pilot study results confirmed the questionnaire's internal consistency. Reliability test was run for this purpose. The output is shared below:

Variable names	Variable codes	Cronbach alpha value
Communication	Com	0.71
Cooperation	Cop	0.79
Trust	Trust	0.74
Mutual dependency	MD	0.86
Knowledge sharing	KS	0.81
Commitment	Comt.	0.83
Relational governance effectiveness	RGE	0.88
Outsourcing success	OS	0.91

Table 11- Reliability test results

The above output (shown in table 11) confirms that the questionnaire successfully achieves high internal consistency.

4.1.2 Descriptive analysis

The descriptive analysis was conducted to extract the basic information from the dataset. The researcher interprets mean values for this purpose. First, overall descriptive statistics for all variables are interpreted, and then the mean values of each construct of all variables are interpreted.

Overall mean values of computed variables

Variables	Mean values
Communication	3.1
Cooperation	3.0
Trust	3.0
Mutual Dependency	3.3
Knowledge Sharing	2.9
Commitment	2.9
Relational Governance Effectiveness	3.2
Outsourcing Success	3.1

Table 12- Overall mean values of computed variables

The analysis of mean values (table 12) shows that the perceptions towards asked variables remain mixed to slightly negative for some and only slightly positive for some. Communication could be improved as it earns a mixed to slightly positive score (3.1), perceptions towards perceived cooperative behaviour remain mixed (3), trust also needs to be improved among outsourcing partners as a mixed response is received (3); there exists mutual dependency among outsourcing partners (3.3), knowledge sharing among outsourcing partners do not happen frequently (2.9), outsourcing partners share weak commitment (2.9), relational governance effectiveness and outsourcing success also show mixed to only slightly positive response (3.2 and 3.1 respectively), which shows the participants' are somehow concerned towards relational governance quality, effectiveness and consequent outsourcing success.

For in-depth understanding, the mean values of all individual constructs are analysed:

Mean values of individual constructs

Communication	Mean
Open/transparent communication b/w vendor and client	3.1
formal and informal communication b/w outsourcing partners	3.2
The way the partner communicates with us supports open sharing of information	3
Mean	3.1

Table 13- Mean values- communication

Table 13 suggests that communication between outsourcing partners is open but could be improved further as response remains mixed; communication encourages open sharing and discussions only to some extent, though perceptions suggest that the outsourcing partners have well-balanced formal and informal communication in most organisations.

Co-operation	Mean
Client and vendor help/support each other	3.2
Outsourcing relationships managed through co-operative rather competitive strategies	2.8
Client and vendor frequently interact to evaluate how things can be handled	3.2
Positive inter-dependence between client and vendor	3
Mean	3

Table 14- Mean values- co-operation

Table 14 suggests that in most cases, client and vendors support each other (3.2), and both outsourcing partners frequently interact to assess how things could be handled (3.2); however, positive inter-dependence among outsourcing partners needs to be improved (3); and currently, outsourcing partners generally do not manage their outsourcing relationships through co-operative strategies (2.8).

Trust	Mean
Vendor is trustworthy	3.2
Vendor competent to offer what outsourcing contract requires	3.3
Vendor makes decision beneficial for client organization	3.1
Vendor always provides assistance	2.7
Client shares trust based friendly relationship with vendor	2.9

Client and vendor do not hesitate to transact when specifications are vague	2.9
Client and vendor do not use opportunities that arise at expense of each other	2.7
Outsourcing partners are even-handed during negotiations	3.2
Mean	3

Table 15- Mean values- Trust

Table 15 suggests that the perceptions towards trust remain mixed. Mostly, the vendor is considered trustworthy (3.2), and outsourcing partners are even-handed during negotiations (3.2); participants also have positive perceptions about the decisions that the vendor takes to benefit the client organization (3.1), and the vendor is also considered competent to offer what outsourcing contract requires (3.3). However, the vendor does not constantly assist (2.7), many clients do not share trust-based friendly relations with the vendor (2.9), both hesitate to transact often when specifications are vague (2.9) and mainly, both parties adopt opportunistic attitudes that hamper mutual trust (2.7).

Knowledge Sharing	Mean
Client and vendor frequently share business knowledge	3.1
The frequent information exchange helps in strategy planning and implementation	3
Outsourcing partners share know-how based on their extensive experience	3.1
Company learned about technology/processes held by the outsourcing partner	2.5
Organization reduced technological dependence on partner since contract beginning	2.7
Partners' technical know-how is assimilated and contributes to key business areas	3
Mean	2.9

Table 16- Mean values- Knowledge sharing

Table 16 suggests that perceptions towards knowledge sharing also remain mixed to slightly negative. Although clients and vendors share business knowledge and their technical knowhow, which is only sometimes assimilated to key business areas, and information exchange sometimes helps organizations in strategy planning and implementation, client organizations do not adequately learn about

technology/processes held by outsourcing partners, and client organizations cannot reduce technological dependence on partner since contract beginning.

Commitment	Mean
Outsourcing partners share strong commitment to fulfil the contractual terms	3.1
Each outsourcing partner is strongly committed to fulfil inter-connected goals	3
Commitment to fulfil each other's expectations reflect into business dealings and behaviour of outsourcing partners	2.8
Mean	2.9

Table 17- Mean values- Commitment

Table 17 suggests that perceptions towards commitment show that commitment is currently weak. Although the participants shared mixed to slightly positive perceptions towards sharing a commitment to fulfil contractual terms and exerting efforts to achieve interconnected goals, the response was slightly negative towards reflecting mutual commitment to achieve mutual goals in business dealings and behaviours.

Mutual Dependency	Mean
Client's performance depends on vendor performance	3.2
Vendor's performance depends on client organization	3.3
Mutual dependency between vendor and client high due to interconnected objectives	3.5
Mean	3.3

Table 18- Mean values- mutual dependence

Table 18 suggests that the mutual dependency between outsourcing partners remains high. As per the table, client performance depends on the vendor performance, and vendor performance also depends on the client's approval. Due to this mutual dependency, the objectives of client and vendor organizations are inter-connected.

RGE	Mean
Strong social capital created to strengthen relation between outsourcing partners	2.9
Promises, obligations and expectations enforced through social processes	3.4
Social processes promote solidarity and flexibility among outsourcing partners	3.1
Outsourcing partners share highly collaborative relationships	3.1
Short and long-term goals/plans are frequently shared between outsourcing partners	3.6
Overall outsourcing partners share a strong, effective business relation	3.1
Mean	3.2

Table 19- Mean values- RGE

Table 19 suggests that although overall perceptions towards relational governance effectiveness are mixed to slightly positive, in-depth analysis shows outsourcing partners could adequately create solid social capital to strengthen mutual relations. Perceptions towards other asked dimensions remain mixed to slightly positive.

Outsourcing success	Mean
Our organization fully satisfied with benefits availed by outsourcing e-services	2.9
Our organization fully achieved/expects to achieve desired benefits from outsourcing	2.8
Benefits of e-service outsourcing significantly outweigh associated challenges	3.1
E-service outsourcing has significantly enhanced the service quality	3.3
E-service outsourcing improved focus on other more important strategic matters	3.6
E-service outsourcing has enhanced our (client) organization's IT competencies	3.2
E-service outsourcing facilitates sharing of know-how from training, education and work experience, which develops organization's competencies and capabilities	2.8
Our organization considers e-service outsourcing experience to be overall successful	3.1
Mean	3.1

Table 20- Mean values- outsourcing success

Table 20 shows that the perceptions towards overall outsourcing success remain mixed to slightly positive with a broad scope for improvement. Individual-level analysis shows that organizations are not fully satisfied with e-service outsourcing benefits and expect only partially to achieve the desired benefits. E-service outsourcing also does not adequately facilitate sharing know-how from training, education and work experience, which develops an organization's competencies and capabilities. The perceptions towards other service outsourcing success dimensions remain mixed to positive.

Motivation for outsourcing	Mean
Cost reduction	3.9
Lack of resources	4.3
Service quality improvement	3.7
Learning from partner	3.4
Reduce administrative burden	4

Table 21- Motivations for e-service outsourcing

The above response (refer to Table 21) shows that lack of resources is the strongest motivation for e-service outsourcing, followed by reducing administrative burden, cost reduction, service quality improvement, and the motive to learn from partners. The findings are visualized in the following pie chart.

Overall response towards environmental tendencies:

Figure 7- Overall response towards environmental tendencies

After presenting key descriptive statistics, next the chapter presents and interprets inferential statistics.

4.1.3 Analysis of inferential statistics

4.1.3.1 Model 1- Effect of communication and commitment on trust

This section deals with the results of the above section of the conceptual framework.

4.1.3.1.1 Pearson Correlation

Pearson correlation test is run to assess the nature and strength of possible association between identified variables without confirming the cause and effect relationship.

Correlations

		Com	Cop	Trust
Com	Pearson Correlation	1	.909**	.881**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	100	100	100
Cop	Pearson Correlation	.909**	1	.917**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	100	100	100
Trust	Pearson Correlation	.881**	.917**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 22- Pearson Correlation (communication, cooperation and trust)

As per Table 22, both- communication ($r=.881$, $p<0.005$) and cooperative behaviour ($r=.917$, $p<0.005$) share a strong positive correlation with perceived trust, but correlation strength remains more robust in the case of cooperation than communication. It implies that communication and cooperation improvement can be positively associated with improved trust among outsourcing partners.

The correlation results only tell about the nature and strength of the association. Next, the effect of communication and cooperation on trust is assessed by running a regression test.

4.1.3.1.2 Multiple Linear Regression

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.924 ^a	.854	.851	.49498

a. Predictors: (Constant), Cop, Com

Table 23- Model summary (com, coop and trust)

As per Table 23, the overall correlation between identified predictors and the outcome variable is strongly positive ($R=.924$), and both predictors (communication and cooperation) predict the outcome variable (trust) with 85.1 per cent accuracy. At the same time, the rest of the variance is caused by unknown factors.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	139.224	2	69.612	284.124	.000 ^b
	Residual	23.766	97	.245		
	Total	162.990	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Trust

b. Predictors: (Constant), Cop, Com

Table 24- ANOVA (com, coop and trust)

As per Table 24, the ANOVA table shows that the overall relationship between independent and dependent variables could be modelled with corresponding values of $F(2, 97) = 284.124, p < 0.005$.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.125	.006		2.083	.031
	Com	.281	.094	.277	2.986	.004
	Cop	.667	.093	.665	7.167	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Trust

Table 25- Regression coefficient- com, coop and trust

The co-efficient table (table 25) shows that both independent variables individually predict trust with corresponding values of communication ($t=2.986$, $p=0.004$) and cooperation ($t=7.167$, $p<0.005$). The following regression equation could be developed:

$$\text{Perceived trust} = .125 + [\text{communication} (.281) + \text{co-operation} (.667)]$$

The equation shows that keeping a constant value of .125 under consideration, a 1 per cent change in communication brings a .281 per cent change in trust, and a 1 per cent change in cooperation brings a .667 per cent change in trust.

4.1.3.2 Model 2- Trust and knowledge sharing- mutual dependency as moderator

4.1.3.2.1 Pearson Correlation

Correlations

		Trust	KS	MD
Trust	Pearson Correlation	1	.886**	.742**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	100	100	100
KS	Pearson Correlation	.886**	1	.705**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	100	100	100
MD	Pearson Correlation	.742**	.705**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 26- Pearson Correlation- trust, knowledge sharing and MD

As per Table 26, both- trust ($r=.886$, $p<0.005$) and mutual dependency ($r=.705$, $p<0.005$) share a strong positive correlation with knowledge-sharing behaviour, implying that improvement in trust and increase in mutual dependency can be strongly positively associated with improved knowledge sharing among outsourcing partners.

4.1.3.2.2 Multiple Linear Regression with moderation test

Model Summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.8993	.8088	.2883	135.3347	3.0000	96.0000	.0000
Model						
	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	-.8521	.3937	-2.1641	.0329	-1.6336	-.0705
Trust	1.2281	.1674	7.3382	.0000	.8959	1.5603
MD	.4268	.1254	3.4028	.0010	.1778	.6757
Int_1	-.1253	.0416	-3.0084	.0034	-.2079	-.0426
Product terms key:						
Int_1 : Trust x MD						
Test(s) of highest order unconditional interaction(s):						
	R2-chng	F	df1	df2	p	
X*W	.0180	9.0502	1.0000	96.0000	.0034	

Table 27- Moderation test output

The results (table 27) confirm that the relationship between trust and knowledge sharing could be modelled. The proposed relationship successfully attains statistical significance in a way that the effect of trust on knowledge sharing is enhanced when the mutual dependency of client and vendor organization increases.

4.1.3.3 Model 3- Effect of trust on commitment

4.1.3.3.1 Pearson Correlation

Correlations

		Trust	Commitment
Trust	Pearson Correlation	1	.873**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.873**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 28- Pearson Correlation- trust and commitment

As per Table 28, trust shares a robust positive association with commitment (.873, $p < 0.005$), implying that improved trust among outsourcing partners could be strongly associated with the strengthened commitment between outsourcing partners.

4.1.3.3.2 Multiple Linear Regression

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.873 ^a	.763	.760	.64065

a. Predictors: (Constant), Trust

Table 29- Model summary- trust and commitment

As per table 29, trust predicts commitment with 76 percent accuracy, and rest variance is caused by unknown factors.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	129.138	1	129.138	314.642	.000 ^b
	Residual	40.222	98	.410		
	Total	169.360	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Trust

Table 30- ANOVA- trust and commitment

ANOVA table (table 30) shows the overall relationship between independent and dependent variables could be modeled with corresponding values of $F(1, 98) = 314.642, p < 0.005$.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.241	.164		1.467	.145
	Trust	.890	.050	.873	17.738	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Commitment

Table 31- Regression coefficient- trust and commitment

Based on co-efficient table (table 31), following regression equation could be developed:

$$\text{Perceived Commitment} = .241 + [\text{trust} (.890)]$$

The equation shows keeping constant value of .241 under consideration, 1 percent change in trust brings .890 percent change in commitment.

4.1.3.4 Model 4- Effect of commitment and knowledge sharing on relational governance effectiveness

4.1.3.4.1 Pearson Correlation

Correlations

		Comt	KS	RGE
Comt	Pearson Correlation	1	.848**	.806**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	100	100	100
KS	Pearson Correlation	.848**	1	.752**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	100	100	100
RGE	Pearson Correlation	.806**	.752**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 32- Pearson Correlation- Commitment, KS and RGE

As per Table 32, both- commitment ($r=.806$, $p<0.005$) and knowledge-sharing behaviour ($r=.752$, $p<0.005$) share a strong positive correlation with relational governance effectiveness. It implies that commitment and knowledge-sharing behaviour improvement can be positively associated with improved relational governance effectiveness in e-service outsourcing cases.

4.1.3.4.2 Multiple Linear Regression

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.816 ^a	.666	.659	.71384

a. Predictors: (Constant), Commitment, KS

Table 33- Model summary- Commitment, KS and RGE

As shown in Table 33, the overall correlation between identified predictors and the outcome variable is strongly positive ($R=.816$), and both predictors (commitment and knowledge sharing) predict the outcome variable (RGE) with 65.9 per cent accuracy. At the same time, the rest of the variance is caused by unknown factors.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	98.572	2	49.286	96.722	.000 ^b
	Residual	49.428	97	.510		
	Total	148.000	99			

a. Dependent Variable: RGE

b. Predictors: (Constant), Commitment, KS

Table 34- ANOVA- Commitment, KS and RGE

ANOVA table (table 34) shows the overall relationship between independent and dependent variables could be modeled with corresponding values of $F(2, 97) = 96.722, p < 0.005$.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.863	.186		4.633	.000
	KS	.245	.112	.242	2.186	.031
	Comt	.561	.104	.601	5.422	.000

a. Dependent Variable: RGE

Table 35- Regression co-efficient- commitment, KS and RGE

The co-efficient table (table 35) shows that both independent variables individually predict RGE with corresponding values of knowledge sharing ($t=2.186, p=0.031$) and commitment ($t=5.422, p<0.005$). The following regression equation could be developed:

$$\text{Perceived RGE} = .863 + [\text{KS} (.245) + \text{commitment} (.561)]$$

The equation shows keeping a constant value of .863 under consideration, a 1 per cent change in KS brings a .245 per cent change in RGE and a 1 per cent change in commitment brings a .561 per cent change in RGE.

4.1.3.5 Model 5- Effect of relational governance on outsourcing success- environmental tendencies as moderator

4.1. correlation

Correlations

	RGE	OS
RGE	Pearson Correlation	.712**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	100
OS	Pearson Correlation	.712**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 36- Pearson Correlation- RGE and OS

As per table 36, RGE shares strong positive correlation ($r=.712$, $p<0.0005$) with outsourcing success, implying improvement in RGE can be positively linked with outsourcing success.

4.1.3.5.2 Multiple Linear Regression

Model Summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.7288	.5312	.8366	36.2595	3.0000	96.0000	.0000
Model						
	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	.1678	.5700	.2944	.7691	-.9637	1.2993
RGE	.7982	.1682	4.7461	.0000	.4643	1.1320
ET	.1389	.1888	.7357	.4637	-.2359	.5137
Int_1	.0040	.0616	.0650	.9483	-.1182	.1262
Product terms key:						
Int_1	:	RGE	x	ET		
Test(s) of highest order unconditional interaction(s):						
R2-chng	F	df1	df2	p		
X*W	.0000	.0042	1.0000	96.0000	.9483	

Table 37- Moderation test

As per Table 37, motivations for e-service outsourcing do not moderate the effect of perceived relational governance effectiveness on e-service outsourcing success, but results confirm that the relationship between perceived relational governance effectiveness and e-service outsourcing success is statistically significant, and 1 per cent change in relational governance effectiveness brings .798 per cent corresponding change in the e-service outsourcing success.

4.1.4 Hypotheses summary

The overall inferential statistics results confirm that communication and cooperation significantly predict trust, and trust shares a positive and statistically significant relationship with knowledge sharing and commitment. The findings further suggest that relational governance effectiveness is predicted by commitment and knowledge sharing, and enhanced relational governance effectiveness determines e-service outsourcing success chances.

After presenting and interpreting the quantitative data, the next section of this chapter presents the interview findings collected by conducting interviews with client and vendor organizations.

4.2 Qualitative data analysis

After presenting survey findings, next section now presents the interview findings. The researcher conducted nine interviews with professionals currently working in three public service organizations in UK that outsourced their e-services to the private sector with different motives (like cost, quality and non-availability of required competencies).

The Three public organisations which were selected to do the interviews are United Kingdom Accreditation services UKAS, Birmingham city council, Southend city Council.

The United Kingdom Accreditation Service (UKAS) is the only National Accreditation Body in the UK. UK Government recognised UKAS in assessing against nationally and internationally set standards and give accreditation to the certifying bodies of these standards all over the world.

Birmingham City Council is a governmental body responsible for the management of municipal issues of the city. Birmingham considered the largest city in the west midlands and the second biggest city in the UK after London.

Southend or (Southend-on-Sea) City council is a governmental body responsible for the management of municipal issues of the city. Southend city is a district in Essex England.

Other than that, the study also conducted six interviews with outsourcing professionals from vendor organizations. By conducting interviews with management of both client and vendor organizations, the study was able to evaluate value of outsourcing and importance of trust in developing effective outsourcing relationships from both—vendor and clients' perspectives.

The client organisation participants were given the code letters from A to I as 9 participants were interviewed. For the vendor organisations, the codes V1 to V6 were given to the six participants.

Before presenting thematic analysis, the researcher presents the brief interviewee profile. All interviewees held middle management posts. The information about their age, gender and experience is given below:

Interviewees	Age	Gender	Experience
A	53	Male	15
B	35	Male	9
C	60	Male	22
D	46	Male	15
E	32	Female	8
F	29	Female	7
G	57	Male	18
H	38	Male	8
I	41	Female	13

Table 38- Interviewee profiles (client organizations)

Table 38 shows that the average age of interview participants was around 43 years old; most were males and had an experience of around 13 years. Next, the interviewee profile from vendor organizations is presented:

Interviewees	Age	Gender	Experience
V1	43	Male	15
V2	49	Male	21
V3	41	Female	13
V4	28	Male	5
V5	25	Male	3
V6	27	Male	4

Table 39- Interviewee profile (vendor organizations)

The profile of interviewees (table 39) from vendor organizations show that the average age of participants was 36 years and two out of three were males and one was female, with average experience of 10 years.

4.2.1 Interviews from client organizations

The application of thematic analysis technique guided the researcher to extract five key themes from interview findings, which are presented below:

4.2.1.1 Theme 1- Motivations for e-service outsourcing

Under this theme, the researcher evaluates the opinions towards why public service firms outsource e-services and the key motivations for making the e-service outsourcing decision. The researcher also explored opinions towards how motivations behind e-service outsourcing influence the relational governance dynamics. The purpose of this question was to explore whether and how motivations behind outsourcing influence relational governance effectiveness. The response is summarized in the following table:

Key e-service outsourcing motivations	Participants (codes)
Reduce the operational/labour cost, and motivation to convert the fixed costs to variable costs, which may produce more cost savings. Cost cutting encourages organizations to improve the process efficiencies by cutting off un-economical expenditures that not only increase costs, but also cause expensive process inefficiencies.	A,B,D,F,H,I
There are many functions that are challenging to manage in house. Managing e-services in house cause inefficiencies due to lack of specialized knowledge, competencies and capabilities. So, to avoid the complexities associated with managing e-services in house, the organizations outsource this function to the third party.	A,C,D,F,G,I

Technological development is rapid. This rapid change in technological environment makes technology quickly obsolete. Instead of continuously investing on the obsolete technologies, it is more suitable to outsource the e-services and avoid the technology obsolescence risk.	C,E,H,I
Risk sharing is another key motivation for making the outsourcing decision. Although, developing new relationships with outsourcing partners create new risks, but through effective management, such risks can be controlled, and the type of risks that could be shared through outsourcing are more serious and sometimes more difficult to manage.	A,C,D,E,I
Organizations make outsourcing decision to free the internal resources and capabilities that could be focused upon the core business operations. E-service outsourcing has enabled organizations to use existing resources for other internal services and tasks that add value for the customers and other relevant stakeholders.	B,C,D,E
Outsourcing decision is also taken to gain access to the advanced capabilities that organizations do not have, and due to which, they cannot effectively perform the functions. So, those functions are outsourced to the partners that have developed specialization in that particular area. Outsourcing decisions in such cases enables the organizations to gain access to the advanced and latest technological tools without incurring investment.	A,B,D,F,G,H,I
Outsourcing decision is also made to improve the focus on the core business processes, as it allows the organizations to outsource time consuming tasks that could otherwise negatively influence the effectiveness and efficiency of organization.	A,B,C, D,F,G,H

Table 40- Motivations for e-service outsourcing

During interviews, the study explored various motivations for outsourcing e-services in targeted organizations, mainly including- cost reduction, outsourcing functions that are difficult to manage, risk sharing, freeing internal resources, gaining access to advanced capabilities and improving focus on core business functions. This means there is only one motivation for making the e-service outsourcing decision in the UK. Multiple motivations show the high expectations that organizations have from their outsourcing decision. Therefore, it is vital to make the right outsourcing decision and then manage

it through effective relational governance. Literature highlights ‘trust’ as a critical factor in successful outsourcing relationships. In the next theme, the researcher presents the interview findings that discuss the role of trust in managing outsourcing relations within a chosen context (e-service outsourcing in the UK).

4.2.1.2 Theme 2- Defining relational governance

To start the discussion, the researcher requested interviewees to share their understanding of what relational governance means, and how it is understood in their organization. The response of each interviewee is summarized in following table:

Relational governance definitions	Interviewees
Relational governance involves informal coordinating mechanisms in which both parties meet each other’s expectations through continuous co-operation. Both parties engaging in positive behaviours and engage in facilitating actions that could lay strong foundation for trust	A
Relational governance comprises efforts that government agencies and their vendors exert to make their relationship successful. It shows their willingness to engage in the facilitating behaviours to foster mutually beneficial relationships	B
It is a governance mechanism used to manage relationship between outsourcing parties with an aim to reduce the opportunism	C
Relational governance denotes a range of relationship governance aspects that may include exercising informal control over each other, commitment, interpersonal trust, communication and mutual dependence	D
Relational governance comprises a set of procedures and rules that empower outsourcing parties to move forwards business relationship. The relational governance is built on communication and trust, when communication fails and trust remains absent, the overall relational governance fails	E
Relational governance activities denote the reciprocal exchange events that incur on basis of open communication, honesty and trust	F

Relational governance comprises relational norms and collaborative activities. The norms are based on trust, and collaborative activities comprise tactics that are jointly carried out to accomplish mutually set e-service outsourcing goals	G
Relational governance could be considered a function that adds value to a business relationship, which cannot be run without parties' trust and commitment with each other	H
Relational governance refers governing the business transactions through relational values and norms	I

Table 41- Relational governance definitions- practitioners' perspective

Now, when the above definitions are analysed, some aspects commonly mentioned by interviewees could be highlighted, including- cooperation, trust, informal controlling mechanisms, willingness to engage in facilitating behaviours, communication, reciprocal exchange, relational norms and collaborative activities. Based on common aspects, *relational governance* from practitioners' perspective could be defined as a set of procedures and rules that empower outsourcing parties to move forward in business relationships by engaging in reciprocal exchange events and collaborative activities that are jointly carried out to accomplish mutually set e-service outsourcing goals; and involve informal coordinating mechanisms in which both parties meet each other's expectations through continuous cooperation by engaging in facilitating behaviours that lay foundation for trust and commitment, and make relationship mutually beneficial, which adds value to the overall business relationship.

When this definition is dissected, the research finds out that practitioners consider relational governance a way to make the business relationship mutually beneficial by winning each other's trust with the ultimate aim of making the business relationship successful by engaging in collaborative activities that lay the foundation for a reciprocal exchange in which the trust is exchanged with the commitment to meet each other's expectations.

4.2.1.3 Theme 3- Role of trust in managing outsourcing relations

Under this theme, the researcher explores why trust is essential in managing outsourcing relations and how initial trust in outsourcing relationships could be developed. During interviews, the researcher also explored which management strategies help sustain the initially developed trust. Besides that, the researcher explored the role of effective communication in developing trust between outsourcing partners.

4.2.1.3.1. Initial trust management in outsourcing relationships

Almost all participants agreed that developing trust at the initial stages of relationship development is highly important as it lays the foundation for ongoing trust. The initial trust formulation requires an open interaction among outsourcing partners to clarify the contractual terms and conditions (A, C, G, H). With initial trust, executing the outsourcing contract (B) is possible. A strong predictor of initial trust is the positive feelings of outsourcing partners towards each other (C). So, the client organization needs to choose a partner with a good reputation and towards whom management already has positive feelings and perceptions. The positive feelings towards each other encourage the partners to interact more frequently (C, D). Telling the truth and respecting each other is vital for initial trust development (A, C, D, E, G, I). Participants also argued that it is essential to understand that the trust gradually gets robust, and trust-based relation between outsourcing parties is reciprocal (B, D, H, I). Overall, the initial trust development requires management to focus on various factors, including- initial reputation, open interaction, positive feelings towards each other, clear communication and clarity in the contractual terms and conditions that must be mutually agreed upon, openly discussed and accepted by all outsourcing partners.

4.2.1.3.2 Trust and communication

Once initial trust is developed, it is essential for outsourcing partners to focus on factors that are critical for ensuring gradual trust development for strengthening outsourcing relationships. A literature review highlighted communication as the most common factor for initial and ongoing trust development in outsourcing business relationships. During interviews, the researcher explored the communication strategies adopted in targeted organizations to manage trust-based outsourcing relationships.

Clear and effective communication for developing trust-based business relationships sets the tone to ensure that the outsourcing partner understands the message (A, C, F). Communication must be clear and frequent to develop mutual understanding (A, B, G, I). Frequent communication cannot develop trust until openness and honesty are integrated into communication strategies (G, I). Another critical factor for effective communication is clearly understanding and respecting organizational cultural differences (H and I). Each organization has its culture and communication preferences (formal or informal). It is essential to choose the communication mode and form that is mutually acceptable to both organizations (F, I). It is also essential for management to ensure that the communication is managed as one team, and outsourcing partners must be invited to regular team meetings (B, C, D and I). Everything must be documented to clarify communication and avoid misunderstanding (B, C and D).

Other than exploring the communication strategies, the researcher explored communication management challenges that targeted organizations face. The response to this is summarized in the following table:

Communication challenges	Respondents
Perceptual and cultural barriers- gap between culture of both organizations and different perceptions towards what 'effective' communication is for both parties	B,C,G,H and I
Lack of understanding of the contractual terms and conditions	A,B,D and G
Lack of initial trust/negative feelings towards partner at the initial level. Lack of initial trust weakens the foundation for robust trust development at latter stages	A,C,D,H and I
Different strategic priorities of both outsourcing partners	A,B,C,D, G and I
Structural barriers that arise from the structural rigidity of organizational structure	D, H and I
Increased co-ordination cost	D and F
Lack of feedback frequency that increases chances of misunderstanding	G and I
Lack of training in collaboration and communication	B, D, H and I
Lack of understanding about how informal and formal communication could be balanced	A, C, D, F, H and I

Challenge arising from communication complexity, control and co-ordination	B, E and F
Communication technological differences among vendor and client organizations. Other technological challenge mentioned by interviewees was unreliable network causing inefficiency and creating frustration among outsourcing partners.	A, C, H and I

Table 42- Communication challenges in e-service outsourcing relations

4.2.1.3.3 Co-operative attitude and trust-based relationships.

Besides communication, the researcher explored how a co-operative and flexible attitude plays its role in managing trust-based relations with outsourcing partners and how such flexibility is demonstrated in routine interactions. Almost all participants agreed that a collaborative and cooperative attitude is essential for developing trust-based relationships. This collaboration and cooperation are reflected in the contractual flexibility (A, G, H and I), which means the terms and conditions in the outsourcing contracts must be made flexible so that in case of any minor/unintentional violation, another outsourcing partner may show flexible attitude and prefer relation-building rather than charging other for violation (B, C, D and H). Co-operation and coordination among outsourcing partners could be encouraged by discouraging the opportunistic behaviour that weakens the trust and commitment to fulfil the mutually beneficial objectives (A, F, H and I).

4.2.1.3.4 Trust and knowledge sharing

The researcher explored the perceptions towards how trust between outsourcing partners influences the outsourcing partners' willingness to share knowledge. The researcher explored how knowledge sharing between outsourcing partners is managed at targeted organisations and the challenges they face while encouraging outsourcing partners to share knowledge. This sub-theme comprises three essential parts. The first part discusses the importance of knowledge sharing (as discussed by interviewees). The second part presents the interviewees' viewpoints about how knowledge sharing is encouraged. In the third part, challenges to knowledge sharing are discussed.

All participants strongly agreed that knowledge sharing is essential to successful outsourcing relationship management. Through open knowledge sharing, organisations make more well-informed decisions (A, B, H, I). Knowledge sharing enables the outsourcing partners to accomplish the technological, economic and strategic benefits of e-service outsourcing (C and D). When outsourcing partners openly share knowledge, it strengthens their mutual bond and commitment to meet each other's expectations (E). Open knowledge sharing also allows the client and vendor organisations to capture and keep the latest know-how of market dynamics, which is very important for making well-informed decisions (C, D and H).

A diversified response was received when participants were asked to mention how knowledge sharing is encouraged at their respective organisations. Per respondents, A and B, knowledge sharing among outsourcing partners are encouraged by emphasising the mutually beneficial objectives that both organisations can achieve by sharing knowledge. Participants D and F mentioned that management tries incentivising knowledge sharing among outsourcing partners. Knowledge sharing is also encouraged by fostering a mutually collaborative and positive mindset (B, F). In many cases, despite being willing to share knowledge, parties need more supportive tools and processes to share the knowledge. So, having the proper knowledge-sharing mechanisms in place is essential to encourage the two-way knowledge flow (C, H and I).

During interviews, respondents mentioned some challenges to knowledge sharing, which are summarised in the following table:

Knowledge sharing challenges	Participants
Lack of appropriate tools and technologies to support inter-organizational knowledge sharing	A, C, F, H and I
Lack of appropriate mechanisms to support knowledge sharing among vendor and client organizations	B, C, D and H
Outsourcing partnership contractual terms and conditions creating resistance to knowledge sharing	A, C, H and I
Lack of organizational capabilities and competencies to support knowledge sharing	A, B, D, G and H

Lack of policy support and a clear direction to guide the firms' knowledge sharing practices	C, E, F and I
Lack of coherence/no shared goals to incentivize the partners to share knowledge with each other	D, E and F

Table 43- Knowledge sharing challenges

While exploring the link between trust and knowledge sharing, the researcher also explored how mutual dependency may play its role in encouraging knowledge sharing among outsourcing partners. All participants agreed that mutual dependence encourages both- client and vendor organizations to share knowledge so that well-informed decisions can be taken, leading towards accomplishing mutually beneficial objectives.

4.2.1.4 Theme 4- Commitment and relational governance

During interviews, the researcher explored perceptions towards how commitment could be understood and formulated in outsourcing relations and how it influences the overall relational governance effectiveness that determines outsourcing success. Based on interviewees' perceptions, commitment in outsourcing relationships can be defined as the outsourcing partners' willingness to exert efforts on behalf of their relationship to fulfil each other's expectations (A, C, D, F, H and I). Mutual dependence increases the need to inculcate a strong sense of commitment (F, H and I) that may psychologically bind the parties to complete the contract. While discussing the importance of commitment for effective relational governance, participants B, C and D said that vendor organizations demonstrate their commitment to outsourcing relations by exerting full efforts to understand the client's expectations entirely. The vendor also demonstrates its commitment by driving accountability to relevant stakeholders (G and I).

Vendor and client organizations want to work closely with each other to increase outsourcing success chances. When commitment is strong, it motivates the outsourcing partners to avoid opportunistic behaviour and spend time understanding their partner's explicit and implicit expectations (A, C, F, H and I). At the employee level, both organizations communicate the level of support required from each other to make outsourcing decisions successful (B, D and C). The mutual commitment is demonstrated by reinforcing the mutual expectations of obligation that is part of the

psychological contract binding both partners to fulfil the outsourcing contract. Almost all partners considered open communication as the foundation for trust and commitment.

Overall, the commitment was considered vital for effective relational governance and strongly connected with the success of e-service outsourcing. Understanding the factors essential for strengthening commitment between outsourcing partners is vital to achieving the desired objectives of e-service outsourcing.

4.2.1.5 Theme 5- Overall challenges in managing outsourcing relations

The researcher also explored the perceptions towards key challenges that targeted organizations face in managing the relationship with outsourcing partners. The response to this theme is summarized in following table:

Challenges in managing outsourcing relations	Interviewees
Ineffective governance and conflict resolution mechanisms	A, C, D, F and H
Opportunistic behaviour due to lack of commitment between outsourcing parties	B, D and I
Cultural differences and structural rigidities hampering outsourcing partners from understanding and fully meeting each other's expectations	B, C, E, F and H
Lack of willingness to understand and <i>get along</i> with each other due to misunderstanding view and distrust	F, G, H and I
Lack of supportive tools and technologies to effectively manage relationship with outsourcing partner	B and I
Complex relationship nature, making it difficult to develop mutual understanding	C, E and F
Conflict of interest and lack of mutual dependence	C, F and H
Difficult control and co-ordination	A, B, E, H and I
Incompetent human resource	A, G and I

Table 44- Challenges in managing outsourcing relations

Table 40 shows that the client organizations face diverse challenges while managing relationships with the vendors. These challenges must be identified and

understood to understand how outsourcing success chances could be increased by improving relationship quality.

4.2.1.6 Theme 6- Suggestions to improve e-service outsourcing success

In last theme, the researcher asked participants to share suggestions about how relational governance could be improved to increase the e-service outsourcing success chances in UK. Most commonly proposed suggestions to improve e-service outsourcing success through effective relational governance are summarized in following table:

Suggestions to improve e-service outsourcing success	Interviewees
Improve communication, make communication more frequent, more interactive and open two-way feedback channels	A, B, D, F, G and H
Arrange trainings to equip human resource with skills and competencies required to ensure effective relationship management with vendor	A, G and I
Devise clear policies to provide necessary guidance about how relationship with vendor could be managed	A, B, D, F and E
Invest on communication and relationship management tools and technologies to make relational governance easier	A, B, C and I
Involve vendor organization into regular meetings to develop cohesion as a team responsible for making outsourcing successful	A, C, D and G
Devise clear and well-communicated conflict resolution mechanisms to ensure the problems are solved in timely manner	A, C and H
Minimize structural rigidity by clarifying how client organization can interact and involve vendor organization in decision making process to lay strong foundation for trust	B, F and I
Invest time and resources on finding the right outsourcing partner who is not only competent to handle the technical issues, but has similar structure and culture to avoid chances of conflict and misunderstanding	A, B and I

Devise clear strategies to attain right balance between control and co-ordination. Open communication, demonstration of commitment to fulfil each other's expectations, clarity in contractual terms and conditions and contractual flexibility are some ways to do this	A, B, E and H
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Table 45- Suggestions to improve e-service outsourcing success

4.2.2 Interviews from vendors

Besides conducting interviews with the client organizations, the researcher conducted six interviews with the vendor organizations. These interviews were with IT contract professionals from Accenture, RTECH and Cloud Central. The interview findings are presented below by applying the thematic analysis technique.

4.2.2.1 Theme 1- Communication, trust and commitment

Under this theme, the researcher explores the value of communication, trust and commitment from the vendor organizations' perspective. The theme is divided into sub-themes, as presented below:

4.2.2.1.1 Communication importance, strategies and challenges

They started with the communication importance of communication, strategies and challenges; all six interviewees considered communication as key to outsourcing success. As per V1 and V2, miscommunication is one of the most commonly highlighted causes of outsourcing failure. V2, V3 and V6 shared similar remarks by contending that although the importance of clear communication is well recognized, the contract complexity and environmental uncertainty sometimes make open communication a real challenge, mainly when the client organization shares no former relationships. Efforts must be exerted to lay the foundation for initial trust (V2 and V5). Other commonly discussed communication challenges were cultural differences (V2 and V6), physical distances (V1, V4 and V2), differences in strategic priorities (V2, V6), differences in management and communications style (V1, V2 and V5), and unclear communication strategy at both sides (V1 and V2).

When interviewees were asked to explain how effective communication plays a role in developing trust between outsourcing partners, all considered open communication as a basis for the initial and ongoing trust. The communication strategy must be a creative blend of formal and informal communication (V1 and V3), and it is better to develop a detailed communication plan to understand all possible communication modes, methods, channels and techniques that need to be adopted in specific situations (V1 and V2). The communication strategy must also ensure strong alignment with the overall business strategy and outsourcing objectives to bring clarity (V2 and V3).

4.2.2.1.2 Co-operation and co-ordination

Interviewees were also asked whether their organization adopts a cooperative and flexible attitude to manage trust-based relationships with outsourcing partners, and if so, how such cooperation and flexibility are demonstrated. The response analysis suggests that encouraging cooperation and coordination is not accessible in all situations, mainly when the client organization exercises strict control, avoids frequent interactions, and does not involve vendors in essential decisions (V2 and V3). However, there are ways to encourage cooperation in the allowed capacity. Like, the vendor can win the trust of the client organization by showing its commitment to fulfilling all contractual obligations and exerting additional efforts to develop an environment of trust conducive to cooperation and coordination (V1, V2 and V3). While discussing the importance of coordination, V3 commented that contractual flexibility is vital to managing the uncertainty in outsourcing relationships. Such flexibility encourages both partners to accommodate changes in uncertain situations and cooperate rather than punishing unintentional deviation (V3 and V5).

4.2.2.1.3 Trust and knowledge sharing

The researcher explored interviewees' opinions towards the role of trust in encouraging outsourcing partners to share knowledge. All three participants mentioned that trust is essential to share valuable knowledge with outsourcing partners (V1, V2, V3, V4, V5 and V6), as when trust and commitment are absent, it encourages opportunistic behaviour, and the organization tries to avoid sharing valuable knowledge for personal gains, which ultimately harms the collective gain (V1, V3 and V3). V2 and V5 further mentioned that trust is not essential for sharing vital knowledge to fulfil the essential

contractual terms and conditions. However, it does play a critical role in cases where knowledge sharing is discretionary and can benefit the client organization without having any clear and direct incentive for the vendor (V2.V6).

4.2.2.2 Theme 2- Challenges in managing outsourcing relationships

Under this theme, the researcher explores the interviewees' perceptions of the most critical challenges targeted vendor organizations face in managing relationships with client organizations. The researcher has concisely summarized the most commonly highlighted challenges in the following table:

Challenges in managing outsourcing relationships	Interviewees
Technological incompatibility	V1, V3 and V5
Management related challenges due to unclear communication and co-ordination policies	V2,V6
Lack of competent employees who could develop effective, trust based relations with the client organization in uncertain and challenging situations, and on ongoing basis	V2, V3
Challenges related to IT transition among vendor and client organization	V1,V4 and V5
Lack of willingness and non-co-operative attitude of client organization	V2,V5 and V6
Challenges related to security and compliance	V2, V3 and V4
High control and co-ordination costs	V1 and V3
Challenges related to compliance and security due to outsourcing contract risky nature	V1, V2,V3,V4,V5 and V6
Cultural and structural resistance	V1, V2,V3,V4,V5 and V6
Lack of clear policies about how communication and relationship with client organization could be managed	V1.V3 and V5

Table 46- Challenges in managing outsourcing relationships

4.2.2.3 Theme 3- Suggestions for improving relational governance to increase e-service outsourcing success

Lastly, the researcher asked interviewees from vendor organizations to share some suggestions about how relational governance could be improved to increase e-service outsourcing success chances. The response is summarized in the following table:

Suggestions for improving relational governance to increase e-service outsourcing success	Interviewees
Request client organization to share open and honest feedback, keep communication open and two way, devise strategies to immediately contact client in case of any misunderstanding, keep communication clear	V1,V2 and V4
Devise clear communication and co-ordination policies, ensure regular and open communication, choose communication modes that are convenient for both- vendor and client organization	V2,V3,V4 and V5
Develop flexible contractual terms and conditions, and adjust priorities in a way that personal gain may not lead towards compromising collective gain	V2,V6
Develop and communicate a comprehensive action plan to outline how communication with client organization could be managed in routine and in difficult times, how conflicts could be resolved (through which channels), how the collective interest is prioritized at expense of personal gain and how technological incompatibility challenges could be possibly addressed	V1, V2,V3,V4,V5 and V6
Eradicate the ambiguity as much as possible through communication clarity, frequency, openness and quality. Feedback, regular interactions, demonstration of honesty and commitment in routine interactions are some ways to minimize ambiguity	V1,V2,V4 and V6
To improve relationship quality, it is important to clearly communicate the expectations and communicate the realistic capacity so that unrealistic expectations from each other could be avoided at early stage	V2.V5

Management may incentivize and encourage the value boosting behaviours that are important for improving relationship quality	V1,V3 and V6
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Table 47- Suggestions for improving relational governance to increase e-service outsourcing success.

4.3 Chapter summary

The overall results (both survey and interview) confirm that the success of e-service outsourcing depends on effective relational governance, which can be enhanced by focusing on management-related factors, including communication, cooperation, trust, knowledge sharing and commitment. The survey and interview findings further confirm that public organizations in the UK currently face various challenges while managing their outsourcing relationships. It is essential to carefully manage outsourcing relations to reduce the outsourcing failure rate in the UK public sector.

After presenting the survey and interview findings, the next chapter now conducts an in-depth discussion by comparing and discussing the survey and interview findings in light of the literature.

Chapter Five- Discussion

This research study was conducted to provide knowledge about the people (perceptions, commitment, cooperative behaviour) and management (trust and communication management mechanisms) related factors that influence the quality of relationships with the outsourcing partners. To do this, the researcher conducted an empirical investigation into public service firms in the UK. The key objective of this mixed-method empirical investigation was to explore the nature of relational governance in an e-service outsourcing context. The secondary interest areas of this research work were to analyse the factors that determine relationship strength with partners involved in e-service outsourcing, evaluate the relationship between relational governance and e-service outsourcing success, and explore the environmental tendencies (e.g. specific economic, socio-economic or political motives that motivated the firm to make outsourcing decision) that motivate public service firms to outsource e-services. This chapter, 'Discussion,' provides an in-depth analysis of survey and interview results in light of the literature. The researcher analyses how proposed primary research results support or contrast the previously proposed findings. The chapter lays the foundation for arriving at a meaningful conclusion presented in the next chapter.

5.1 E-services and outsourcing

Today, governments are heavily investing in information and communication technologies to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of governance processes and systems. The investments are mainly in web-based technologies to encourage cost-effective and operationally efficient government.

Web-based technologies are also making the delivery of government services more convenient for businesses and citizens (Hoque *et al.*, 2019; Kesan *et al.*, 2019). During the interviews, the participants shared similar opinions and considered the technological advancement in the ICT field an opportunity to deliver services more efficiently and cost-effectively.

In e-governance, e-services denote the processes and solutions that enable service delivery through electronic channels. By conducting surveys and interviews with middle managers of client and vendor organizations, the current study found that e-services are on the rise in the UK. However, most participants shared that their organization preferred outsourcing e-services to reliable vendors. Managing a whole e-

services portfolio in-house was challenging due to limited organizational competencies, capabilities and capacity. Interviewees mentioned that government organizations need more capabilities and competencies to efficiently deliver services through electronic channels. Skilled labour shortage, rising fixed costs, inefficiencies due to lack of specialized knowledge, competencies and capabilities, quickly changing technological environment making technologies obsolete, and inability to handle the e-service delivery complexity are some strong motivators for making outsourcing decisions. While discussing why public sector organizations make outsourcing decisions, Lahiri and Kedia (2011) commented that although technical innovation is critical for firm success, more than merely focusing on technical innovation without developing the required competencies and capabilities is required.

E-services involve technical changes and demonstrate the government's commitment to improve broader social and political environments. Other than social and economic motives, various political motives are also attached to the government's decision to offer e-services (mentioned by some interviewees and Mahalik, 2010). These diverse motives for implementing e-services encourage public organizations to implement e-services after carefully evaluating their capacity and capabilities, as poor e-service implementation could harm the governments' image and hinder their ability to achieve the desired social, economic and political objectives. It provides another reason why public sector organizations outsource services, particularly when they have limited capabilities. Considering the widespread use of information and communication technologies among government organizations, it has become interesting to explore how e-services could be delivered successfully to achieve the broader e-governance objectives.

In agreement with the literature, the current study found that investment in digital technologies is also becoming inevitable for government agencies in the UK. E-governance is permitting new ways to interact with the citizens. Due to the widespread recognition of e-service importance, governments worldwide, including the UK, are investing heavily in large e-service projects (Hiles and Hon, 2016). However, such projects' failure rate remains predominantly high (Sasse, 2019). In some cases, such projects never reach the implementation phase; some fail immediately after implementation, and some fail after some time. As such projects involve extensive resources, it is essential to reduce the failure chances (Sasse, 2019). The interviewees

also acknowledged that e-services implementation involves complex challenges, due to which public organizations get compelled to take services of some third party.

Up till now, the researcher discussed e-service trends in the public sector. In light of the literature and primary research results, the study confirms that e-service implementation is an exciting study area due to governments' growing interest in e-governance worldwide. E-service outsourcing success is strongly connected with relational governance effectiveness. Failure to ensure effective relational governance could significantly reduce the e-service outsourcing success chances. Before evaluating the factors that determine relational governance effectiveness, the researcher first conceptualizes the relational governance concept by exploring and comparing the scholar's and practitioners' perspectives.

5.2 Objective 1: Conceptualizing relational governance in e-service outsourcing context

The first research objective of this mixed method empirical research was to explore how scholars and practitioners conceptualise e-service outsourcing relational governance and how conceptualisations of both sides may or may not differ and support each other. The comparison of literature and interview findings indicates that scholars, practitioners, and practitioners' conceptualisation of e-service outsourcing relational governance supports each other. An overview of how practitioners defined relational governance in the e-service outsourcing context highlights some commonly highlighted aspects, including- relational norms and values based on trust, open communication and commitment. The practitioners' view of relational governance involves informal coordinating mechanisms in which both parties meet each other's expectations through continuous cooperation and facilitate behaviour and actions that could lay a strong foundation for trust. These efforts are exerted to make relationships successful by discouraging opportunism. Through relational governance, the e-service outsourcing parties exercise informal control over each other. Interviewees also mentioned that relational governance activities involve reciprocal exchange events to add value to a business relationship.

Now, when practitioners' perspective is compared with scholars, the analysis indicates that although scholars have defined relational governance using comparatively more

complex terms, the essence remains the same. For instance, Zaheer and Venkatraman (1995) defined *relational governance* as the exchange involving relationship-specific assets based on inter-organisational trust embodied in the processes and structure of inter-organisational relationships. The key relational governance aspects highlighted in this definition are- an exchange-based relationship built on trust. All interviewees commonly discuss both these aspects. The additional aspect that Zaheer and Venkatraman (1995) covered was that exchange and trust are deeply embedded in relationship structure. Another seminal definition of relational governance was proposed by Baker *et al.* (1995), who contended that relational governance denotes the governance of business transactions through relational norms and values that refer to social regulations and complex processes. The complexity of relational governance mechanisms was discussed in the literature. However, it was not directly mentioned by the participants during interviews. However, in later questions about how relational governance is managed, they pointed out how complex it is to build and maintain trust in an increasingly complex and challenging business environment. A common point between practitioners' and scholars' perspectives is that both considered relational governance a value-added function that increases the chances of accomplishing the mutually beneficial objectives in a business relationship.

5.3 Objective 2: Motivations for e-services outsourcing- analysis of primary data in light of literature

The second research objective was to explore the environmental tendencies that motivate public service organisations to outsource e-services. The drive to successfully launch e-service projects despite inadequate competencies and capabilities is becoming a strong outsourcing driver in e-governance. During the last decade, outsourcing e-services has become common in developing and developed world regions. Government agencies are outsourcing their e-services projects to increase their success chances (Žitkienė and Dudė, 2018; Lahiri and Kedia, 2011). The current study also confirmed that e-services in the UK are also being outsourced to vendors for the same reasons. Outsourcing is being considered a way to reduce the burden and improve efficiency without investing in capacity and capability building. However, the unfortunate fact is

that most of the outsourcing projects fail to meet the parties' expectations (Mahalik, 2010).

This also holds in the current case because, during interviews, the participants discussed how e-service outsourcing projects meet failure due to organisations' inability to develop effective relationships with their outsourcing partners. The interviewees mentioned various reasons which led the outsourcing project to fail, including lack of cooperation, hesitation to share valuable knowledge with each other, engaging in opportunistic behaviour, and, most importantly, not trusting each other. All these factors reduce the e-service outsourcing success chances. The current study was executed to evaluate the factors that determine e-service outsourcing success. However, before analysing the e-service success determinants, the researcher analyses what, in the first place, motivates the public sector organisations to outsource their e-services.

The comparison of literature and interview findings suggests that there are many reasons or a limited set of reasons for outsourcing e-services. The outsourcing decision is made by considering multiple factors. The underlying context also exerts a strong influence on outsourcing decisions. Scholars consider outsourcing decisions complex as they involve multifaceted technical and non-technical contextual factors. The literature cites some common outsourcing motivations including- political and regulatory factors (Chen and Perry, 2003; Mahalik, 2010), the situation of the marketplace, easy availability of vendor with suitable skills and competencies, highly mature IT outsourcing marketplace, prevailing regulatory environment (Lahiri and Kedia, 2011; Cordella and Willcocks, 2012), low outsourcing risk (Joha and Janssen, 2010), complexity and compatibility of the IT services that need to be outsourced (Lahiri and Kedia, 2011; Žitkienė and Dudė, 2018), skills shortage in the labour market (Iqbal and Dad, 2013; Lahiri and Kedia, 2011), cost reduction (Moon *et al.* 2016), advancement in information and communication technologies (Jun and Weare, 2011) and growing competition for market share (Jun and Weare, 2011; Chen and Perry, 2003).

When primary research findings are referred to, the researcher finds out that the lack of resources is the strongest motivation, followed by reducing administrative burden, cost reduction, service quality improvement and the motive to learn from partners by outsourcing e-services. The interview findings further suggested that public

sector organisations in the UK tend to outsource e-services because managing e-services in-house causes inefficiencies due to lack of specialised knowledge, competencies and capabilities. Outsourcing decision is also made because public service organisations in the UK consider it a way to access advanced capabilities through their outsourcing partner. The firms consider it an opportunity to develop a specialisation in that particular area. Another most commonly cited motivation for outsourcing was to free up resources and improve the focus on the core business processes. The interviewees also mentioned risk sharing, cost reduction and quick technological advancement as crucial factors that were considered while outsourcing.

The comparison of literature and primary research findings points towards the fact that public organisations make outsourcing decisions by considering multiple factors. The multiple factors also show the multiple expectations that firms have from making the outsourcing decision. They expect that by outsourcing e-services, they will be able to save costs, improve efficiency, build specialised capabilities by learning from their partner, handle the competition and divert the focus on core business operations simultaneously. Unfortunately, these expectations are not fully met in most cases due to firms' inability to develop a strong relationship with the vendor. Here, trust plays a critical role and can lead the outsourcing contract towards success or failure.

In order to understand the outsourcing motivations, the literature proposes the transaction cost theory, which explains how outsourcing decisions are made by considering the transaction costs. The theory emphasises the need to adopt strategies to reduce transaction costs and maximise its benefits. The primary research findings here validate Williamson's transaction cost theory, where the participants discussed how outsourcing transaction is managed by adopting well-thought strategies (aligning communication strategy according to stakeholders' needs, strategic thinking and negotiation handling). Such transactions are deemed critical and highly influence firm success; therefore, their characteristics (like complexity, specificity and uncertainty) require careful handling. The transaction cost theory was proposed almost four decades ago. Till today, various studies (like Lacity *et al.* 2011) consider TCE theory valid for assessing the governance mechanisms of various transactions. Agreeing with the literature, the current study also acknowledges that this theory can be referred to understand which core competencies a firm can keep in-house and which could be outsourced for better results. The interviewees further agreed that when e-services are

outsourced, such transactions involve opportunistic costs. Opportunism and bounded rationality are two fundamental assumptions deeply inherited into such transactions, with important cost implications that must be considered to make the right decision.

Although the focus of this research was on exploring the relational rather than technical and formal governance mechanisms in e-service outsourcing, the methodological flexibility enabled the researcher to conduct an in-depth investigation, resulting in themes that provide empirical support to the transaction cost theory. For instance, in agreement with the scholars that support transaction cost theory, the current study further confirmed that e-service outsourcing decisions are made by considering whether e-service delivery is complex and whether the organisation must dedicate specific assets to manage the e-service delivery. The interviewees further agreed that the outsourcing decisions are complex and require management to take a holistic view while deciding whether to manage the activities in-house or outsource to a third party. Agreeing with Williamson, the study found that such transactions involve technical challenges and behavioural and environmental aspects, which must be carefully handled to make the transaction successful. The literature suggests that high transaction complexity also drives transaction costs (Lacity *et al.*, 2011).

After understanding what motivates public firms in the UK to outsource their e-services, the following section compares the literature and primary research findings to understand the factors that determine relational governance effectiveness in the e-service outsourcing context.

5.4 Objective 3: moderating effect of environmental tendencies on relational governance and outsourcing success.

The conceptual framework suggests that environmental tendencies play a moderating role between relational governance and outsourcing success. According to the literature review

Environmental tendencies towards outsourcing e-services are significant when deciding to outsource or not in public organisations and motivate them to give this mission to the private sector. (Lahiri and Kedia, 2011). However, the quantitative results showed

that the environmental tendencies do not moderate the relationship between relational governance and outsourcing success despite their significant relationship.

The above can be attributed, according to the literature review, that there are several reasons for establishing the outsourcing relation; these reasons could be political, social, or economic reasons (Khan and Khan, 2017). these reasons could affect the outsourcing decision, but they do not control the strength and direction of this relationship.

In the current case, the interviewees agreed that e-service delivery is complex and, therefore, outsourcing is costly. The literature further suggests that when highly complex transactions are not effectively governed, it drives up costs and reduces the success chances of transaction success (Nehemia *et al.*, 2019; de Carvalho *et al.*, 2018). Here, the study can build a connection by commenting that the high e-service outsourcing failure rate in the UK could be associated with the firms' inability to handle the transaction complexity. To ensure a successful outcome, it is essential to take a holistic view and extend the focus from technical to non-technical relational aspects of transactions.

For instance, the literature suggests that outsourcing transactions involve various activities, including vendor selection, contract negotiation, contract management and communication management to establish strong vendor relationships (Nehemia *et al.*, 2019; de Carvalho *et al.*, 2018). These activities, when effectively managed, increase the outsourcing success chances. As the current study specifically focused on the non-technical/relational aspects of managing e-service outsourcing contracts, the analysis of survey and interview data highlights some strategies that participants mentioned to increase the success chances, including- sharing open and honest feedback, devising clear communication and co-ordination policies, developing and communicating a comprehensive action plan and communicating the expectations to avoid misunderstandings. These strategies, when effectively implemented, increase the relational governance effectiveness, which then increases the e-service outsourcing success chances.

5.5 Objective 4: predictive power of the antecedents and outcomes (factors) of trust on relational governance effectiveness.

5.5.1 Trust, commitment and relational governance- analysis of primary research results in light of literature

As discussed, the primary research results validate the trust and commitment theory, as both- survey and interview findings consider trust a strong predictor of commitment that both parties show to fulfil their contractual obligations. The mean value analysis has indicated that the trust between client and vendor organisations involved in e-service outsourcing in the UK remains low. The inferential statistics confirm trust as a significant predictor of commitment, which means low trust could result in a weak commitment to fulfil each other's expectations. The descriptive statistics also confirm that the commitment between outsourcing parties is weak. The detailed analysis suggests that although outsourcing partners show some commitment to fulfilling contractual terms, their goals need to be more strongly interconnected. Moreover, they also need more willingness to fulfil each other's expectations, and this commitment must be strongly reflected in outsourcing partners' business dealings and behaviour.

It is essential to strengthen mutual commitment because it strongly influences relational governance effectiveness. When outsourcing partners are committed to each other, it develops a strong relationship basis, increasing the outsourcing success chances (Gottschalk and Solli-Sæther, 2005; Schoenherr *et al.*, 2015). The interview findings suggest that solid commitment increases the outsourcing partners' willingness to exert efforts on behalf of their relationship to fulfil each other's expectations. Here, although quantitative survey findings considered mutual dependence an insignificant moderator, interview results suggested that when outsourcing parties depend on each other, it increases the need to inculcate a strong sense of commitment that may psychologically bind the parties to complete the contract. When this finding is analysed in light of social exchange theory, the analysis suggests that mutual dependence increases the 'need' to strengthen commitment, as parties can harm their mutually aligned interests if they share weak commitment (Schoenherr *et al.*, 2015; John *et al.*,

2017). The importance of aligning the parties' interests is also widely recognised in the outsourcing relational governance literature (Leininger, 1997; Lee and Kim, 2005).

Interestingly, the interview findings showed that participants knew the importance of sharing strong commitment and considered it vital for outsourcing success. Other than having awareness, the participants also demonstrated a willingness to work closely with each other and avoid indulging in opportunistic behaviour. However, despite being aware and willing, parties still need to show more vital willingness due to non-supportive mechanisms. The commitment remains to be clarified, which inhibits them from clearly understanding each other's expectations. The conflict of interest also makes the development of mutual understanding more challenging.

The comparison of primary and literature findings suggests that both- trust and commitment are nurtured over time. Strong outsourcing relationships develop when trust is developed through formal bargaining and informal sense-making. When initial trust is developed, the governance structure of the mutual relationship gets codified into the relational contract, which is informally understood within a 'psychological contract'. Here, both parties use their interpretations and perceptions to view how other partners would act in the future. When these perceptions are understood by each other, it strengthens their commitment and lays the foundation for the contract's success.

5.5.2 Trust, knowledge sharing and relational governance- analysis of primary research results in light of literature

When response towards the perceived willingness to share knowledge is analysed, the findings suggest that when both parties win each other's trust, it encourages them to share knowledge about business processes and procedures openly. The frequent exchange of information helps vendor and client organisations plan and implement business strategies. Moreover, it is also essential that both- client and vendor organisations share know-how based on their extensive experience. When outsourcing partners do not hesitate to share valuable knowledge, it enables both companies to learn from each other (Cheng *et al.*, 2008). Particularly in the e-service outsourcing context, the knowledge-sharing behaviour makes it possible for client organisations to learn about the technology/processes held by the outsourcing partner. Literature suggests that through knowledge sharing, client organisations tend to reduce their initial

technological dependence on their partners. The client organisation assimilates the technical know-how held by the outsourcing partner and has contributed to other business areas of the client organisation (Attar *et al.*, 2019).

Now, when survey respondents' response towards 'knowledge sharing' is analysed, the study finds out that the knowledge-sharing intentions of outsourcing parties remain low (as per survey results) despite recognising the importance of sharing valuable knowledge (as per interview findings). During interviews, the participants agreed that as outsourcing contracts are implemented in a highly dynamic environment, it is essential to share knowledge to make more well-informed decisions. The outsourcing partners mutually achieve their strategic/economic/technological objectives through knowledge sharing. It strengthens their mutual bond and equips outsourcing partners with the latest know-how of market dynamics (also mentioned by Marchewka and Oruganti, 2013).

However, outsourcing partners still need help to share knowledge due to various challenges. For instance, the mean values suggest that although client and vendor organisations share business knowledge and technical know-how, the shared knowledge still needs to be fully assimilated to key business areas, due to which shared information helps organisations in strategy planning and implementation only to a limited extent. Client organisations need to adequately learn about technology/processes held by outsourcing partners so they cannot reduce technological dependence, cited as an essential motivation for outsourcing e-services. Due to poor knowledge sharing, many firms cannot achieve the desired objective of 'reducing technological dependence', which is one of the key motivators for outsourcing decisions (Ali *et al.*, 2018; Park *et al.*, 2011).

As the survey was quantitative, the researcher needed help investigating the knowledge-sharing challenges that outsourcing partners face. For this purpose, interview findings could be referred to. As per interview data, although outsourcing partners remain willing to share knowledge, a lack of supportive tools and processes inhibits them from timely sharing the knowledge. Lack of appropriate tools and technologies to support inter-organisational knowledge sharing, lack of appropriate mechanisms, outsourcing partnership contractual terms and conditions creating resistance, lack of organisational capabilities and competencies, lack of policy support and a clear direction to guide the

firms' knowledge sharing practices and lack of coherence/no shared goals to incentivise the knowledge sharing are some commonly highlighted challenges that discourage partners from sharing knowledge. Similar challenges have been highlighted by some previous studies (like Khan and Khan, 2017; Lahiri and Kedia, 2011; He and Lu, 2017; Chen and Perry, 2003) as well, which shows that firms involved in outsourcing tend to face similar challenges due to internal and external environmental complexity.

Here, primary data could be referred to understand how knowledge sharing could be encouraged among outsourcing partners. For instance, interview participants shared that knowledge sharing could be encouraged by emphasising the mutually beneficial objectives, incentivising the knowledge sharing among outsourcing partners, fostering the mutually collaborative and positive mindset and having the proper knowledge-sharing mechanisms to encourage the two-way knowledge flow.

The literature suggests that the mutual dependence of outsourcing parties encourages them to share knowledge (Marchewka and Oruganti, 2013; Lee and Kim, 2005; Lee *et al.*, 2008). However, the survey findings did not confirm the moderating influence of mutual dependence. The interview findings here share different opinions and support the literature by suggesting that when client and vendor organisations depend on each other, it encourages them to share knowledge. A possible reason for the inconsistency between the survey and interview findings is that the survey carried close-ended questions, and the sample size was small. A bigger sample size could confirm whether mutual dependence significantly encourages the parties to share knowledge. Further empirical investigation is needed here to get a more precise understanding.

5.5.3 Cooperation and trust- analysis of primary research results in light of literature

Besides communication, cooperative behaviour is critical in building trust-based relationships with vendors. To succeed, client and vendor organisations should be willing to help and support each other. Outsourcing relationships are successful when managed by adopting cooperative rather than competitive strategies because the inability to show such cooperation increases the chances of engaging in opportunistic behaviour. Cooperative behaviour encourages client and vendor organisations to frequently interact with each other to evaluate how things can be better handled (Susarla *et al.*, 2020; Schoenherr *et al.*, 2015; Tan and Sia, 2006; Mayer and Argyres, 2004).

Agreeing with the literature, the empirical findings also confirmed that interdependence between vendor and client organisations must be positive to develop trust-based relationships (Susarla et al., 2020; Schoenherr et al., 2015). However, analysis of descriptive statistics suggests that although targeted client organisations help their vendors to some extent, a majority of the participants considered their relationship managed through competitive rather than cooperative strategies, which, to some extent, explains the reason for the high outsourcing failure rate in the UK and rest of the world. The response was also mixed to only slightly positive towards the statement that client and vendor organisations frequently interact to evaluate how things can be handled and that positive interdependence exists between them. The overall results show that the cooperation between vendor and client organisations needs to be higher.

When inferential statistics are referred to, the statistics confirm a strong effect of cooperation on trust, which means that low-cooperative behaviour could significantly reduce mutual trust. The response towards the 'perceived trust' could be analysed to confirm this. Here, the descriptive statistics analysis shows that the trust between vendor and client organisation is developed when the client organisation considers the vendor trustworthy and competent enough to fulfil the contractual obligations. When trust is formed, vendors make mutually beneficial decisions. Mutual trust also encourages vendors to assist clients and meet their expectations. This trust-based friendly relationship makes transactions easier when even the specifications are vague. Trust-based relation is critical for discouraging partners from engaging in opportunistic behaviour. Moreover, during negotiations, each party must consider each other's interests (Babin et al., 2017).

Despite the importance of trust, the overall mean value remains low, showing significant scope for building and improving trust. The descriptive statistics suggest that perceptions are weakly positive towards considering the vendor trustworthy and that negotiations are evenly handed. However, the opinions were divided about believing that the vendor can assist; many client organisations do not share trust-based friendly relations with the vendor as vendor and client organisations hesitate to transact often when specifications are vague, and mainly, both parties adopt opportunistic attitudes that hamper mutual trust. The interview findings also revealed that weak trust increases the parties' engagement in opportunistic behaviour, ultimately reducing the

outsourcing success chances. When descriptive and inferential statistics are analysed together, it becomes apparent that the lack of cooperative behaviour is among the significant reasons for weak trust between vendor and client organisations.

Overall, both- literature and primary research findings confirmed that cooperative behaviour is a key trust antecedent. However, in the current context, the outsourcing parties hesitate to adopt cooperative behaviour, which could be a possible reason for the lack of trust and high outsourcing failure in the UK.

5.5.4 Communication and trust- analysis of primary research results in light of literature

Referring to the conceptual framework, the first part hypothesised that the effect of communication and cooperative behaviour affect trust. Strong literature support is available to confirm communication and cooperation as the trust antecedents in the e-service outsourcing context (Babin et al., 2017; Erdogan and Tokgoz, 2020; Ali *et al.*, 2017; Susarla *et al.*, 2020; Das and Teng, 2002; Mayer and Argyres, 2004; Schoenherr *et al.*, 2015; Dyer and Chu, 2000; Goo *et al.*, 2009). Effective communication requires organisations to open transparent communication channels, balance formal and informal communication, open two-way communication, and encourage the outsourcing partners to share and discuss their concerns openly. The literature identifies similar communication strategies for outsourcing success, and the current study provides empirical support in the selected context. The statistically significant effect of communication on trust shows that exchange parties can only achieve trust by investing resources in improving communication.

When descriptive statistics are analysed, the analysis suggests that although open communication exists between vendor and client organisations, there is significant room for improvement. Both organisations occasionally conduct open discussions through formal and informal communication means. The mixed perceptions show split opinions about communication effectiveness. The correlation and regression statistics confirm a strong positive relationship, showing that any improvement in communication effectiveness can bring significant and visible improvement in trust. Agreeing with existing literature, the study considers effective communication critical for trust development. The interview findings here indicate that communication's importance arises even further when client and vendor organisations have no prior

interaction history. Through open interactions, the outsourcing partners lay the foundation for initial and ongoing trust, and solid communication is necessary to continue outsourcing relationships with no prior history to become a serious challenge. Here, the literature informs that frequent communication is vital at the initial stage and crucial at later stages because outsourcing contracts are implemented in a quickly changing environment, resulting in a change of goals and expectations (Lee and Choi, 2011).

As the quantitative survey provided limited response options and perceptions towards communication effectiveness remained mixed, so, to take deeper insights, the interview findings could be referred to as the researcher was able to highlight some communication challenges that organisations are currently facing while managing their outsourcing relationship with vendors. The findings suggest that the perceptual and cultural barriers that emerge from the gap between the cultures of both organisations present a significant communication challenge.

Other than cultural differences, structural rigidity delays communication and offers limited informal communication options, while literature considers informal communication essential for effective relational governance. Some previous studies (like Gregory *et al.*, 2009; Schmitt and Van Biesebroeck, 2013) discussed how cultural and structural barriers affected the relationship quality between vendor and client organisations.

Sometimes, the contractual terms and conditions need more clarity, which makes initial trust-building challenging. The difference in the outsourcing partners' strategic priorities and cultural and structural differences increase the coordination costs. A similar opinion was made by Leininger (1997), who considered aligning strategic priorities critical for a successful vendor-client relationship. Interviewees further mentioned that as feedback is shared infrequently, it sometimes must be clarified. The importance of taking frequent feedback is also extensively highlighted in the literature. The interviewees further mentioned that organisations offer insufficient training opportunities to enhance the employees' communication and coordination skills, which must be developed at organisational and individual levels to ensure smooth inter-organisational communication flow.

Interview findings further suggested that targeted organisations find it challenging to balance formal and informal communication. Participants further mentioned that most communication challenges arise from complexity, weak control and infrequent coordination. Ali *et al.* (2017) made a similar point by commenting that active communication in outsourcing relationships is based on three C's- coordination, cooperation and collaboration. When any of these factors are missing, it reduces the communication quality, ultimately reducing overall relationship quality. Another critical challenge interviewees mentioned was the different communication tools and technologies vendors and client organisations use to interact.

Outsourcing parties' ability to communicate their expectations is critical to developing mutual understanding. As per interviewees, communication can only build trust once it is considered open, honest and transparent by both parties. Moreover, respecting organisational cultural differences is also essential, which, according to Gregory *et al.* (2009) and Schmitt and Van Biesebroeck (2013), becomes a reason for lousy communication when vendor and outsourcing organisations have significant structural and cultural differences. Inviting vendors in regular team meetings and documenting everything to clarify communication are two other critical success factors mentioned by interviewees and some previous studies (like Lee *et al.* 2015).

Overall, the comparison of literature, survey and interview findings suggests that communication is vital for building initial and ongoing trust, which is critical for successful outsourcing relationships.

5.6 Objective 5: Exploring the outsourcing factors in light of social exchange theory and trust and commitment theory.

Considering the growing importance of understanding how e-service outsourcing contracts could be made successful, the researcher attempted to understand how the e-service outsourcing project success chances could be increased within the UK by improving the relational governance mechanisms. The literature widely recognizes relational governance as an influential antecedent of outsourcing success, so it was essential to explore the determinants of relational governance effectiveness (Gottschalk and Solli-Sæther, 2005; Schoenherr *et al.*, 2015; Sia *et al.*, 2008; Huo *et al.*, 2016; Schoenherr *et al.*, 2015).

During interviews with the vendor and client organizations, the study found that e-service outsourcing meets failure when the decision is taken without considering the relational and non-technical aspects of outsourcing. Here, the literature presents a similar argument, as some previous studies (like Miller and Luse, 2004) consider non-technical reasons like poor communication more important for e-service outsourcing failure than technical reasons. Some commonly highlighted e-service outsourcing failure reasons cited by interviewees and literature are- ineffective communication, lack of cooperation, opportunistic behaviour and lack of trust between vendor and client organizations (Meng *et al.*, 2007; Mahalik, 2010; Wearden, 2018; Sasse, 2019; He and Lu, 2017). So, it is essential to study how, through effective relational governance, government agencies in the UK can successfully outsource their e-services and achieve desired political, economic and social objectives.

In connection with this, the third research objective was to explore the factors (such as communication, co-operative behaviour, trust, knowledge sharing and commitment) that influence relational governance effectiveness, leading to e-service outsourcing success. To achieve this research objective, the researcher first identified the factors influencing relational governance effectiveness from the literature and then collected primary data to understand the role played by each factor in enhancing relational governance effectiveness. Before discussing the importance of each determinant, the researcher first evaluates how primary research results obtained to achieve the second objective support previously proposed theories.

5.6.1 Relational governance mechanisms and social exchange theory

The comparison of primary research findings with the literature suggests that the current study supports previous theories and models that attempt to explain the outsourcing of relational governance mechanisms. For instance, both- survey and interview findings suggested that trust holds central importance in making e-service outsourcing relationships successful because when outsourcing partners trust each other, it obliges them to fulfil each other's expectations by fulfilling the contractual obligations. It validates the social exchange theory, which considers trust vital for successful exchange relationships (Monica *et al.*, 2012). In support of the social exchange theory, the participants mentioned that the trust-based relationship between

client and vendor discourages them from adopting opportunistic behaviour, ultimately increasing the outsourcing success chances by strengthening their relationship.

When a relationship is perceived as trustworthy, it develops the basis for a reciprocal exchange, in which the perceived trust is exchanged with commitment and increased willingness to share knowledge, and both- commitment and knowledge sharing increase the e-service success chances by improving the relational governance. Such reciprocal relations are complex and involve multifaceted factors (Qi and Chau, 2013; Monica *et al.*, 2012; Liao *et al.*, 2009), as literature and current research suggests.

The social exchange theory further urges the parties involved in the exchange process to be cooperative, as without cooperation, a positive and mutually beneficial exchange relationship could not be established (Schoenherr *et al.*, 2015; Cook *et al.*, 2013). Here, both- survey and interview results confirmed the importance of adopting cooperative behaviour for outsourcing success, which confirms the theory's validity in a chosen research context. Validating Schoenherr *et al.*'s (2015) point, the study considered both- cooperative behaviour and communication essential for trust, strengthening the mutual commitment between exchange parties. The exchange relationship develops as parties tend to exchange the trust with commitment. Interview findings further confirmed that trust is developed and shaped by the underlying context, and once developed, it improves the relational governance effectiveness, leading to outsourcing success.

The study also validates social exchange theory's assumption that the exchange parties tend to behave rationally to maximize the return (Huo *et al.*, 2016), partners tend to prefer social credit over-indebtedness, partners have goal orientation, and interaction occurs in a specific context (John *et al.*, 2017). The study validates these assumptions by discovering that the exchange parties involved in e-service outsourcing apply rational thinking while developing relational governance strategies. They both understand that a healthy relationship is vital for achieving mutual and individual goals. The interview findings further confirm that when a party shows a cooperative attitude and avoids opportunism, the other party tends to reciprocate it by showing a more significant commitment to fulfilling contractual obligations. Both parties have their goals, which, through effective communication, are aligned to avoid the conflict of interest that may reduce the outsourcing success chances.

Moreover, interviewees acknowledged that the success of e-service outsourcing is context-dependent, and no set of communication/relational governance strategies may be effective for improving relational governance in all contexts. The findings also confirm the social exchange theory's proposition that rewarding a particular action increases the willingness to perform that action (Cook *et al.*, 2013). For instance, the study found that when both parties are convinced that a trust-based relationship can drive the outsourcing success chances, which is beneficial and serves the interests of both parties, it encourages them to communicate and cooperate. Similarly, when they are convinced that knowledge sharing can strengthen relational governance effectiveness linked with e-service outsourcing success, they become more willing to share valuable information (also reported by Lee *et al.* 2015 and Rutten *et al.*, 2016).

The second proposition of social exchange theory is that when partners consider a particular behaviour necessary in terms of probability and return value, the chances of acting (Cook *et al.*, 2013). In the current case, the survey results suggested that the participants believed that effective communication and cooperation can develop mutual trust; they were more likely to invest time and effort in improving mutual communication and cooperation. Similarly, the more strongly they believed knowledge sharing could drive relational governance, the more likely they were to share the knowledge. The magnitude and intensity of the relationship increased with an increase in the expectations, which confirms the exchange theory's second proposition. Concerning the conceptual framework (presented in section 2.6), the study confirmed that social exchange theory could be applied to understand each mapped relationship.

5.6.2 Referring conceptual framework to SET theory

As survey and interview findings have confirmed the significant association between each mapped relationship, the proposed framework can be further explained in light of social exchange theory. The framework considers communication and cooperation as two trust antecedents. Here, SET suggests that when e-service outsourcing partners consider communication and flexible behaviour critical for building trust, they are likely to improve communication and adopt cooperative behaviour (Babin *et al.*, 2017; Erdogan and Tokgoz, 2020; Ali *et al.*, 2017; Susarla *et al.*, 2020; Das and Teng, 2002; Mayer and Argyres, 2004; Schoenherr *et al.*, 2015; Dyer and Chu, 2000; Goo *et al.*, 2009). Similarly, when both parties consider trust important

for knowledge sharing and commitment, they are more likely to engage in trust-building activities. Moreover, when both parties consider knowledge sharing and commitment important for increasing the relational governance effectiveness, they are more likely to share knowledge and demonstrate commitment to fulfil contractual obligations (Rutten *et al.*, 2016; Yam and Chan, 2015; Lee *et al.*, 2015; Attar *et al.*, 2019; Díaz-Reza *et al.*, 2018; Choudhury and Sabherwal, 2003). Lastly, the strongly positive and significant relationship between effective relational governance and outsourcing success develops a strong exchange relationship in which both parties invest resources to improve the relational governance to benefit from the outsourcing success. It is an important finding which needs further empirical testing, as during interviews, the interviewees mentioned the need to consider the contextual factors while evaluating the influence of relational governance on outsourcing success.

5.6.3 Referring conceptual framework to trust and commitment theory

Other than confirming social exchange theory's applicability to understanding relational governance dynamics in an e-service outsourcing context, the study also provides solid empirical support to the trust and commitment theory. For successful relational exchange, all relationship management activities revolve around building trust and commitment among exchange parties (Morgan and Hunt, 1994; Kern and Willcocks, 2002). Referring to the conceptual framework, the primary research findings suggest that both- trust and commitment are central to developing vendor-client relationships. Supporting Kern and Willcocks's (2002) point, the study confirmed that shared values and cooperation strongly influence trust in e-service outsourcing. The survey results confirmed the effect of cooperation and communication on trust, and interview findings considered open communication important for developing shared values. Interview findings further revealed that when both parties consider relationship termination detrimental to their interests, it encourages them to adopt the relational governance strategies that reduce relationship termination chances.

As interviews were conducted to get deeper insights, the study found that the prevailing environmental uncertainty is an important contextual factor determining the parties' willingness to trust each other. The high environmental uncertainty makes initial trust-building challenging, particularly when both parties do not share a prior relationship. The interviewees pointed out that outsourcing contracts are implemented

in a complex, unpredictable and uncertain environment where outsourcing parties tend to exchange invisible assets through cooperation, trust, commitment and willingness to share valuable information. The value of these intangible assets is hard to determine, yet cannot be underestimated.

The comparison of primary research findings with the literature highlights another agreement point. Langfield-Smith and Smith (2003) contended that contract handling becomes easier when both parties know each other before the contract, as in such cases, trust building becomes easier. In an agreement, the interview with the vendor organization representativeness mentioned that the initial trust building is challenging when the vendor and client only know each other after the outsourcing contract. Although the interviewees from the client organization did not discuss much about how initial trust is developed, the vendor interview findings confirmed that by investing some time in initial trust building through more active communication, the chances of opportunism decline. Through regular communication, both outsourcing parties get to know each other and develop mutual understanding, laying the foundation for long-term, trust-based relationships. Ineffective communication hampers initial trust and can deteriorate the relationship quality among parties with prior interaction history.

5.6.4 Referring conceptual framework to transaction cost and SET theory

Correlating the proposed framework and primary research findings with the transaction cost theory, the study further found that e-service outsourcing transaction involves unavoidable intangible costs, which exert as decisive an impact on outsourcing success as tangible costs. The intangible costs are the time, effort, energy and resources that exchange partners exert to keep the relationship working and achieve desired objectives (Lacity *et al.*, 2011). Social exchange theory once again explains the relational governance mechanisms here. When incentives in exchange for these costs are high in the form of mutual trust, commitment, improved governance and high outsourcing success chances, then parties are more likely to bear these intangible costs (Huo *et al.*, 2016). Both- the literature and primary research findings consider opportunistic behaviour as a risk to outsourcing success, which can be reduced through effective relational governance.

Agreeing with the literature, the interview data indicated some collaborative characteristics (like mutually shared goals, teamwork, collaboration opportunities and frequent interactions to keep expectations clear) that foster a cooperative relationship, which is developed on trust and commitment. Literature informs that the vendor and client organizations have some inherent conflict of interest within outsourcing engagement, as the client organization seeks cost-effective solutions, while vendors are looking for high-profit margins (Malhotra and Lumineau, 2011). Such conflict of interest increases the chances of adopting opportunistic behaviour, which, according to Malhotra and Lumineau (2011), is among the common reasons for outsourcing failure.

Here, the current study informs that when outsourcing e-services, client and vendor organizations should first try to resolve the possible conflict of interest areas so that they may not engage in opportunistic behaviour at a later stage. It could be done by developing strong trust through open communication and cooperation. The relationship should be formed in a way that serves the interests of both parties. The objectives should be mutually aligned, and both parties' broader strategic interests must be connected with the success of the outsourcing contract.

The discussion discusses each mapped relationship by comparing the literature and primary research findings.

5.6.5 Relational governance and e-service outsourcing success

The relationship between relational governance and e-service outsourcing success has been well-understood and discussed in detail up till now in light of relevant concepts and theories. The relationship derives theoretical solid support from the social exchange theory, which contends that the parties exert efforts to improve the relational governance when they believe improving the relational governance would increase the chances of outsourcing success. Since mutually beneficial exchange plays a critical role in all business dealings, it is essential to understand the exchange dynamics when outsourcing e-services.

Summing up all mapped relationships, the exchange plays its role in building initial trust. When outsourcing parties believe that initial trust can make relationship management easier, it encourages them to communicate and cooperate frequently. Once trust is developed, it sets the basis for knowledge sharing. When parties trust each other, they tend to reciprocate by sharing valuable information and showing more significant

commitment. Similarly, when parties believe that improving relational governance can increase e-service outsourcing success chances, it motivates them to take care of all antecedents vital for improving relational governance.

Overall, the researcher successfully achieved the third research objective by collecting quantitative and qualitative data. The response to this objective derives strong support from existing literature. The proposed framework could be to understand how public firms in the UK can successfully manage their e-service outsourcing contracts to avoid failure. The researcher achieved the fourth research objective as the study confirmed each mapped relationship and refined the initial framework developed based on a detailed literature review. The refined framework is presented below:

Figure 8- Conceptual framework

5.7 Chapter summary

Summarizing the discussion in this chapter, the researcher finds an overall agreement with the literature by considering relational governance essential for ensuring the success of e-service outsourcing. While explaining how public organizations can enhance relational governance while outsourcing e-services, the current study validates the social exchange theory and trust and commitment theory, as both theories can explain how trust could be established and, once established, how it strengthens the commitment and encourages knowledge sharing (both considered necessary for improving relational governance) by developing a reciprocal exchange relationship.

Chapter Six- Conclusion and Recommendations

In this chapter, 'Conclusion and Recommendations', the researcher summarizes all critical points discussed in the results and discussion chapter. The conclusion for each research objective is presented, and an overall conclusion is drawn to evaluate what is learned from this empirical research. The researcher discusses how proposed findings can help practitioners and contribute to the existing body of knowledge. Next, the researcher presents some recommendations for the client and vendor organizations. All recommendations are based on the primary research results and aim to help public firms in the UK increase outsourcing success chances through effective relational governance. In the last section of this chapter, the researcher discusses study limitations, which provide the basis for further research.

6.1 Conclusion

E-services outsourcing has emerged as an exciting area of research due to ongoing technological developments. Particularly after the pandemic, practitioners and researchers are interested in exploring how firms outsource their services to ensure survival in the post-pandemic world. Even before the pandemic, outsourcing had become a popular trend, as both- public and private organisations were outsourcing their services to third parties to achieve their desired business objectives. The pandemic has given another solid push for the outsourcing trend in a way that other than private service companies, today, public service companies are also seeking ways to leverage the benefits of outsourcing to ensure their survival in an increasingly complex and competitive post-pandemic world.

Public organisations' motives for outsourcing e-services to the private sector are diverse. Social, economic and political reasons exist for outsourcing e-services to the third parties. The current research study has focused on the UK to explore the e-service outsourcing trends and associated relational governance mechanisms. The analysis has revealed that the outsourcing trend is rising from a political perspective because the UK government is considered too big and inefficient. Hence, outsourcing is considered a viable option to achieve the efficiency objectives. The public organisations in the UK are outsourcing e-services to save costs, fight bureaucracy, support small businesses and improve service quality.

However, the most common e-service outsourcing motivations are difficult to identify, as firms make outsourcing decisions considering multifaceted factors. These factors could be economic, political, social or a combination. The diversity in the outsourcing motivations reflects firms' expectations from their outsourcing decision. It also indicates the possible negative implications that firms can face due to outsourcing failure. Although the UK have well-competent human resources compared to other parts of the world, the UK is still facing e-service outsourcing challenges. The high outsourcing failure rate increases the need to evaluate how public firms in the UK can make outsourcing successful by taking services from vendors from the private sector.

Despite the high outsourcing failure rate, public firms in the UK are still actively engaged in outsourcing, which shows that firms are willing to accept the challenges associated with e-service outsourcing but are still hiring third-party service providers because they have not only economic constraints that hinder them from ensuring optimal delivery of e-services but also face political pressure from the government. Like in the UK, the government aims to expand the e-services to incorporate the latest technologies into the e-governance model. So, it puts pressure on public firms to deliver high-quality services that may fulfil the government's political objectives.

Besides the political pressure, many public firms in the UK are also outsourcing their e-services due to constant workload and shortage of human capital that could meet the growing demand for e-services. Another significant outsourcing motivation is the need to focus on the core business activities by outsourcing e-services to third parties.

Identifying these motivations is essential to understand the current outsourcing trends in the UK. The multifaceted motivations for e-service outsourcing indicate that the decision is not merely made in response to political pressure or to cut costs.

Despite having solid implications, the high outsourcing failure rate in the UK, particularly in the public sector of the UK, urges researchers to explore the reasons behind e-service outsourcing failure. Based on analysis, the study found that in most cases, the most common reasons for outsourcing failure were non-technical. Ineffective management of outsourcing relationships has been consistently highlighted as a critical reason for outsourcing failure in the UK. Considering the growing e-service outsourcing trend in the UK and the high outsourcing failure rate due to poor relational governance, this empirical research study was conducted to critically evaluate the

factors influencing effective relationship management in outsourcing electronically provided services (e-services). The research aim was to provide knowledge about the people (perceptions, commitment, cooperative behaviour) and management (trust and communication management mechanisms) related factors that influence the quality of relationships with the outsourcing partners.

To achieve this aim, the researcher adopted a mixed research method approach and collected quantitative data through an online survey and qualitative data through semi-structured interviews from three public service organisations in the UK. Besides collecting the data from the client organisations, the researcher interviewed the vendor organisations to whom they outsourced their e-services.

In this way, the researcher explored the relational governance mechanisms from the perspective of both parties. The overall research purpose was to analyse how the public sector in the UK is managing its outsourced relationships to deliver e-services to the public.

Based on survey and interview findings, the study found that the management of public organisations must adapt with the new requirements of the new relation in order to handle various administrative and structural challenges while creating value for the e-service users. The resource constraints and continuous pressure from the private sector to stay competitive, operational inefficiencies and end users' growing expectations make outsourcing an easy option to manage e-services. In-house e-service management requires public firms to handle all these challenges, which decreases the attractiveness of in-house options. By collecting primary data, the study confirms that the trend of e-service outsourcing in the UK is on the rise and will continue rising due to public organisations' drive to share the risks and offer better quality services to people at affordable costs.

Through outsourcing, public firms in the UK attempt to achieve political and economic objectives. However, the findings have confirmed that achieving economic objectives like cost reduction and efficiency improvement are not easily accomplished, and require firms to ensure effective management of their outsourcing relationships. Besides handling the technical aspects of outsourcing, both- survey and interview

findings confirm that the management needs to take care of all non-technical, management-related aspects that could increase the outsourcing success chances.

When firms outsource their e-services, they form new business relationships, which, if ineffectively managed, can turn outsourcing into a liability instead of an opportunity to achieve the desired economic objectives. Ineffective outsourcing relationship management also hampers the trust between outsourcing partners and make implementation of outsourcing contract difficult. Therefore, it is essential to understand how new outsourcing relationships could be managed and how management-related challenges associated with outsourcing could be handled to increase the outsourcing benefits and overcome associated costs. The study makes a valuable contribution to the existing literature by explaining how, through outsourcing, public organisations in the UK can create value for all outsourcing partners, which mainly include client and vendor organisations.

The outsourcing relations involve multiple stakeholders, mainly including- top management of both organisations, technicians, middle management, management representatives responsible for relationship dealing, government and customers/citizens. Considering the number of stakeholders involved and the impact of outsourcing on the client, vendor and customers, the current study evaluated how organisations in the UK can develop long-term, healthy outsourcing relationships to use outsourcing as a tool to achieve the desired economic objectives and effectively deliver the central and local e-services.

Despite spending heavily on contracting and outsourcing e-services and demonstrating a commitment to bring innovation to the e-governance model, the UK government still needs to work on high outsourcing failure rates, mainly due to ineffective e-governance outsourcing management. Outsourcing failures have hampered the private sector's confidence, which the government relies on to deliver e-services. Despite having clear guidelines about how outsourcing relations could be managed, the public sector needs to pay more attention to the guidelines, which reduces the relational governance effectiveness and decreases e-service outsourcing success chances. There is a need to explore how public firms in the UK can enhance relational governance by adopting effective management practices that inculcate trust and strengthen the commitment between outsourcing partners.

As managing outsourcing relations is a complex and multidimensional study area, the researcher adopted the mixed methodology to explore the factors influencing relational governance effectiveness and outsourcing success. In-depth qualitative interviews were conducted to explore the factors influencing relational governance effectiveness. A quantitative survey was conducted to evaluate the influence of identified factors on relational governance effectiveness. The survey and interview data were analysed to conclude the response to each research objective.

The study developed six key research objectives. The first research objective was to explore how scholars and practitioners conceptualise e-service outsourcing relational governance and how conceptualisations of both sides [may/ or not] differ and support each other. This research objective was achieved by conducting a detailed literature review and comparing the literature insights with the interview findings to explore how both perspectives support or contradict each other. Based on the comparison, the study concludes that although relational governance in the e-service outsourcing context is complex, its conceptualisation is clear to academicians and practitioners. They both consider relational governance critical for outsourcing success, and from both perspectives, central importance is placed on trust and commitment while assessing the relational governance effectiveness.

From practitioners' perspective, relational governance is centred on relational norms and values based on trust, transparent communication and commitment. Effective relational governance requires cultivating and managing the relational norms and values communicated through transparent communication strategies. Such relational norms and values foster trust between outsourcing parties and ultimately strengthen their commitment to fulfilling the contract. Practitioners emphasise informal coordinating mechanisms for building trust and cooperation and consider informal communication a powerful tool that encourages both parties to engage in facilitating rather than competing behaviour. According to practitioners, engaging in opportunistic behaviour reduces the relational governance effectiveness, decreasing outsourcing success chances as each party tends to maximise its interests. Similarly, when an informal control is effectively exercised, it sets the basis for a reciprocal exchange in which parties exchange trust with commitment to fulfil each other's expectations. Understanding how such a reciprocal exchange relationship could be established is critical for relational governance effectiveness and, ultimately, outsourcing success.

Both- academicians and practitioners defined outsourcing relational governance as for both- relational governance involves reciprocal exchange involving relationship-specific assets whose exchange requires inter-organisational solid trust. Practitioners mainly focus on the informal control and coordination mechanisms to cultivate and manage this trust. At the same time, as per academicians, the outsourcing parties can embed trust into the relationship structure by attaining the right balance between formal and informal control and coordination mechanisms. Both perspectives recognise that cultivating trust in relational governance involves the management of both sides to handle complex processes. This complexity arises due to the relational aspects of the contract, which are more complex, ambiguous and hard to govern than the technical, contractual aspects. However, compared to the academicians, the practitioners consider such complexity more easily manageable if well-thought-out efforts are applied, and both parties are willing to understand and cooperate.

Overall, based on the academic and practitioners' perspectives, the study concludes that managing effective relational governance is critical for the successful completion of e-service outsourcing contracts, and effective relational governance requires both parties to exert genuine efforts for trust building. Once trust is developed, it encourages parties to exchange mutual trust with a commitment to fulfil each other's expectations. It also discourages them from opportunistic behaviour, threatening any business relationship. When these complex relational governance mechanisms are effectively managed by cultivating inter-organisational trust, relational governance becomes a value-added function that increases the outsourcing success chances and motivates both parties to accomplish mutually beneficial objectives. The in-depth comparison of practitioners' and academicians' perspectives enabled the researcher to achieve the first research objective to a great extent. However, more research is needed to understand how practitioners' and academicians' perspectives may differ under different contexts (like when outsourcing contracts are being smoothly managed versus when both parties find it challenging to execute the contract due to poor relational governance). Future studies may work on this dimension and extend the work by comparing both perspectives in different contexts.

Considering the high importance of effective relational governance for outsourcing success, rising e-service outsourcing trends in the UK, and the high outsourcing failure rate among public organisations in the UK, it is interesting to explore the factors that

enable both parties to enhance relational governance effectiveness. However, before exploring the trust and relational governance antecedents and consequences, it is important to explore 'why' public firms in the UK make outsourcing decisions and which factors they consider while making outsourcing decisions. In connection with this, the second objective of this research study was to explore the environmental tendencies that motivate public service organisations to outsource e-services. This research objective was achieved by conducting in-depth interviews with the managers working in different public service firms in the UK. The interview data enabled the researcher to highlight some critical motivational factors that compel organisations to opt for outsourcing despite understanding all associated challenges.

Despite having a high outsourcing failure rate, firms are still actively engaging in outsourcing relationships, which shows their motivation to consider outsourcing a viable strategy for accomplishing desired business objectives. Although entering outsourcing arrangements requires firms to develop specific competencies and capabilities needed for effectively managing their outsourcing relationships, and many firms lack those competencies, despite these shortcomings, the survey and interview data confirmed that firms are still strongly motivated to outsource their e-services. The key motivation is to successfully deliver the e-services to the customers with limited resources and capabilities. Although firms need more competencies and capabilities to manage their outsourcing relationships, the bigger problem is that they need more resources and capabilities to deliver e-services to intended customers. With resource constraints, it has become difficult for companies to keep pace with change and fulfil the government's objectives of integrating e-governance into existing governance models. So, to avoid the bigger problem, public firms tend to outsource e-services to the private sector that are more well-equipped and ready to fulfil the stakeholders' expectations.

However, the lack of resources and capabilities to deliver e-services is not the only motivation, as many public firms make outsourcing decisions to reduce the administrative burden and enhance efficiency. Without making the outsourcing decision, firms have to expand their organisational capacity to accommodate the ever-changing customer needs and continuously growing demand. So, outsourcing is considered a viable and easy way to manage the growing demand without expanding the organisational capacity. UK public firms need help with operational inefficiency

due to high work burdens. Outsourcing is considered a way to reduce the administrative burden and deliver high-quality e-services without wasting human capital.

In many cases, outsourcing decision is made to gain access to the advanced capabilities by learning through their outsourcing partners. When firms lack specialised knowledge in a particular field, outsourcing makes it easier for organisations to acquire new competencies and capabilities while delivering the services along their learning journey. Risk sharing is another strong motivation that increases the attractiveness of outsourcing compared to in-house management options.

Overall, the complexity of outsourcing decisions reflects the multifaceted motivations for outsourcing e-services to third-party service providers. Firms outsource e-services to free up resources, focus on their core business operations, reduce burden, acquire new competencies, reduce costs, share risks and keep pace with the changing technological environment. So, to understand the motivations for outsourcing, it is essential to carefully consider the underlying context in which the firm operates. Understanding and recognising the outsourcing motivations takes work, and these multiple motivations not only reflect decision complexity but also refer to the multiple expectations that firms build while making outsourcing decisions. However, meeting these diverse expectations requires firms to focus on all technical and non-technical aspects that increase outsourcing success chances. Unfortunately, firms fail to focus on the non-technical dimension and build their expectations without exerting efforts to make outsourcing decisions successful. As a result, many of them still need help to achieve the desired outsourcing objectives, and their outsourcing arrangements lead towards failure.

Concluding the discussion of this research objective, the study found that outsourcing is costly as it has severe implications for both vendor and client organisations. Therefore, it is essential to set realistic expectations and devise clear motivations for making such decisions to increase outsourcing success chances. Both parties should understand these motivations well so they can exert full efforts to serve them through outsourcing. For instance, when cost reduction is the critical motivation for outsourcing e-services, both parties should coordinate and arrange regular meetings to evaluate whether this desired objective is being achieved through outsourcing. Similarly, when the motivation is to learn from the outsourcing partner, the focus could

be arranging frequent meetings to encourage the two-way knowledge flow. Adopting a holistic view without setting unrealistic expectations from outsourcing, communicating clear motivations for making outsourcing decisions, and demonstrating a commitment to serve those motivations through effective outsourcing management are crucial for e-service outsourcing success. Public firms in the UK mostly make outsourcing decisions because they lack resources and secondary motivations for outsourcing e-services include reducing administrative burden, reducing costs, improving service quality, resolving operational inefficiencies and learning from the partner about how e-services could be effectively delivered. The fulfilment of these outsourcing motivations requires management to pay attention to all outsourcing relationship management factors that influence the outsourcing success.

In connection with this, the third research objective was to explore the factors (such as communication, cooperative behaviour, trust, knowledge sharing and commitment) that influence relational governance effectiveness, leading to e-service outsourcing success. This research objective was achieved by collecting both- survey and interview data. The main focus of the empirical investigation was on this research objective, as it focused on the trust antecedents and consequences that improve relational governance and increase e-service outsourcing success chances. Based on survey and interview findings.

Based on survey and interview findings, the study concludes that in most cases, the outsourcing decision meets failure due to vendor and client organisations' inability to handle the non-technical and management-related aspects. among which opportunistic behaviour, lack of coordination and poor communication are most commonly cited failure reasons. The presence of these aspects creates an environment of distrust, which weakens the parties' commitment to fulfil each other's expectations, which ultimately leads the outsourcing contract toward failure.

In outsourcing relationships, trust holds central importance, as in an environment of trust, outsourcing parties feel obliged to fulfil the contractual obligations and enter an exchange relationship in which trust is reciprocated with the commitment to exert full efforts to make outsourcing successful. In such an environment, the chances of indulging in opportunistic behaviour also decrease significantly. The trust triggers an exchange relationship, in which parties tend to reciprocate trust in various ways, such

as by showing commitment to fulfil each other's expectations, sharing valuable knowledge and fulfilling contractual obligations without adopting opportunistic behaviour.

The primary research findings suggest that vendor and client organisations can develop such exchange relationships by improving communication strategies. This can be achieved by developing a communication plan between all levels in both client and vendor organisation and keep all communications channels open.

Both parties should adopt a cooperative over competitive attitude towards each other first by setting the contract terms and conditions on win-win bases and that any loss is loss for both parties and any win is win for both parties as well communication and cooperation are deemed critical for developing trust, and without cooperation, parties cannot develop mutually beneficial exchange relationships. Similarly, when both parties believe that trust is the way to make outsourcing successful, it encourages them to adopt management strategies that enhance trust. By applying rational thinking, vendor and client organisations invest their time and resources to communicate frequently, as effective communication enables both parties to understand and trust each other.

Handling outsourcing contracts becomes easier when both parties share a prior business history; in that case, comparatively less time is spent on communication. However, when parties are new and share no prior history, more efforts are exerted on developing initial trust, which provides the foundation for the ongoing trust. The chances of adopting cooperative behaviour also increase when both parties are convinced that adopting competitive and opportunistic behaviour can harm the interests of both parties. Here, ensuring that both parties' interest is strongly aligned with the outsourcing success is essential.

The chances of actively interacting, communicating and cooperating rise when such actions are considered essential for getting the desired return and when such actions are considered critical for achieving the desired result. These findings confirm the validity of social exchange theory as social exchange theory also states that the reciprocal relationship gets established when parties expect a rewarding return from engaging in the reciprocal relationship. Here, both- survey and interview findings provide strong empirical evidence to confirm the effect of communication and cooperation on trust,

which enhances the relational governance effectiveness through strengthened commitment and knowledge sharing. So, communication and cooperation are exchange behaviours whose expected reward is mutual trust, which is considered critical for outsourcing success.

As the study has confirmed communication and cooperation as strong trust antecedents, evaluating how communication could be enhanced and how a cooperative attitude could be adopted to foster trust is essential. Based on survey findings, the study concludes that parties adopt cooperative attitudes by setting mutually shared goals, keeping expectations clear, and frequently interacting. These collaborative characteristics foster the cooperative relationship and reduce the chances of conflict of interest. Naturally, the conflict of interest between vendor and client organisations remains in outsourcing relations. However, the critical challenge for both parties is to pursue their individual business goals without compromising the interests of each other. Both parties must explore the middle ground, which is only possible through open and frequent interaction. It also requires a willingness to adopt a flexible attitude and prefer relation-building over accomplishing short-term goals.

Open and frequent communication develops shared values, which lays the foundation for trust. The prevailing environment uncertainty and pressure to build initial trust to keep things going encourage both parties to increase the communication quality and frequency. In such an environment, communication and cooperation are considered invisible assets exchanged for trust and commitment, two main pillars of effective relational governance in the e-service outsourcing context. The communication effectiveness could be enhanced by opening transparent communication channels, achieving a balance between formal and informal communication, opening two-way communication, and encouraging the outsourcing partners to share and discuss their concerns openly.

Currently, vendor and client organisations in the UK recognise the importance of effective communication. However, the frequency of communication needs to be increased as parties tend to spend less time on communication due to time constraints. It could be a reason for the high outsourcing failure rate in the UK. Some common challenges that make communication difficult between vendor and client organisations in the UK are time limitations, perceptual and cultural barriers, structural rigidity

causing communication delays and limited informal communication options. Some barriers to adopting the cooperative attitude include- differences in the outsourcing partners' strategic priorities, lack of clarity in the contractual terms and conditions, structural and cultural differences, inadequate communication skills, imbalance between formal and informal communication and lack of supportive communication tools and technologies. These challenges increase coordination costs and discourage parties from interacting and cooperating.

Hence, to foster trust, it is essential to address these challenges. Once effective communication and coordination costs are reduced, and a facilitating environment is created in which communication and coordination become easier, parties start trusting each other, and a foundation for success gets established. When trust is developed, parties are likely to share valuable knowledge, mainly when such knowledge-sharing behaviour is critical for successful outsourcing relationships. Both parties are even more likely to engage in knowledge-sharing behaviour when they depend on each other to achieve desired business objectives. However, considering knowledge-sharing behaviour essential for outsourcing success is more important than perceived mutual dependency because parties are less likely to share information even if they depend on each other when they do not consider knowledge-sharing important for the successful execution of outsourcing contracts. Open knowledge sharing enhances the firm's ability to make more well-informed decisions and reduces the initial technological dependence of client organisations on vendors.

Outsourcing contracts are executed in a highly dynamic environment in which making well-informed decisions is essential to keep pace with the changing external environment. In such an environment, both parties must be willing to share knowledge to achieve mutual business goals. Such knowledge sharing strengthens the mutual bond and enhances the relational governance effectiveness. Despite recognising the importance of knowledge sharing, vendor and client organisations in the UK face various challenges that make knowledge sharing difficult for them, mainly including- difficult assimilation of collected knowledge into different business areas, inability to use the shared knowledge in making important decisions, insufficient knowledge sharing mechanisms, poor understanding of each other's technological system/organisational processes, outsourcing partnership contractual terms and conditions creating resistance, lack of organisational capabilities and competencies,

lack of policy support and a clear direction to guide the firms' knowledge sharing practices and lack of coherence/no shared goals to incentivise the knowledge sharing. Due to poor knowledge sharing, client organisations depend on their vendors for service provision and need to learn from their outsourcing partners. As both- survey and interview findings confirmed that knowledge sharing is a significant relational governance effectiveness predictor, it is essential to take measures that could make knowledge sharing easier for both parties.

Other than knowledge sharing, the commitment between outsourcing parties is another direct determinant of relational governance effectiveness. Based on primary research findings, the study concludes that strengthening the mutual commitment between outsourcing parties is vital for outsourcing success, as commitment is vital for any business relationship, and no business contract could be executed when the parties involved in the contract lack commitment to fulfil contractual obligations. However, in the current case, both parties not only need to demonstrate the commitment to fulfilling basic contractual terms and conditions, but they should also be willing to fulfil each other's expectations to strengthen the business relationships and increase outsourcing success chances while operating in a highly dynamic and complex business environment.

When commitment between outsourcing partners is high, it encourages both parties to exert efforts on behalf of their mutual relationship to fulfil each other's expectations. Despite recognising the importance of a solid commitment, the vendor and client organisations involved in e-service outsourcing in the UK need help to demonstrate commitment due to non-supportive mechanisms. The inherent conflict of interest is a significant reason for weak commitment in outsourcing contracts. These findings suggest trust and commitment are challenging to build and take time to nurture. Both parties can nurture trust and commitment through formal bargaining and informal sense-making. When trust and commitment are developed, the formal contractual relationship gets codified into the relational contract, which legally and morally binds both parties to understand each other and fulfil each other's expectations, leading towards e-service outsourcing success.

Overall, the researcher was able to accomplish the third research objective. The collection of quantitative and qualitative empirical data increased the breadth and depth

of understanding, and the study proposed results that can be considered to reduce the outsourcing failure rate in the UK. The study proposes practically applicable findings and contributes to the existing literature by proposing a conceptual framework that explains how public firms in the UK can enhance their relational governance while entering into e-service outsourcing contracts. In connection with this, the fourth objective of this research study was to propose an e-service outsourcing framework that explains how e-service outsourcing can be successful through effective vendor-client relationship management.

The last research objective was achieved by conducting a detailed literature review to develop an initial conceptual framework and then collecting quantitative and qualitative primary data to refine the conceptual framework. The primary research findings were based on proposing a UK context-specific detailed conceptual framework that mapped the connection between critical variables. The conceptual framework explained how public firms in the UK can nurture trust and commitment by adopting effective relational governance strategies. Communication and cooperation are critical trust development antecedents, and trust is a key antecedent of commitment and knowledge sharing. Commitment and knowledge sharing are confirmed as strong predictors of effective relational governance, which ultimately leads towards success in e-service outsourcing. The conceptual framework outlines some key challenges that public firms in UK are currently facing while managing their outsourcing relations, mainly including- perceptual and cultural barriers, lack of understanding of the contractual terms and conditions, lack of initial trust towards partner, different strategic priorities, structural barriers, coordination cost, lack of feedback frequency, lack of training in collaboration and communication, unbalanced informal and formal communication, communication complexity, control and coordination, communication technology differences among vendor and client organisations, unreliable network causing inefficiency and creating frustration among outsourcing partners.

Framework also highlights some critical motivations for entering into outsourcing arrangements, including- The lack of resources, reduced administrative burden, cost reduction, service quality improvement, inefficiencies and the motive to learn from partners by outsourcing e-services. The framework further outlines some suggestions interviewees proposed to overcome the identified challenges. These suggestions are discussed in detail in the next section. The proposed framework needs further empirical

validation and sets the basis for further research. Future researchers can employ the framework to evaluate the relational governance mechanisms of firms operating in and outside the UK. The framework provides basic guidelines about how trust and commitment could be nurtured. However, one fundamental limitation of this research is that the researcher collected data in a single period and relied on the participants' opinions and perceptions. Further empirical testing may require researchers to collect actual data about outsourcing success and failure and increase the breadth and depth of understanding by adding more contextual factors that influence the management's ability to cultivate trust and commitment in outsourcing relationships.

6.2 Recommendations

The above recommendations are for both- client and vendor organizations. As the researcher separately collected data from vendor and client organizations, findings can be used to propose specific recommendations for the vendor organizations. For instance, results suggest that miscommunication is cited among the most severe challenges by interviewees from vendor organizations. They should specifically pay attention to this dimension and try to adopt communication technologies compatible with their client organizations to handle business relations smoothly. Vendor employees need to be trained to understand how they can ensure open communication, mainly when contract complexity and environmental uncertainty are high.

Findings further suggested that the difference in the communication and management style was considered a significant challenge from the vendors' side. To resolve this challenge, it is essential to adopt a flexible leadership style, and managers should be trained to adopt a flexible and adaptable attitude while dealing with client organizations. It is essential to align the communication and leadership style according to the client organization to win their trust and lay the foundation for success. Findings further suggest vendor organizations adopt a flexible communication strategy and consider using different communication modes, methods, channels and techniques that could be adopted in different situations. It is equally important to ensure that the communication strategy of vendor organizations is strongly aligned with the overall business strategy.

The interview findings suggested that when strict control is exercised from the client side, it is not easy for vendor organizations to encourage coordination and cooperation. In such cases, it is essential to arrange meetings with client organizations in which they

are convinced about the importance of having clear communication and why frequent interactions are essential for ongoing business relations. One way to win the client's trust is when the vendor shows the commitment to fulfil all contractual obligations and exerts additional efforts to develop an environment of trust that is conducive to cooperation and coordination. Another critical thing that vendors must consider is requesting client organizations to integrate flexibility into contractual terms and conditions that may enable both organizations to accommodate unexpected changes by coordinating and cooperating rather than punishing each other.

Overall, the above recommendations are based on the primary research results. If successfully implemented by client and vendor organizations, the recommendations can significantly reduce misunderstandings, enhance relational governance, and ultimately lead towards outsourcing success. The findings also contribute to the existing literature, as the study proposes a conceptual framework that explains how vendors and client organizations can communicate and coordinate when an e-service outsourcing relationship is formed. The conceptual framework also explains the trust and commitment mechanisms by outlining the trust antecedents and consequences. As the conceptual framework derives strong support from literature and is backed with empirical evidence, it further enhances the theoretical value of this research. However, it is essential to note that the above-proposed findings hold specific applicability for the vendor and client organizations involved in e-service outsourcing within the UK. The generalizability of the proposed findings could be weak for organizations outside the UK or private sector and manufacturing organizations. In the next section, the researcher explains all fundamental limitations that could affect the findings' applicability. The study limitations also set the scope and context of this research. Based on study limitations, the study proposes future research suggestions that could be considered to extend the work further and make valuable additions to the literature.

6.2.1 Recommendations on trust building

The overall survey findings suggest that e-service organizations consider outsourcing a viable option to manage their e-services, particularly when they lack the skills and resources to meet customers' expectations. The e-service outsourcing trend in the UK is on the rise, and public organizations should benefit from this option as it will enable them to focus on their core business activities. However, findings also suggest that e-service outsourcing must not be done without enhancing the firms' readiness for change. Although by outsourcing e-services, firms release themselves from many duties, the outsourcing contract brings new business relationships, which must be effectively managed to achieve the desired objectives. So, before making the outsourcing decision, the findings suggest public service organizations invest time and efforts in finding a reliable partner because investing time in finding a trustworthy and reliable partner will be less time-consuming than outsourcing services to a new partner with whom time and resources need to be spent to build the initial trust.

Findings further suggest that it is only possible in some cases to find a trustworthy partner that public organizations can trust. In such a case, it is essential to build the initial trust, laying the foundation for later ongoing trust. The primary research findings suggest that public organizations develop initial trust through frequent communication.

This can be done by establishing communication plan at the beginning of the contract and through all phases of the project. Also, both parties should provide the required resources and create multiple communication channels; in-person and on-line. Also, efforts should be made to decrease physical and cultural barriers

Client organizations are recommended to select vendors with good reputations towards whom the management has positive feelings, as such feelings will make communication easier during initial trust building. To develop initial trust, the communication must be transparent, and partners should show a respectful attitude towards each other. The initial reputation building, open and more frequent interactions, having prior positive feelings towards each other, and a clear understanding of contractual terms are some factors that are vital for initial trust building.

Initial trust could be developed by openly interacting with the outsourcing partners, and clarity must be brought into the contractual terms and conditions to avoid misunderstanding. keeping the communications open in all channels and levels with

honesty will lead to trust and respect between both parties. Once initial trust is developed, parties must not stop exerting efforts, as it only lays the foundation for ongoing trust, which also needs to be effectively managed. For ongoing trust, the findings are essential to the communication, which must be clear, frequent, open and transparent.

6.2.2 Recommendations to improve communications.

After presenting the conclusion to each research objective, the researcher presents some recommendations to the relevant stakeholders about how they can more effectively manage their outsourcing relations to achieve the desired objectives of e-service outsourcing:

Findings further suggest outsourcing partners to manage communication as one team, and to do this; vendors must be regularly invited to attend the team meetings at the client organization. Both- parties should document everything to make communication clear and reduce the chances of misunderstanding.

Many times, firms outsource e-services to the outsourcing partners that operate in a different work environment. The structural and cultural differences sometimes make communication difficult. So, both parties need to understand and respect the organizational culture differences—a well-balanced formal and informal communication strategy tailored to the cultural differences suits here. Findings also suggest outsourcing partners document meaningful discussions so they can be referred to later without confusion. In cases where the cultural differences are high, both parties should develop acceptable communication strategies in both work cultures.

Communication strategies should focus on the following:

- Define the relationship communication objectives and what each part want to achieve from these communications.
- Specify the communication team from each party taking into consideration to have same level of managerial levels and knowledge of the contract terms and conditions.
- Setting the standards of the communications and terms used to make the message clearer and more concise.
- Create plan that contains the required resources and timeline.

- Always evaluate the communication objectives and strategies and adjust if necessary.

Another critical recommendation to enhance communication is understanding and aligning the strategic priorities of outsourcing partners. When these strategic priorities are misaligned, it creates a conflict of interest, which ultimately reduces the outsourcing success chances.

Aligning the strategic priorities can be achieved by finding the common long-term objectives and setting a unified objectives for both parties like learning objectives and system continuous improvement. The alignment can also be achieved by making the satisfaction of the end customers is the priority for both of them.

A key challenge identified during the interviews was the structural barrier hindering communication. To resolve this challenge, both parties should sit and openly discuss how communication is affected by structural barriers and possible ways to resolve this issue. Striking the right balance between formal and informal communication modes is essential to ensure smooth information flow, vital for outsourcing success. When cultural and structural hurdles are not removed, it increases the coordination cost, so the parties start avoiding coordinating with each other, and from there, grounds for possible misunderstandings get set. So, reducing the costs of communicating and coordinating with each other from the early stages is essential.

Another key recommendation is to keep communication open-ended so that feedback can be taken from both sides. The feedback should be taken constructively, and parties must not hesitate to accept constructive criticism to exert mutual efforts to improve the performance. During interviews, the interviewees from client organizations mentioned that they face communication challenges due to a lack of staff training in communication and collaboration. So, findings suggest that companies arrange communication training for employees responsible for communication with outsourcing partners. The training should help employees learn how to balance informal and formal communication, handle difficult situations (mainly when a possible misunderstanding occurs), and balance control and coordination to strengthen the relationship besides implementing the contract.

Results further suggested that communication challenges arise from technological differences in some cases, as vendor and client organizations use different communication technologies to coordinate. This technological difference makes communication difficult, mainly when both parties are willing to find a mutually acceptance solution. To resolve this challenge, it is essential to use the communication technologies that employees in both organizations are familiar with and can easily use those tools for inter-organizational interaction. Specific attention must be paid to exploring multiple communication modes to overcome the communication failure that may emerge from unreliable networks.

6.2.3 Recommendations to boost cooperative behaviour

It is essential to adopt a cooperative attitude to strengthen the relationship and make outsourcing success a mutually desired goal. The findings suggest outsourcing partners adopt a flexible and cooperative attitude to manage the trust, and both parties should demonstrate this flexibility in their routine interactions. Another key recommendation is that outsourcing partners (client and vendor organizations) should understand how they can discourage engaging in opportunistic behaviour and how relations could be strengthened without affecting the contract implementation. Even if a minor unintentional violation occurs, the outsourcing partners are recommended to prefer relationship building over executing the contract by imposing a fine for violation.

Findings further suggest that the success of e-service outsourcing also depends on the outsourcing partners' willingness to share knowledge, as they make more well-informed decisions by sharing valuable market insights. To encourage knowledge sharing, outsourcing partners should first develop mutually beneficial objectives. Management should consider incentivizing knowledge-sharing behaviour to make engagement in knowledge-sharing behaviour attractive for both parties. It is also essential to communicate how both parties can benefit from sharing knowledge. However, management needs to foster a positive and collaborative mindset to do this. Another key recommendation is to invest in the supportive tools and processes that facilitate knowledge sharing. The training could also be arranged to equip the employees with the skills needed to share knowledge effectively. Moreover, management on both sides should coordinate to develop supportive knowledge-sharing

mechanisms that could encourage two-way knowledge flow. Management on both sides should also offer clear policy support, as many times, employees hesitate to share knowledge as they have unclear ideas about whether their organization will support or discourage them from sharing valuable information.

Effective management of initial and ongoing trust enables the companies to strengthen their commitment to outsourcing partners. The study results consider trust and commitment as two keys to e-service outsourcing success compared to the other factors (knowledge sharing, communication, and cooperative behaviour). Strong trust between outsourcing partners strengthens their mutual commitment, increasing the e-service outsourcing success chances. Both- client and vendor organizations need to demonstrate their commitment. The client organization can demonstrate its commitment to fulfilling outsourcing contracts by exerting full efforts to understand the client's expectations entirely.

6.2.4 Recommendations to enhance knowledge sharing.

Concerning knowledge sharing, the interview findings revealed that sometimes, vendor organizations may need help finding a direct incentive to share information with the client organization. However, even in such cases, findings suggest vendors adopt a holistic view and should share the knowledge to help the client by taking discretionary action. According to the results, such action will lay a strong foundation for trust, which is key to outsourcing success. Interviewees mentioned a lack of competent staff that could develop effective, trust-based relations with the client organization in uncertain and challenging situations and on an ongoing basis. While training, specific attention must be given to enhancing these skill areas. Findings further suggest that many employees in vendor organizations consider the IT transition between vendor and client organizations to be challenging. To smoothly handle such a transition, vendor organizations should appoint a separate team that may handle the technical and behavioural challenges associated with such a transition.

6.2.5 Recommendations to encourage commitment.

Vendor organizations can also show their commitment by driving a sense of accountability to relevant stakeholders. When both sides work to strengthen the commitment, it encourages both sides to avoid engaging in opportunistic behaviour and instead prefer cooperation over competition to achieve mutually set goals. It is also essential to demonstrate such commitment from top to bottom, as findings suggest that it only offers the desired results when translated from top to bottom. At the operation level, findings suggest that client and vendor organizations communicate the need for support and cooperation to make outsourcing successful.

The successful implementation of the above-proposed recommendations can significantly increase the success of e-service outsourcing success chances in the UK. During interviews, the interviewees were also asked to mention the overall challenges they face in managing outsourcing relations, and the study got a diverse response. Interviewees were also asked to share some solutions to resolve the identified challenges. The findings suggest that vendor and client organizations should devise conflict resolution mechanisms so that timely action can be taken whenever any misunderstanding arises. Conflict can be resolved without affecting the contract. Results have indicated that distrust reduces the outsourcing partners' willingness to *get along* with each other, which weakens their commitment and ultimately reduces the outsourcing success chances.

Another key improvement area is investment in supportive tools and technologies to manage relationships with outsourcing partners effectively. Organizations could invest in relation-building tools and technologies that facilitate inter-organizational interaction and relationship management and assist client organizations in ensuring effective coordination and control. As it is the human resources responsible for managing the outsourcing relations, findings suggest that vendor and client organizations periodically arrange training to equip human resources with the skills and competencies required to ensure effective relationship management. It is essential to involve the vendor in regular meetings to develop team cohesion and make that team responsible for making outsourcing successful.

6.3 Limitations and future research suggestions

This research work has some limitations that must be outlined here to inform the reader about how the proposed findings could be applied in the real world. The first limitation is the restricted geographic area where the empirical investigation is held. The researcher has specifically selected the public sector organizations from the UK to evaluate the relational governance mechanisms of e-service outsourcing. It means that organizations outside the UK need to consider the findings by considering contextual differences. Another fundamental limitation is that the researcher only focused on the public sector organizations involved in outsourcing. At the same time, many private sector organizations from the service sector are also actively engaged in outsourcing activities. Here, the contextual difference between private and public sector limit the findings' generalizability for other companies.

As this study was completed in a limited time, the researcher could only collect data from a limited sample size, affecting the proposed findings' external validity. The sample size from vendor organizations was minimal. Moreover, instead of collecting the actual data about outsourcing success/failure, the researcher relied on the participants' opinions and perceptions about the asked questions. Outsourcing success derives influence from different technical and non-technical factors, but the current study specifically focused on the non-technical, relation-building related factors. Moreover, outsourcing contracts involve multiple stakeholders, but the current study only collected data from client and vendor organizations. These limitations set the basis for further research.

Based on the above limitations, the study recommends that future researchers conduct research outside the UK to understand how relational governance mechanisms are handled by public sector organizations involved in outsourcing in other countries. Future studies may also compare the results for developed and developing countries to understand how the macro-environment of developing and developed countries influences outsourcing success. Another key future research area could be to explore how vendor organizations whose client organizations remain unwilling to interact more could handle the situation by improving their relation-building mechanisms. Future studies may also evaluate whether an initial trust in the vendor plays any role in ensuring the ongoing trust at later stages. Studies may specifically focus on exploring

how control and coordination mechanisms could be ensured without engaging in opportunistic behaviour and affecting the contract implementation.

Future studies may evaluate how mutual dependence can encourage or discourage outsourcing partners from sharing knowledge. In-depth interviews could be conducted to evaluate how structural and cultural hurdles could be tackled to encourage a smooth, two-way knowledge flow. Future researchers may also collect data from a larger sample size to enhance the validity of the proposed results. Lastly, future researchers may explore other (internal and external) contextual factors influencing outsourcing partners' ability to ensure effective relational governance. It will enhance the proposed conceptual model's accuracy, validity and predictability. It will offer a more comprehensive understanding to the researchers and practitioners interested in studying the relational governance mechanisms of e-service outsourcing.

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Appendices

1. Interview guideline- Vendor organization

- Kindly briefly introduce yourself by mentioning your role and experience at your current organization.
- How does effective communication play its role in developing trust between outsourcing partners?
- Does management at your organization adopt a cooperative and flexible attitude to manage trust-based relationships with outsourcing partners, if so, how such cooperation and flexibility is demonstrated?
- How does trust between outsourcing partners influence the outsourcing partners' willingness to share knowledge?
- Kindly mention the most important challenges your firm faces in managing relationships with client organizations that outsourced e-services.
- Please share some suggestions about how relational governance could be improved to increase the success of e-service outsourcing.

2- Participant Information Sheet - Vendor

Research Project Title

Factors influencing the success of outsourcing in e-governance- an empirical investigation of public services in the United Kingdom

Invitation

You are being invited to take part in this research project. Before you decide, please understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully and discuss it with others. Ask us if anything needs

clarification or if you want more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the project's purpose?

Due to the rapid development in information and communication technologies, there is a growing interest towards applying the latest ICTs to improve the responsiveness, performance and quality of the public service sector in cooperation with the private sector. Hence, this empirical research aims to critically evaluate the factors that influence effective relationship management in outsourcing electronically provided services.

This research study aims to provide knowledge about the people (perceptions, commitment, cooperative behaviour) and management (trust and communication management mechanisms) related factors that influence the quality of relationships with outsourcing partners. UK public service firms can utilize the knowledge gained from this research to increase the chances of outsourcing success through effective relationship management.

Why Have I been invited?

The researcher has chosen to recruit Employees working in private organizations that are outsourced from a public organization to provide their electronic services. The study has a strong relevance to your experience with the Public organizations.

What would be involved for me?

You will be asked to participate in an online interview, which the researcher estimates will take 30-45 mins. The interview will be scheduled at your time convenience. It will be a semi-structured discussion about your experience with the Public organizations.

Do I have to take part? What will happen to the data I provide?

Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. You have the absolute right to withdraw from the study without a reason. Your identity will be kept confidential and anonymous at all stages of the study. Similarly, any collected information from the interview will be stored in the researcher's Password-protected One-drive and

destroyed upon the study's completion. All responses will be held by the UK General Data Protection Regulation (UK GDPR), tailored by the Data Protection Act 2018.

What do I need to do if I wish to take part?

Please read this information sheet carefully before signing the attached consent form. If you are happy to participate in the study, please sign the consent form and return it to the researcher.

Does this study need ethical approval?

This study has been reviewed and approved by the University of the West of Scotland's Research Ethics Committee.

What if I have any concerns or queries?

For further information or clarification regarding the study, please do not hesitate to contact me by email [REDACTED] or by Phone at : [REDACTED]. You can also contact my lead supervisor Dr. Allison Wylde via email address: [REDACTED]

Yours sincerely,

Khaled M. Aldajah

Doctoral Student

University of the West Of Scotland / London Campus

2. Survey questionnaire

This research study explores the effectiveness of relational governance in the e-service outsourcing context by analyzing the factors that determine relationship

strength with partners involved in e-service outsourcing and evaluating the relationship between relational governance and e-service outsourcing success. This survey targets middle-level managers working in the targeted public service organizations and actively managing the outsourcing relationships of the target population. You are requested to participate in this survey as your input is significant for the current research purpose. Participation in this survey remains voluntary, so you do not need to provide any justification if you reject this invitation. If you accept the survey invitation, we assure you that your privacy will be fully protected, the shared data in raw and identifiable form will remain confidential, and anonymity will be ensured. It will take a maximum 15 minutes to fill survey form. If you feel uncomfortable responding to any items, you may skip them. Thank you so much in advance for your time and co-operation.

General questions

Please mention your gender

- Male
- Female

Please mention your age

- 18 to 33 years
- 34 to 49 years
- 50 to 60 years
- Above 60 years

Please mention the length of stay at your current organization

- Less than 2 year
- 2 to 5 years
- 5.1 to 10 years
- Above 10 years

Please mention your role at the organization

- Outsourcing manager
- Relationship manager

- Middle manager
- Other (please mention)

Instructions to fill out the survey form:

Please share your opinions according to the following Likert scale:

Strong disagreement -1- disagreement -2- indifferent -3- agreement -4- strong agreement -5

Factors Influencing Relational Governance Effectiveness:

Communication	1	2	3	4	5
There exists an open and transparent communication between vendor and client organization					
There is a well-balanced formal and informal communication between outsourcing partners					
The two-way communication encourages the outsourcing partners to openly share and discuss the concerns					

Co-operative behaviour	1	2	3	4	5
Both- client and vendor organizations help and support each other					
The outsourcing relationships are managed by adopting the co-operative rather than competitive strategies					
Client and vendor organizations frequently interact with each other to evaluate how things can be better handled					
There exists positive inter-dependence between client and vendor organization					

Trust	1	2	3	4	5
Vendor is trustworthy					
Vendor has competence to offer what outsourcing contract requires					
Vendor makes decision that is beneficial for the client organization					

Vendor always provides assistance to the client organization					
Client organization shares a trust based friendly relationship with the outsourcing partner/vendor					
Client and vendor organizations do not hesitate to transact when specifications are vague					
Client and vendor organizations do not use opportunities that arise at expense of each other					
Each outsourcing partner has been even-handed during outsourcing contract negotiations					

Knowledge sharing	1	2	3	4	5
Client and vendor organizations frequently share the knowledge about business processes and procedures					
The frequent exchange of information helps both- vendor and client organizations in planning and implementation of business strategies					
Both- client and vendor organizations share know-how based on their extensive experience					
Company has learned a lot about the technology/processes held by the outsourcing partner					
Organization has decreased the initial technological dependence on partner since outsourcing contract beginning					
The technical know-how held by the outsourcing partner is assimilated by client organization, and has contributed to other business areas of the client organization					

Commitment	1	2	3	4	5
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Outsourcing partners share strong commitment to fulfil the contractual terms					
Each outsourcing partner is strongly committed to demonstrate behaviour required for fulfilment of inter-connected goals					
The commitment to fulfil each other's expectations reflect into business dealings and behaviour of outsourcing partners					

Mutual dependency	1	2	3	4	5
The organizational performance of the client organization depends on the vendor performance					
The organizational performance of the vendor depends on the client organization					
There exists high mutual dependency between vendor and client organization as both have interconnected objectives					

Motivations to make e-service outsourcing decision

Motivations	1	2	3	4	5
The outsourcing decision was made primarily to reduce the costs					
The outsourcing decision was made primarily because there was no required technical/human expertise to effectively deliver e-services					
The outsourcing decision was made primarily because management considered outsourcing a way to improve the e-service quality					
The outsourcing decision was made primarily because organization wanted to learn from the outsourcing partner and enhance its capabilities					
The outsourcing decision was made due to high administrative burden					

Other					
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Overall environmental tendencies:

Kindly select the most suitable option that most accurately defines your motivation to make outsourcing decision:

1. Cost reduction
2. Lack of resources
3. Service quality improvement
4. Learning from partner
5. Reduce administrative burden

Relational governance effectiveness	1	2	3	4	5
Strong social capital is created and used to strengthen the relation between outsourcing partners					
The enforcement of promises, obligations and expectations occur through social processes					
Social processes that are involved in the enforcement of promises, obligations and expectations tend to promote the norms of solidarity and flexibility among outsourcing partners					
Outsourcing partners share highly collaborative relationship with each other					
Short and long-term goals/plans are frequently shared between outsourcing partners					
Overall, outsourcing partners share a strong, effective governed business relation with each other					

E-service outsourcing success	1	2	3	4	5
Our organization is fully satisfied with the overall benefits availed by outsourcing e-services					
Our organization has fully achieved/expects to fully achieve the desired benefits from e-service outsourcing					
Benefits of e-service outsourcing significantly outweigh the associated challenges					
E-service outsourcing has significantly enhanced the service quality					
Through e-service outsourcing, our (client) organization is in a better position to focus on other more important matters of strategic concern.					
E-service outsourcing has significantly enhanced our (client) organization's IT competencies					
E-service outsourcing facilitates the sharing of know-how from training, education and work experience, which develops organization's competencies and capabilities					
Our organization considers e-service outsourcing experience to be overall successful					

3. Consent Form

Title of Project:

Factors influencing the success of outsourcing in e-governance- an empirical investigation of public services in United Kingdom

Please initial box:

- 1 I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated xxx for the above study with the relevant information and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

- 2 I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.

- 3 I understand that my responses will be anonymised and that confidentiality will be ensured.
- 4 I agree to take part in the above study.

Your signature will certify that you have voluntarily decided to take part in this research study having read and understood the information in the sheet for participants. It will also certify that you have had adequate opportunity to discuss the study with the researcher and that all questions have been answered to your satisfaction.

Name of Participant:

Signature:

Date:

Name of researcher: Khaled Aldajah

Signature:

Supervisor's details

Name: Dr. Allison Wylde **Email:** _____

Date:

1 copy for participant and 1 for researcher

4. RESEARCH THESIS SUBMISSION (RTS) FORM

**POSTGRADUATE RESEARCH DEGREE RESEARCH THESIS
SUBMISSION (RTS) FORM**

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

IMPORTANT NOTES: (1) The form must be completed and signed electronically before submitting to [REDACTED] (2) Soft-bind a hard copy of the completed and signed form into the thesis before submitting it to the Doctoral College. The confirmation of submitted thesis will be acknowledged by email and this form will be signed/dated on receiving the

School	Please select.	Campus	Please select.	Degree	Please select.
Title of thesis – as proposed on TEA form (Sentence case)	Factors influencing the success of outsourcing in e-governance- an empirical investigation of public services in United Kingdom				
Title of submitted thesis – if different (Sentence case)					
Candidate's full name	Khaled Mahmoud Salman Aldajah		Banner ID	B00355777	
Candidate's signature	[REDACTED]		Date	03/09/2022	

thesis.

The thesis is my own work, with other work adequately referenced.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Yes	No
Other work has been adequately referenced.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Yes	No
The thesis is the correct version for submission and is the same version as any electronic versions submitted (IMPORTANT NOTE: it is the responsibility of the candidate to ensure that the correct version of the thesis is submitted)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Yes	No
The above stated name is as it appears in the thesis, passport and as it will appear on the official award certificate and record. (IMPORTANT NOTE: it is the responsibility of the candidate to ensure that the correct name is submitted)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Yes	No
The above stated title of the submitted thesis is as it appears in the thesis and as it will appear on the official award certificate and record. (IMPORTANT NOTE: it is the responsibility of the candidate to ensure that the correct title of the thesis is submitted)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Yes	No

As the student of the University of the West of Scotland I maintain a high standard of personal conduct, co-operate with all members of staff and agree to abide by the University's Regulations.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Yes	No
My thesis as detailed above should be made available via the institutional repository, subject to such conditions as the Librarian may require.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Yes	No
I confirm that plagiarism has been considered and excluded using Turnitin (the University approved software).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Yes	No
I confirm that I have followed the University style and standard of presentation of the thesis.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Yes	No

Submitted by (name)			
Submitted by (name)		Khaled Mahmoud Salman Aldajah	
Signature of individual submitting		Date submitted	03/09/2022

Received by Doctoral College (name)			
Received by Doctoral College (name)			
Submission method <i>(e.g. handed in, posted internally, posted externally)</i>		E-thesis submitted?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
			<input type="checkbox"/> No
Signature		Date received	Please enter a date

1- Ethical Approval

I confirm I have read the UWS and my School Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship.

Principal Investigator

The information supplied above is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, accurate. I have read the university ethics guidelines and clearly understand my obligations and the rights of study participants, particularly in relation to obtaining valid consent.

Signed:: This form was signed by Khaled Mahmoud Salman Aldajah

[Redacted Signature]

on 25/07/2021 16::13

Supervisor/Director of Studies

I support the above application and I agree to supervise the work.

Signed:: This form was signed by Dr Nicholas Telford

[Redacted Signature]

on 20/09/2021 17::53